

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Deliverable 3.3

Assessment of Soil Threats and Ecosystem Services from each MS with the harmonized procedures

EJP SOIL
SERENA

Due date of deliverable: 31.05.2024
Actual submission date: 28.06.2024

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EJP SOIL

Project title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Project website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020

Project duration: 60 months

Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER: D3.3
DELIVERABLE TITLE: Assessment of Soil Threats and Ecosystem Services from each MS with the harmonized procedures
DELIVERABLE TYPE: Report
WORK PACKAGE N: WP3
WORK PACKAGE TITLE: National SoilHUBS: Assessment of (bundles of) Soil functions/threats/ecosystem services at different scales
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DISSEMINATION LEVEL: PU

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13991088](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13991088)

Suggested reference:

Hessel R, G Buttafuoco, E Medina-Roldán, D Smiraglia, J Coblinski, L Kukk, B Lemerrier, S Pindral, J Reyes Rojas, R Lorenzetti, C Pesch, K Amalevičiūtė-Volungė, S Asins, F Assennato, A Astover, Z Bakacsi, A Benó, G Bondi, T Brunner, S Callewaert, K Cockx, L Congedo, J Cuijsen, P Csontos, P De Fioravante, E Doñate, A Fahy, V Feiza, C B Foldal, A Gaillot, L Gardin, C Gedeon, D Josipovic, P Kassai, T Kikas, M Kocsis, A Laborczi, D Luts, J Makovníková, I Marinosci, D Montagne, M Munafò, K Oorts, L O’Sullivan, B Pálka, L Pásztor, E Putku, N Riitano, N Saby, E Schmaltz, V Shahrokh, B Szabó, G Szatmári, M Trip, F Ungaro, J Volungevičius, T Weninger, R Žydelis. 2024. Assessment of Soil Threats and Ecosystem Services from each MS with the harmonized procedures. SERENA deliverable 3.3, 253 pp. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13991088](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13991088)

ABSTRACT

Cookbooks for the evaluation of soil threats (ST), soil-based ecosystem services (SES) and bundles based on indicators were developed for soil erosion, soil erosion control, SOC loss, GHG and climate control, soil sealing and bundles of these SES/ST. Cookbooks were applied in a variable number by member states involved in SERENA from the minimum of 4 applications for bundles to a maximum of 11 applications for soil erosion. The maps resulting from these applications were compared to earlier results from member states, when these were available. When differences were observed potential explanatory factors were listed. A fuller evaluation of the cookbook results is planned in WP1 in collaboration with stakeholders. The results of the cookbooks applications showed that despite the harmonisation efforts made in the cookbook, there still remained variability in the way in which different MS applied the cookbooks, e.g. due to differences in available data. Besides, a comparison with earlier data proved difficult in a number of cases, as such a comparison can best be done if not too many factors differ between the old application and the new one. On the other hand, this also illustrates that benefits can be obtained for evaluation of ST, SES and bundles if assessments based on indicators can be standardised more. Recommendations for improvement of the cookbooks were collected, and should help to make the cookbooks even better suited for future applications.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

EU	European Union
MS	Member States
SES	Soil-based Ecosystem Service
ST	Soil Threat
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction and objectives

Soils are crucial for economic and environmental well-being because they form the basis for agricultural production and also provide a range of other ecosystem services (Bispo et al, submitted). For example, healthy soils provide better water purification and regulation, buffering and cycling of nutrients (Lori et al 2018), more biodiversity (Rillig et al 2019, Oehlmann et al 2021) and carbon sequestration, cycling and regulation (Bossio et al 2020, Griscom et al 2017). However, these services are affected by soil threats that may lead to physical, chemical and biological degradation of the soil (Attard et al, 2011; Cassman 1999, Gasso et al 2013; Sapkota et al 2012; Hessel et al 2022). This important role of soils is increasingly recognised, with high level objectives at EU scale (e.g. EU 2020) and meeting the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) being reliant in large part on sustainable land and soil management (Bouma et al 2019).

Soil quality/health is often described using soil indicators (e.g. EEA 2023, Bispo et al, submitted). These are soil properties that can indicate the degree to which soils are affected by soil threats (ST) and to what extent they can provide soil-based ecosystem services (SES). While soil quality is the potential capability of a given soil type and land use, soil health is its actual (current) capacity to deliver goods and services (Faber et al 2022). As already mentioned by Van Camp et al (2004) the importance of monitoring indicators is that they can give information on how soils are changing over time, e.g. whether the health of a soil is improving, deteriorating or staying the same under a particular use and management practice. Thus, indicators are essential to support public policies and for assessing their efficiency and success.

To be able to use indicators for evaluation purposes, reference values, thresholds and target values are needed. The reference is a value for an indicator representing its normal background value for defined local circumstances, usually defined within the state boundaries of a country, and referring in general to a context of soil type, climatic zone and elevation, and land use and management (Faber et al 2022). The target value represents the desired status for a particular indicator or set of indicators given specific ecological conditions, land use and objectives for use (Faber et al 2022). The threshold value is the value that marks the boundary between healthy conditions and degraded conditions. As different countries use different methodologies to evaluate ST/SES, and different thresholds etc, it is difficult to compare the status of soils in different countries. A further complicating factor is that combinations of certain ST/SES co-occur in space or time, so that different ST/SES cannot always be evaluated independently. These combinations are called bundles of ST/SES.

Within the SERENA project one of the main aims is to evaluate indicators of soil threats (ST), soil-based ecosystem services (SES) and bundles of ST/SES, based on indicators. This is done at EU-scale and at member state (MS) scale. This document deals with the application at MS scale (in some cases regional scale). For evaluation at MS scale the aim was to perform this evaluation in all MS involved in SERENA in similar fashion, so that comparison between countries will be facilitated. A second aim was to compare the results obtained in this way with earlier results from the different countries. To achieve these aims, cookbooks had to be developed that describe how to evaluate the different ST/SES/bundles.

The following steps were necessary to apply the cookbooks:

1. Selection of ST/SES that are relevant for SERENA (SERENA D2.2 Antón et al 2022)
2. Selection of indicator to be used for each ST/SES (SERENA D2.3.1 Montagne et al 2024)

3. Selection and harmonization of methodology to evaluate the selected indicators (SERENA D2.3.1, Montagne et al 2024)
4. Writing the Cookbook that describes how to apply the selected methodology (SERENA D2.3.2, Buttafuoco et al 2024)
5. Application of cookbook at MS scale
6. Comparison of cookbook results with earlier MS results

Steps 1-4 have been done by other work packages 2 and 3 in SERENA, and have been described elsewhere (see references above). The objectives of this deliverable are to present the results of the applications of the cookbooks, and to compare these with earlier results from the member states. A final step, that is not described in this document, as it will be performed later is an evaluation of the cookbook results by stakeholders, looking at questions like: Is the cookbook result better than earlier results? Are cookbook results of good quality? How realistic are they? Etc. The results of that evaluation will be included in work from WP1.

2 Methodology

As the development and application of cookbooks for different ST/SES/bundles involved several WPs of SERENA, an intertask working group on cookbooks was started. Within this working group, separate groups were established to develop cookbooks for specific ST, SES and bundles. This finally resulted in development of cookbooks for:

1. Soil erosion and soil erosion control
2. SOC loss
3. GHG and climate control
4. Soil sealing
5. Bundles of ST/SES

The reasons for choosing these ST/SES have been described elsewhere (Antón et al 2022), but can be summarized as having been influenced by 1) the importance that is attached to different ST/SES and to bundles within SERENA, 2) the interest of MS in specific ST/SES and in bundles, 3) the possibility to evaluate specific ST/SES/Bundles and 4) The availability of expertise and time within SERENA.

The cookbooks provide a guide to MS in using harmonized indicators and approaches for assessing the STs/SESs of interest. However, flexibility was left to MS to define how to apply such indicators and methodologies (i.e. equations or models) to deal with MS-specific conditions related to data availability, specific software/GIS platform, soil and climate context, etc. The different cookbooks describe the methodology that was used to evaluate the different ST/SES (see D2.3.2); this part of methodology is therefore not repeated here. Instead, the focus here is on the overall methodology to develop and apply cookbooks.

Table 2.1. Stages in development and application of cookbooks

Stage	Tasks	Result
1. Critical analysis of methodologies	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Review available MS info in SERENA (Foldal et al 2022, Michel et al 2023) 2. Review literature and other sources 	Selection of methodology to be included in cookbook
2. Develop cookbook	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Write cookbook for selected methodology 2. Revise cookbook based on feedback MS/region test 	Final version of cookbook, which could be applied by all MS
3. Test and apply cookbook	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Test draft cookbook 2. Provide comments to development group 3. Apply final version cookbook 	Maps of ST/SES at MSs scale following the cookbooks that can be evaluated by stakeholders (T1.3) be compared to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - current national results (from T3.1) - results at EU scale from SEREMA WP5

Three stages have been defined in development and application of the cookbook (see table 2.1).

Most of the steps described in Table 2.1 have been performed by the working groups for development of the different cookbooks, but application of the final version of the cookbooks was done by all MS that indicated willingness to apply these cookbooks.

Apart from the choice for development of certain cookbooks in SERENA, participating MS also had a choice on which cookbooks they would like to apply. Earlier in the project, it was already investigated which MS were potentially interested to evaluate which ST/SES/bundles. This was one of the factors that was considered in the decision on which cookbooks to develop. This was, however, done at a stage within the project in which it was not yet clear what application of cookbooks would entail in terms of data needs, software, expertise and time. Table 2.2 shows which cookbooks have finally been applied by which MS, illustrating that all cookbooks have been applied by at least several MS and that the total number of applications was 41. Table 2.3 shows the cases where comparison with current national map is possible, based on information from Foldal et al (2022) and Michel et al (2023). It shows that in several cases there were no earlier data available, so that comparison is not possible. It also shows that for all ST/SES there were earlier data available from at least one MS.

Table 2.2. ST/SES/bundles evaluated by MS.

Cookbook	Country																	Total
	Austria	Belgium	Czech republic	Denmark	Estonia	France	Hungary	Ireland	Italy	Latvia	Lithuania	Netherlands	Poland	Portugal	Slovakia	Spain		
Soil erosion	V	V				V	V	V	V		V	V	V		V	V	11	
Soil erosion control							V		V				V		V		4	
SOC loss		V			V	V	V	V	V		V		V	V			9	
GHG/climate regulation			V		V			V	V			V	V			V	7	
Soil sealing	V	V						V	V			V				V	6	
Bundles			V		V				V				V				4	
Total	2	3	2	0	3	2	3	4	6	0	2	3	5	1	2	3	41	

Table 2.3. ST/SES/bundles for which a comparison is possible. Brown indicates there is a cookbook application but no earlier results to compare it with.

Cookbook	Country																	Total
	Austria	Belgium	Czech republic	Denmark	Estonia	France	Hungary	Ireland	Italy	Latvia	Lithuania	Netherlands	Poland	Portugal	Slovakia	Spain		
Soil erosion	V	V				V	V		V		V		V		V	V	9	
Soil erosion control							V		V						V		3	
SOC loss		V						V	V		V		V				6	
GHG/climate regulation					V			V	V				V			V	5	
Soil sealing	V	V						V	V							V	5	
Bundles													V				1	
Total	2	3	0	0	1	1	3	3	5	0	2	0	4	0	2	3	29	

Cookbooks were provided to MS by the coordinators of the cookbooks; who also provided assistance in application if needed.

A template (Annex 1) was developed for reporting on the cookbook application and the comparison with earlier results (Foldal et al 2022, Michel et al 2023). The template also addresses a comparison of cookbook results with earlier results, but restricts this to a factual comparison (identifying differences and some possible explanations of these), as a fuller evaluation of the results will be done in WP1. As a comparison is only possible when both cookbook results and earlier results are available, the number of MS/cookbook combinations for which this can be done is smaller than the number of cookbook applications (compare tables 2.2 and 2.3).

The main part of this deliverable consists of the reports that have been provided by MS for the different ST/SES/bundles. Chapters 3-7 provide the reports for the different ST/SES/bundles. Chapter 8 compares the results of the different cookbooks, and synthesises these where possible.

3 Soil erosion and soil erosion control

The indicator selected to evaluate soil erosion and soil erosion control is soil loss by water erosion (Montagne et al 2023). The methodology to evaluate this indicator was the revised universal loss equation (RUSLE) (Renard et al 1997), which estimates the mean annual soil loss rates by sheet and rill erosion. It does not simulate other forms of water erosion (such as gully erosion), and also does not model deposition.

The RUSLE model consists of the following equation:

$$A = R \times K \times LS \times C \times P$$

where A (Mg or t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) is the annual average soil loss, R (MJ mm ha⁻¹ h⁻¹ yr⁻¹) is the rainfall-runoff erosivity factor, K (Mg or t ha h ha⁻¹ MJ⁻¹ mm⁻¹) is the soil erodibility factor, LS (dimensionless) is the slope length and slope steepness factor, C (dimensionless) is the cover-management factor and P (dimensionless) is the support practices factor.

Soil erosion control was evaluated by setting the C-factor (cover management factor) to 1 (meaning that there is no reduction in erosion rate due to cover), and comparing the results of that simulation with a simulation that used a C-factor based on land use, crop type and management. The difference in soil erosion is then taken to be the erosion that is prevented by the presence of vegetation. It should be realized that in this way, the current situation is compared to a situation in which the soil is bare. This is in accordance with the definition of the C-factor but is not a measure of the effect that appropriate management would have on erosion compared to current agricultural practices.

The cookbook for soil erosion and soil erosion control provides a detailed description of how the different factors of the RUSLE equation were calculated (Buttafuoco et al., 2024). The following sections present the RUSLE applications that have been done within the framework of SERENA.

3.1 Austria

Thomas Brunner, Thomas Weninger, Elmar Schmaltz

Notes: JRC maps are assumed to be in EPSG: 3035 (?); All maps were projected into EPSG: 31287, resampled to 25m resolution and snapped to the grid used in JRC LS-factor map. Some border cells have unassigned values. A small enclave of the Austrian territory (Außerfern) is not present in all of the datasets used and therefore omitted.

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
Land use	Corine Land Cover (CLC) 2018	Initially vector, typical raster resolution is 100 * 100 m	Open data https://www.data.gv.at/katalog/dataset/76617316-b9e6-4bcd-ba09-e328b578fed2
Soil	JRC maps for sand, silt and clay contents (based on LUCAS)	500 * 500 m	JRC data obtained per request form https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/topsoil-physical-properties-europe-based-lucas-topsoil-data

	SOC map from Umweltbundesamt (UBA)		(Ballabio et al., 2016) UBA data can be obtained from: https://doi.org/10.60669/g6wg-x975 (Wenzel et al., 2022)
Climate	SPARTACUS monthly rainfall sums averaged over 1991-2020 period (own calculations)	1000 * 1000 m	Data available from https://doi.org/10.60669/k7rq-6378 (Hiebl and Frei, 2016) (Hiebl and Frei, 2018)
LS-factor	JRC national map for LS factor	25 * 25 m	JRC data obtained per request form https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/ls-factor-slope-length-and-steepness-factor-eu (Panagos et al., 2015a)
R-factor	Monthly rainfall sums averaged over 1991-2020 period based on the specified climate data Calculation by (Johannsen et al., 2022)	1000 * 1000 m	Calculation as proposed in cookbook using monthly rainfall sums from https://doi.org/10.60669/k7rq-6378 (Hiebl and Frei, 2016) (Hiebl and Frei, 2018) Data from (Johannsen et al., 2022), not publicly available
C-factor	Lookup table for corine land cover classes – mostly from (Panagos et al., 2015b)		Tables 4 and 5 in (Panagos et al., 2015b) Mean value for non-irrigated cropland from (Schmaltz et al., 2023)
P-factor	JRC EU-wide map for P-factor	1000 * 1000 m	JRC data obtained per request form https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/support-practices-factor-p-factor-eu (Panagos et al., 2015c) (Panagos et al., 2020)

Methods

Data preparation

The datasets used have different spatial extents, coordinate reference systems and grid resolutions. They were all reprojected to EPSG: 31287 and resampled to a resolution of 25 m, which is the highest resolution available among the input datasets. The JRC LS-factor map with 25m resolution was used as snap grid to have coinciding raster cells. These steps were performed beforehand in ArcGIS Pro Software. The area of interest was defined by converting the 25m JRC LS-factor map into one polygon.

Corine Land Cover (CLC) 2018 was used for assigning C-factor values during the cookbook procedure by reclassification. It is shown in Figure 3.1.1.

Figure 3.1.1. Corine Land Cover 2018 classes for Austria

C-factor values were assigned to most CLC classes from two tables in (Panagos et al., 2015b). All forest classes were assigned the same C-factor. Some got C-factor values of zero (bare rock, glaciers). The high C-factor values visible in Figure 3.1.2 within the Alpine areas seem to arise mostly from CLC class 333 (sparsely vegetated areas), which is assigned a very high C-factor of 0.2308 by (Panagos et al., 2015b). Not that there would be no erosion happening, but it seems dubious whether RUSLE is suited to reproduce these processes. To the CLC class 211 (non-irrigated arable land), which is dominant in the Austrian cropland, a C-factor of 0.11 was assigned based on (Schmaltz et al., 2023), as (Panagos et al., 2015b) give no value for this class. (Schmaltz et al., 2023) used biannual crop rotations that therefore tend to be lower than typical single-crop C-factors. It also includes currently (2018) implemented GAEC and AEP measures. The C-factors used in the default run are shown in Table 3.1.1.

Table 3.1.1. C-factors used in the default run

Corine Code	C-factor	Corine Label	source
111	0.0539	urban continuous	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
112	0.0539	urban discontinuous	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
121	0.0539	industry transport etc	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
122	0.0539	industry transport etc	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
123	0.0539	industry transport etc	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
124	0.0539	industry transport etc	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
131	0.0539	mining landfills etc	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
132	0.0539	mining landfills etc	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
133	0.0539	mining landfills etc	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
141	0.0539	green urban areas	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
142	0.0539	sport and leisure	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
211	0.11	non-irrigated arable	(Schmaltz et al., 2023) MEAN all Austrian cropland
221	0.3403	vineyards	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
222	0.2188	fruit trees berries	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
231	0.0853	pastures	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
242	0.13	complex cultivation patterns	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
243	0.1211	arable with natural vegetation	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
244	0.1211	agro-forestry areas	set to same as 243
311	0.012	broad-leaved forest	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
312	0.012	coniferous forest	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
313	0.012	mixed forest	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
321	0.0345	natural grassland	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
322	0.0345	moors and heathland	set to same as 321
324	0.0215	transitional woodland shrub	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
331	0	beaches dunes sandplains	set to zero
332	0	bare rock	set to zero
333	0.2308	sparsely vegetated areas	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
335	0	glaciers perpetual snow	set to zero
411	0	inland marshes	set to zero
412	0	peatbogs	set to zero
511	0	water courses	set to zero
512	0	water bodies	set to zero

For calculation of the K-Factor, sand, silt and clay content maps from (Ballabio et al., 2016) were used, which are based on LUCAS data. For soil organic carbon, a map from (Wenzel et al., 2022) was used. Competences on soil mapping are split in Austria between cropland and forested areas, so that a nation-wide map for these parameters is not readily available. As proposed in the cookbook, the pedotransfer function from EPIC (Sharpley and Williams, 1990), was used with these input parameters to calculate K. The resulting K-factor values are shown in Figure 3.1.4.

For the Support-practices factor, the map of (Panagos et al., 2015c) and (Panagos et al., 2020) was used. The map seems to mostly indicate infrastructure, water bodies and glaciers, as shown in Figure 3.1.5.

For the default variant, the monthly rainfall sums were averaged over the period 1991-2020 based on data from the Austrian Meteorological Survey (Hiebl and Frei, 2016), (Hiebl and Frei, 2018). For a second variant, one of the output maps of (Johannsen et al., 2022) was used, which is shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**3.1.7. The values of this map were scaled by a factor of 10 for unit

conversion into $\text{MJ mm}^{-1} \text{ha}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$. The third and fourth variants are the remaining two combinations. Thus, we have a total of four variants:

- 1 = default values as proposed in the cookbook
- 2 = R-factor substituted
- 3 = C-factor modified for CLC class 333
- 4 = C-factor modified for CLC class 333 and R-factor substituted

Application cookbook

The only changes made to the cookbook were the inclusion of the alternative R-factor map and changes for including export of the figures and rasters created during calculation. Several steps were duplicated for the 4 different variants investigated.

Comparison results

The maps were only roughly visually compared with the available national Erosion maps of (Schmaltz et al., 2023) and (Strauss, 2007) as well as with (Panagos et al., 2015d). A quantitative comparison is outside the scope of this task.

Results

Application cookbook

Figure 3.1.2. Map of C-factor values for default run

Figure 3.1.3. Map of C-factor values with reduced C-factor for CLC class 333

Figure 3.1.4. K-factor map

Figure 3.1.5. P-factor map

Figure 3.1.6. Default R-factor map

Figure 3.1.7. Annual R-factor from (Johannsen et al., 2022)

Figure 3.1.8. Soil loss resulting from default run

Figure 3.1.9. Soil loss resulting from default run but with reduced C-factor for CLC class 333

Figure 3.1.10. Soil loss when using R-factor map from (Johannsen et al., 2022)

Figure 3.1.11. Soil loss when using R factor from (Johannsen et al., 2022) and reduced C-factor for CLC class 333

Comparison

As was already noted in the section on C-factor calculation, some CLC classes prevalent in alpine areas show very high soil loss in the default run (Figure 3.1.8). This comes in combination with presumably very high LS factors in alpine areas and non-compensated rainfall sums (altitude, snowfall) for the R-factor. As this is contradictory to our national experience and presumably, these areas should not be modelled with RUSLE anyway. A reduction of the C-factor for CLC class 333 leads to the results shown in Figure 3.1.9. These reduced C-factors do not lead to a large reduction in soil loss rates.

Using the alternative R-factor map of (Johannsen et al., 2022) gives the results shown in Figure 3.1.10. Eventually, using both the R-factor map of (Johannsen et al., 2022) and the reduced C-factor for CLC class 333 gives the results shown in Figure 3.1.11.

Neither of these variants seem very plausible at a first glance. An actual quantitative comparison would have to be performed at higher spatial detail (e.g. agricultural production zones, or NUTS3 level) and is out of the scope of this test.

Reinforced by these comparisons, we doubt the usefulness of applying this approach at a national level. We would even consider it a misuse of the RUSLE to apply it in alpine regions, forests/shrublands etc. This is the reason why the existing Austrian “nation-wide” RUSLE-based erosion maps are restricted to arable land only.

We strongly opt for either not applying this approach to these alpine regions. Typically, we would do RUSLE-based modelling in arable land only.

Recommendations

- The Markdown-Version of the cookbook is very well elaborated and nice to work with.
- Some more specifications on which R version to use to be able to use all the dependencies (somewhere between 4.0 and 4.3?).
- Rgdal package seems to be retired – good idea to use it? Replaced it with terra (no expert with R) and seems to work. Are there even rgdal calls or is it just imported and never used?
- Figures and output rasters should be saved to disk instead of just displaying.
- Calculation with 25m resolution is already very time- and space consuming for a small country like Austria (80.000 km²).

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3.2 Belgium

Seth Callewaert

Region (if not national scale): Flanders

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
Soil	K-FACTOR MAP based on soil texture calculated in Flanders	5x5	Publicly available
Land use	Simplified LU map (2018)	5x5	Publicly available
Climate	R-Factor: long-term 30 yr averaged monthly Rainfall (between 1961 and 1991) from the Royal Meteorological Institute (RMI) source: https://publish.geo.be/geonetwork/srv/dut/catalog.search#/metadata/5e225a61-ca78-11ee-8c59-847b573ec00f	1000x1000	Publicly available
Topography	LS from ESDAC (Panagos et al. (2015))	25x25	Publicly available
Topography	DHMVII – DTM Flanders	5x5	Publicly available
P-Factor	No reliable data available, P=1		

Methods

Data preparation

All data layers were converted to the Lambert72 projection and resampled to a 5x5 m resolution and clipped to match the extent of Flanders, if this was not the case (ESDAC and RMI data).

Application cookbook

C-Factor: arable land was given a C-Factor value of 0.37, which is the average crop C-factor value for arable land in Flanders (Verstraeten et al., 2001). Grassland and Forest were attributed a C-factor value of 0.01 and 0.001, respectively.

K-Factor: the K-Factor map as used in Flanders is used here. This map is based on the detailed soil map but only takes into account soil texture and was converted to K-Factor value by Declercq and Poesen (1991). Due to a lack of LUCAS observations in Flanders and the early stage of the regional monitoring network, it is not possible to reliably calculate the K-Factor based on SOC measurements.

R-Factor: The R-factor was calculated as indicated based on RMI data for a 30 year averaged monthly rainfall.

LS-Factor: Since the Cookbook code did not provide any method to calculate the LS-Factor, the LS-Factor map from Panagos was used. We added the LS-Factor map as used in the Regional modelling in a later stage as comparison. The regional modelling takes into account the Land Use when calculating the upstream area by attributing a Parcel Connectivity reduction between Agricultural Parcels and other LU types (Parcel to Parcel, Parcel to Grassland, and Parcel to Forest). The Parcel Connectivity reduces the Upstream Area contributing to a pixel affecting the L-Factor, this to simulate the border (dis)connectivity between different Land uses. The Parcel Trapping Efficiency determines the relative contribution of the area (100% for arable land; 25% for grassland).

Comparison results

We compared the map that results from application of the cookbook visually with the following:

- Application of cookbook, but using LS factor from Panagos instead of our own LS factor map

- Results of Panagos (so not according to cookbook)
- Results of Department of Environment and Spatial Development of the Government of Flanders

Results

Application cookbook

C-Factor: The same C-Factor values are used as for the regional calculations, however in Flanders the Land Use map is complemented with infrastructure and waterway shapefiles and the yearly agricultural parcel registration, providing a more yearly representative Land Use. It was however not clear whether the SERENA Cookbook was looking at a specific year, or whether it wants to calculate a more general pattern.

R-Factor: the values calculated by the method given in the Cookbook code range for Flanders from: 200.1 to 316.5. There is no evident spatial pattern visible within the data. This can mostly be attributed to the interpolation effect and the very local occurrence of rainfall. There does not appear to be a geographical relationship for the rainfall erosivity in Flanders. In accordance with the research of the R-Factor in Flanders, due to the high spatial and annual variability of rainfall measurements, the use of location specific R-Factor values in Flanders is not recommended for generalized erosion maps since this introduces an extra factor of uncertainty to the model and can be quite influential (Gobeyn et al., 2021; Notebaert et al., 2006). When looking at the values, however, the model yields rather low R-Factor values compared to the values used in the modelling done by Flanders: 870 (Verstraeten et al., 2006) to 1250 (Deproost et al., 2018). For the calculation of the R-Factor in Flanders the method as described by Renard (1997) and Verstraeten (2006) is used, which is based on rainfall measurements at 10 min resolution. This high resolution monitoring makes the estimation of the R-Factor more refined, since separated storm events can be quantified and yield a more reliable estimate of the Rainfall Erosivity, than only looking at monthly averaged rainfall measurements, which are then spatially extrapolated for the region. Therefore we are more confident to use the R-Factor values as calculated in Deproost et al. (2018). For this exercise we however calculated the erosion using the values obtained by applying the Cookbook code.

LS-Factor: The ‘Panagos’ LS-Factor map has values ranging from 0.03 to 47.24, and shows a spatial pattern which can be expected from the topographic variation in Flanders, namely, higher values in the more hilly southern part of the region, while lower values in the northern flatlands. When comparing the ‘Panagos’ LS-Factor map to the regionally created map based on the 5m resolution DEM, once again a much higher value is obtained in the regional mapping, where the values range from 0.03 to 9424.71. This leads obviously to a big discrepancy between the outcomes of both erosion models. The fact that both LS-Factors are based on the same formula, indicates that the resolution of the DEM will greatly impact the outcome of the LS calculation and in extent the Erosion map as well.

Table 3.2.1. Overview of Maxima and Minima of calculated RUSLE Factor Values

	Cookbook MIN	Cookbook MAX	Regional MIN	Regional MAX
R-Factor	200.1	316.5	1250	1250
K-Factor	0.012	0.042	0.012	0.042
LS-Factor	0.03	47.24	0.03	9424.71
C-Factor	0.001	0.37	0.001	0.37
P-Factor	1	1	1	1

Erosion maps:

Using the SERENA Cookbook code, two erosion maps are calculated, one using the LS-Factor as obtained from EUSO (Panagos) (Figure 3.2.1) and one with using the regionally calculated LS-Factor (Figure 3.2.2). It is clear from a visual interpretation that using the regionally calculated LS-Factor the erosion increases in the southern part of the region, which is logically explained by the higher LS-values in this area calculated by the regional model. This indicates that a correct estimation of the LS-Factor is crucial for the calculation of the erosion rate. For this estimation it is of utmost importance to consider the impact of resolution of the DEM on the results of the erosion calculation.

Figure 3.2.1 Results using LS from Panagos

Figure 3.2.2 Result using own calculated LS

Comparison

The resulting erosion maps are compared to both the Erosion map generated by EUSO (Panagos) (Figure 3.2.3) and the Regionally calculated erosion map (Figure 3.2.4). It is evident that the spatial patterns, namely that there is more erosion in the southern than in the northern part of the region,

are consistent over all four maps. This can logically be explained by looking at the formula. Since the RUSLE is just a linear multiplication of the factors, the factor with the highest magnitude range will be the most influential. In Flanders, the magnitude ranges of the different factors are: $R = 10E1$, $K = 10E1$, $LS_{panagos} = 10E3$, $LS_{regional} = 10E5$, $C = 10E2$ (see Table 3.2.1). From this it is evident that the variability of the topographic factor (LS) will be most influential for the pattern generation in the output, since the difference between a high LS value and a low LS value overturns differences in all other values. Since the topography in Flanders has a north-south differentiation in Flanders (northern flatland and southern hilly landscape) the pattern of the calculated erosion follows this differentiation for all maps. The fact that this is the case for all maps, suggests that the cookbook as well as the regional method adequately takes the topography into account in terms of spatial variation.

The most important difference however is the quantity of the estimated erosion. When visually assessing both Cookbook methods, it seems that they yield lower erosion values than the Panagos and Regional erosion maps. Nevertheless, it should be considered that the Panagos map is an aggregated map with resolution of 100x100 m, while all other maps are shown at a resolution of 5x5 m. This difference in resolution will visually impact the pattern by giving a more diffuse visualisation of more moderate values due to averaging for lower resolution (100x100m), while giving sharper contrasts of high and low values, leading to a visual overload of the more prominent categories (low erosion rates in the Cookbook method, high erosion rates in the regional method). This is clear when looking at the Table 3.2.2, where it is evident that not only the maximum erosion rate from the Panagos is lower than for the Cookbook methods, but the minimum erosion rate is higher as well, clearly demonstrating the averaging effect. So even if it visually seems that the Panagos map shows higher erosion rates, it in fact shows greater regions with more averaged out erosion rates.

Here again, it is important to look at the magnitude range differences between the factors, however, to compare the different implementations of the model (Cookbook and Regional) the magnitude of the factors between the different implementations should be considered. Once again, looking at Table 3.2.1, it can be observed that the LS-Factor has the greatest difference in magnitude. In fact, only 2 factors are calculated differently, namely the R- and LS-Factor with a magnitude range difference of $10E1$ and $10E2$, all other factors are comparable throughout the different implementations. This makes it evident that it is of utmost importance to correctly estimate the LS- and R-Factors, while changes in the other factors will not be as influential to the final result of the erosion calculations on regional scale. The R-Factor as calculated in the cookbook is a very rough estimate for when no high-resolution temporal data is available, it is recommended that a method is given for MS where this high-resolution data is available in order to better estimate the R-Factor. As mentioned before for the LS-Factor calculation, the spatial resolution of data will highly influence the outcome of the resulting LS-values. More attention to this is needed calculating erosion and setting thresholds, since this will influence the magnitude of the calculated erosion values, rapidly changing the class to which a pixel is categorized. The relationship between the LS-Factor and the DEM resolution should be studied more in order to correctly convert the resolution of erosion maps, as it can be expected that there is no one-on-one relationship due to the change in landscape representation for different spatial resolutions and the landscape/neighbouring dependency of the Upstream Area (incorporated in the LS-Factor). This insight is needed in order to consistently estimate the erosion risk and making it more robust to fixed thresholds. This is especially the case for hilly regions where slope lengths are often shorter than the used resolution, since lower resolution DEM's will have a flattening effect on the topography.

Figure 3.2.3 Map from Panagos et al. (2015)

Figure 3.2.4 Erosion map as calculated by the Department of Environment of the Government of Flanders

Table 3.2.2: Maxima and Minima for Erosion values calculated by the different implementations

	CookBook LS_p	CookBook LS_r	Panagos	Regional
Min Erosion	0.000081	0.000076	0.00026	0.00045
Max Erosion	54	570	41	98000

Recommendations

The RUSLE is a model to quantify the gross erosion, which is the erosion that could occur based on environmental conditions at a certain location. This is however very different from the actual or the net erosion. Setting thresholds of the potential erosion based on soil regeneration does not seem very realistic, since potential or gross erosion as modeled by the RUSLE is very prone to overestimation due to its lack of nuance for small scale interactions. This makes the validation of potential erosion maps so difficult, because there is no realistic way to measure this potential erosion, only the actual erosion can be measured. Looking at net erosion, which takes into account the transport capacity of overland flow, the estimated values should be more realistic and comparable to the actual erosion. However, a model always comes with a certain uncertainty and will still be an estimate. It does, however, make more sense to calibrate and validate a net erosion model based on observations, than trying to fit a potential erosion model to certain measurements, and using it to set threshold values for soil threats. The fact that erosion maps are so sensitive for data resolution, formula interpretation and data availability make the use of these models for policy and legislation purposes very tricky, especially when considering spatially different regions with different data availability and model implementations.

In addition, the fact that only the C-Factor and the P-Factor of the RUSLE are humanly manageable (LS-factor could also be influenced, but is not as variable), while the impact of these Factors on the resulting erosion calculation is rather small. It seems thus rather strange to use potential soil erosion as an indicator for soil health, since it is more of a static indicator of the environmental properties of the soil than it is an indicator of how well a soil is managed. This could be obtained by looking at the change in erosion values (best in percentage, since absolute change will also deal with comparability issues over different resolutions) starting from a baseline scenario.

This is in line with what was suggested in the written cookbook text when looking at the SES of Erosion control. In the Cookbook approach however the baseline scenario is set to a bare soil scenario (C-Factor = 1) which is, for Flanders and most non-(semi-)arid climates not a natural or baseline state of soils. More interesting would be the use of a standardized C-Factor based on regional practices and vegetation (crop) patterns, and compare these to the actual practices related to erosion factors C and P. Here the challenge is to get the data of these practices on parcel level, in order to correctly adapt the necessary factors. This will lead to a more accurate quantification of the human impact on erosion, which can be positive or negative, in contrast to the proposed methodology where the impact will theoretically always be positive as compared to the baseline scenario.

Lastly, it is important, when comparing different years to each other at certain locations, that not only practices change between different years, but also the parcel shape can differ, leading to changes in Land Use, directly impacting the baseline scenario (in the case of the Flanders implementation this will impact the C-factor, as well as the LS-factor). So, when comparing the 'avoided erosion' between different years, it is important to look if changes are caused by management practices on the same land use or if the changes are due to land use changes, which should be addressed differently when estimating agricultural impact on soil health.

Recommendations based on implementation issues:

Hereunder I listed some remarks which were raised while reading the Cookbook (mostly the written version). Some of these questions are also valid for the script since they address some data interpretation and processing remarks, which could be interesting to tackle in a review of the cookbook (text and script).

- For the R-Factor:

- Over which timespan are we looking for the R-Factor?
 - Should we look at the actual yearly R-Factor value for a certain year, or should a statistically relevant timeframe for climatic variables (30-years) be considered?
 - What is the appropriate temporal resolution to use? We have high resolution data on precipitation, up to minutes for recent years (from years 2000 onwards) or up to 10min dating back to 1898.
- How do we go from point data (+/- 28 weather stations for Flanders) to a spatial extent of the whole territory? There should be guidelines for the interpolation. Or do we calculate a mean value based on the calculated R-factor for every station and just use one R-Factor value? In Flanders, now, we use the 30-year mean value of our ‘head’ meteorologic station at Uccle (RMI), which represents the rain erosivity for the current climate, but does not reflect the effective rain erosivity for a specific year. We only consider one meteorologic station, due to the longevity of the data set and its central location in Flanders, and since it’s a climatologic estimate we do not suppose a significant spatial variation in Flanders. When looking at yearly R-Factor values, however, there are quite significant differences in R-factor values based on the precipitation patterns of the specific year. These variations are on a longer timescale more balanced so that they are not significantly different for the 30-year mean. Depending on the timescale, there is a difference in importance of spatial representation of the R-Factor (for Flanders especially)
- The formula given in eq. 4 in the text of the Cookbook is incorrect, Rudi also mentioned this in a comment, there should not be I30 in the formula (see Renard, 1997)
- There should be added information about how to calculate the I30 in the text Cookbook, and it would be interesting to include these equations in the script, as example for MS that have this data available, since preprocessing and implementation of the formulas in a scripting context is not as straightforward as generally conceived.
- FYI: in Flanders we are developing a python package enabling the calculation of the R-Factor based on 10-min resolution rainfall data. Right now, we have only implemented a specific rain energy (e_r) formula used in Flanders (based on Verstraeten, 2006), but we are currently developing the integration of other formulae such as Brown and Foster (1987). See: <https://github.com/watem-sedem/rfactor>
- For the K-Factor:
 - Once again, there is need to go from point measurements (texture, SOC) to a spatially distributed factor. What should be the ground for this? Should a specific type of Digital Soil Mapping algorithm be used or does a simple interpolation suffice? And how do you consider the error based on these kinds of interpolations?
 - In the text Cookbook 2 possible equations are given. How do we choose one? Personal favourites and data availability? Maybe it should be important to stress the difference between SOC and OM as used by the different equations (conversion between both is possible, however, often disputed).

- In Flanders, we do not have enough data to create a spatially significant SOC map, however, there are projects for sampling rolled out. It would be interesting to incorporate these measurements into the K-factor, however, there was no information provided on how to accomplish this.
- The LUCAS dataset for SOC is based on ± 30 observations in Flanders, so the usability is highly doubted.
- For the LS-Factor
 - In the text Cookbook the formula for S, the slope gradient, is given in degrees, however the check to see whether the first or second equation should be used the slope gradient is given in percentages (9%, which is only 5.14... degrees)
 - References to these equations should also be added in the Cookbook, and maybe refer to the original source (Renard, 1997 and McCool, 1987)
 - There is a note stating that the possible maximum slope is 50%, why is this limited and why to 50% (= 26.6°)?
 - You refer to SAGA GIS to calculate the LS-Factor, however there are some parameters that should be chosen, which will influence the outcome. Maybe this should be addressed as well?
- For the C-Factor
 - You explain how to calculate the C-Factor, not considering that the data needed is very specific and often not available especially for the management part of the C-Factor. How do we go about this?
 - Shouldn't the seasonality be considered? The C-factor varies over the year and will be crucial in relation to the rainfall seasonality. Is this taken into account in this method, and if so, how?
 - What is meant by the $\text{Min}(C_{\text{landuse}})$ and the $\text{Range}(C_{\text{landuse}})$ in eq. 12 of the text?
- For the P-Factor
 - Where do we get data on the contouring, stone walls, and grass margins? What sources are used and can this be deemed representative? Maps made by JRC use random attribution of practices on NUTS2 level, which is not really useful when trying to map erosion, however it could be used for indicators at NUTS2 level but even than the random attribution could greatly influence the effectiveness of the applied measures.

Recommendations based on methodological issues:

Here some remarks are given on the overall methodology as used for the cookbook, once again this is mostly based on the written text of the cookbook, but has a relevance for the scripted cookbook as well.

- By using RUSLE there is no account for the landscape connectivity, can this somehow be included? In Flanders we use the WaTEM model to estimate potential soil loss by water erosion, here a parcel connectivity factor is applied for changes in land use reducing upstream area due to parcel borders.
 - By using our 'Regional' LS-Factor this connectivity is taken into account for those specific maps.

- For the Erosion Control SES, the SES is only estimated by a change in C-Factor, which is somewhat strange, as this only takes into account vegetational management. In addition, as mentioned earlier, a C-Factor of 1 will greatly overestimate erosion values leading to the conclusion that the scenario ‘as is’ – with the current vegetation and management - will have a very big impact already (reduction of 80% of the erosion on wheat fields up to 50% for fallow land cfr. Table 1 of the Cookbook), so it would seem that further improvement will be less relevant. By this implementation, it is not possible to have negative values since the C-Factor cannot be greater than 1. Maybe there should be looked at the specific parts of the C-Factor which are impacted by agricultural practices (C_{crop}) instead of the whole C-Factor. Furthermore, the impact of the P-Factor is not included in the erosion control analysis. To me it seems that the inclusion of a support practice will have a more relevant impact on the erosion values and can be used to stimulate or discourage some practices, while showing a more realistic impact of the erosion control measures that are being taken.
- Within the C-Factor there is an anthropological aspect to it as well. The formula given states: $C_{arable} = C_{crop} * C_{management}$, since the management of the crops is incorporated in the C formula, this is not a solely ecosystem based factor.

Recommendations for the script:

Hereunder are some recommendations for the script as delivered by the task leaders.

- The use of SpatRasters is easier for GIS analyses, since more tooling is available. Since gdalr is deprecated this can be a valid substitute (using the terra package)
- K-FACTOR: Depth of the measurement should be given, do we only consider the top soil (up to 15, 20 or 30 cm) or subsoil as well?
- Add the calculation of the LS based on a DEM, even though this is not done for Poland, it is important that MS can calculate the LS based on their national DEM if available. This is the most crucial parameter for the RUSLE calculation (especially in Flanders(hilly regions)), because the formula and resolution used for this factor are crucial for the final result. In Flanders we take the parcel connectivity into account for the calculation of LS, but this is not the case for the suggested cookbook, so we cannot compare the difference (only if we use the panagos LS, this is however on 25m instead of 5m resolution, with great differences in values as mentioned previously).
- The final plotting of the Erosion map does not seem to work, maybe the data is too big (too high resolution), there are probably better ways to plot in R (using ggplot or similar). It would be interesting to make some more analysis plots in R to effectively show differences in similar manners for all MS. Only a visual interpretation of large regions doesn't seem to be reliable.

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3.3 France

Arthur Gaillot and David Montagne

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
Land use/C-factor	Land use map from Corine Land Cover + Data from crop declaration	90 x 90 m	Corine Land Cover https://www.data.gouv.fr/fr/datasets/corine-land-cover-occupation-des-sols-en-france/ + https://www.data.gouv.fr/fr/datasets/registre-parcellaire-graphique-rpg-contours-des-parcelles-et-ilots-cultureaux-et-leur-groupe-de-cultures-majoritaire/
Soil/K-factor	Clay, Silt, sand and SOC content maps	90 x 90 m	Actually non public data.
Climate/R-factor	R-factor map	90 x 90 m	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/rainfall-erosivity-european-union-and-switzerland
Support Practice/P-factor	P-factor map	90 x 90 m	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/support-practices-factor-p-factor-eu
Topography/LS-factor	Slope	25 x 25 m	https://geoservices.ign.fr/telechargement-api/BDALTI

Methods

Application cookbook

K-factor:

K-factor was calculated with a resolution of 90 m x 90 m from clay, silt, sand and SOC content maps using the equation proposed by Sharpley and Williams, 1990:

$$K = \left\{ 0.2 + 0.3 \times \exp \left[-0.0256 \times Sand \left(1 - \frac{Silt}{100} \right) \right] \right\} \times \left(\frac{Silt}{Clay + Silt} \right)^{0.3} \times \\ \times \left[1 - \frac{0.25 \times SOC}{SOC + \exp(3.72 - 2.95 \times SOC)} \right] \times \left(\frac{0.7 SN_1}{SN_1 + \exp(-5.51 + 22.9 \times SN_1)} \right) \times 0.1318$$

in which

$$SN_1 = 1 - \frac{Sand}{100}$$

LS-factor:

The LS-factor was re-calculated from the national DEM with a 25 m resolution using the same method that Panagos *et al.* (2015) used.

C-factor:

C-factor was based on national crop data (Table 3.3.1). For surfaces that are not included in the crop declarations, C-factor from Corine Land Cover 2018 was used (Table 3.3.2). The map of national crop data (named “register parcellaire graphique” (RPG) in French or “graphical land register” with a literal translation) is a map produced at the national scale where each field is described: surface, crop, previous crop and localization. The map is updated every year based on declarations provided by farmers to obtain financial supports under the Common Agricultural Policy. In the present case, we used the RPG 2022 assuming that the crop distribution is similar from year to year at the national scale.

Table 3.3.1. C-factor according to crop specified in the national data on crop declarations

C-factor	crop
0.1302	Other perennial crops
0.2188	Citrus
0.1302	Garlic
0.1302	Dill
0.1302	Angelica
0.1302	Anise
0.1302	Peanut
0.1302	Artichoke
0.1302	Eggplant
0.2	Winter oats
0.2188	Avocado
0.2	Spring oats
0.1302	Burdock
0.1302	Basil
0.2	Winter durum wheat
0.3	Spring durum wheat
0.1302	Eligible strip along a forest with production
0.1302	Eligible strip along a forest without production
0.1302	Blueberry
0.2188	Grazed woodland
0.3	Field border
0.1302	Borage 5 years or less
0.1302	Bromegrass 5 years or less
0.0906	Buffer strip
0.2	Winter soft wheat
0.34	Non-forage beet / Chard
0.3	Spring soft wheat
0.1302	Forage beet
0.1302	Carob
0.1302	Chestnut grove maintained by pigs or small ruminants
0.1302	Forage carrot
0.2	Other cereal of another genus
0.1302	Carrot
0.1302	Caraway
0.1302	Sweet cherry for processing
0.1302	Cucumber / Pickle
0.1302	Zucchini / Pumpkin
0.1302	Oak grove maintained by pigs or small ruminants
0.1302	Celery
0.1302	Chicory / Endive / Escarole
0.3	Other cereal of the genus Fagopyrum
0.2	Other cereal of the genus Phalaris
0.28	Other cereal of the genus Sorghum
0.25	Other cereal of the genus Panicum

0.2	Other winter cereal of the genus Avena
0.1302	Forage cabbage
0.2	Other winter cereal of the genus Hordeum
0.1302	Milk thistle
0.2	Other winter cereal of the genus Secale
0.2	Other winter cereal of the genus Triticum
0.1302	Cabbage
0.3	Hemp
0.1302	Chives
0.2	Intercropped crops: 2 crops each representing more than 25%
0.1302	Intercropped crops: 3 crops each representing more than 25%
0.1302	Butternut squash
0.1302	Camelina
0.1302	Chamomile
0.3	Other spring cereal of the genus Avena
0.3	Other spring cereal of the genus Hordeum
0.1302	Forage mix of cereals and/or protein crops (proportion < 50%) and/or forage legumes (proportion < 50%)
0.25	Other spring cereal of the genus Secale
0.25	Other spring cereal of the genus Triticum
0.38	Other spring cereal of the genus Zea
0.1302	Garden cress 5 years or less
0.1302	Coriander
0.1302	Chervil
0.1302	Watercress
0.25	Non-compliant hemp
0.1302	Soilless greenhouse crop
0.2188	Chestnut
0.1302	Cumin
0.25	Winter rapeseed
0.3	Spring rapeseed
0.1302	Cowpea
0.1302	Orchardgrass 5 years or less
0.1302	Spelt
0.1302	Spinach
0.1302	Tarragon
0.1302	Other annual forage crop of another genus
0.1302	Fescue 5 years or less
0.1302	Fava bean
0.1302	Other forage faba bean
0.1302	Other annual vegetable or fruit
0.1302	Timothy 5 years or less
0.1302	Other perennial vegetable or fruit
0.1302	Fennel
0.1302	Fenugreek
0.1302	Strawberry
0.1302	Other row forage crop of another genus
0.1302	Faba bean sown before 05/31

0.1302	Vetch
0.1302	Other pure forage grass 5 years or less
0.1302	Bean / Flageolet bean
0.2	Hops
0.5	Fallow land 5 years or less
0.5	Fallow land 6 years or more
0.5	Fallow land 6 years or more declared as EFA
0.5	Black fallow
0.1302	Other thistle
0.1302	Lavender / Lavandin
0.1302	Lettuce / Batavia / Oak leaf lettuce
0.1302	Winter sweet lupine
0.3	Spring sweet lupine sown before 05/31
0.1302	Cultivated lentil (non-forage)
0.1302	Forage lentil
0.1302	Other winter forage lupine
0.1302	Other spring forage lupine
0.25	Fiber flax
0.25	Non-textile winter flax
0.3	Non-textile spring flax
0.1302	Bird's-foot trefoil
0.1302	Dehydrated alfalfa
0.0906	Other alfalfa
0.1302	Corn salad
0.1302	Mallow
0.2	Cereal mix
0.1302	Miscanthus
0.1302	Dehydrated sweet clover
0.1302	Other sweet clover
0.1302	Sweet corn
0.38	Silage corn
0.1302	Minette
0.38	Corn
0.1302	Mix of dominant forage legumes and cereals and/or oilseeds
0.1302	Mix of dehydrated legumes (among themselves)
0.32	Mix of forage legumes (among themselves)
0.1302	Mix of dominant legumes at sowing and forage grasses 5 years or less
0.1302	Lemon balm
0.3	Melon
0.1302	St. John's wort
0.1302	Mix of dominant non-forage legumes and cereals and/or oilseeds
0.23	Millet
0.1302	Moha
0.28	Oilseed mix
0.1302	Mustard
0.1302	Other nitrogen-fixing plant mix
0.25	Mix of protein crops (peas and/or lupin and/or faba bean) dominant sown before 05/31 and cereals

0.1302	Mix of protein crops (peas and/or lupin and/or faba bean)
0.1302	Daisy
0.1302	Marjoram / Oregano
0.1302	Salt marsh
0.1302	Mint
0.2188	Hazelnut
0.2188	Walnut
0.1302	Summer turnip rape
0.1302	Forage turnip
0.1302	Winter turnip rape
0.1302	Turnip
0.1302	Nyjer
0.28	Other oilseed of another genus
0.28	Other oilseed species Helianthus
0.1302	Poppy
0.28	Other winter oilseed species Brassica napus
0.2	Other winter oilseed species Brassica rapa
0.1302	Onion / Shallot
0.2145	Olive grove
0.3	Other spring oilseed species Brassica napus
0.28	Other spring oilseed species Brassica rapa
0.21	Winter barley
0.21	Spring barley
0.1302	Nettle
0.1302	Sorrel
0.3	Other protein crop of another genus
0.1302	Parsnip
0.1302	Daisy
0.1302	Watermelon
0.1302	Common meadow grass 5 years or less
0.1302	Chickpea
0.1302	Phacelia 5 years or less
0.2	Nursery
0.2	Other winter forage pea
0.1302	Other spring forage pea
0.1302	Small red fruit
0.1302	Winter pea
0.2188	Pistachio
0.1302	Primrose
0.1302	Leek
0.1302	Pumpkin / Squash
0.1302	Other annual MAP (Medicinal, Aromatic, and Perfume plants)
0.0906	Permanent grassland - dominant grass (woody forage resources absent or scarcely present)
0.1302	Green peas
0.1302	Other perennial MAP (Medicinal, Aromatic, and Perfume plants)
0.32	Spring pea sown before 05/31
0.0906	Long rotation pasture (6 years or more)

0.1302	Ente plum for processing
0.1302	Pansy
0.1302	Parsley
0.1302	Black psyllium from Provence
0.1302	Psyllium plantain
0.34	Table potato
0.34	Starch potato
0.0906	Other temporary grassland 5 years or less
0.1302	Bell pepper / Chili pepper
0.1302	Pavie peach for processing
0.2188	Williams pear for processing
0.1302	Forage radish
0.1302	Radish
0.0906	Ryegrass 5 years or less
0.1302	Rice
0.1302	Rosemary
0.1302	Arugula
0.1302	Reed bed
0.1302	Rutabaga
0.1302	Vineyard restructuring
0.1302	Dehydrated sainfoin
0.1302	Other sainfoin
0.1302	Wooded area on former agricultural land
0.1302	Salsify
0.1302	Sage
0.2	Winter rye
0.3	Spring rye
0.1302	Temporarily non-farmed agricultural land
0.3	Sorghum
0.28	Soybean
0.0906	Pastoral land - dominant grass and woody forage resources present
0.1302	Pastoral land - dominant woody forage resources
0.1302	Savory
0.25	Buckwheat
0.1302	Tobacco
0.2188	Short-rotation coppice
0.1302	Thyme
0.1302	Tomato
0.1302	Jerusalem artichoke
0.1302	Tomato for processing
0.1302	Dehydrated clover
0.1302	Other clover
0.32	Sunflower
0.1302	Truffle orchard (oak grove with mycorrhizal plants)
0.2	Winter triticale
0.25	Spring triticale
0.1302	Valerian

0.1302	Other vetch
0.3363	Vine
0.2188	Orchard
0.3363	Vine: non-productive wine grapes
0.3363	Vine: table grapes
0.1302	X-Felium 5 years or less

Table 3.3.2. C-factor according to the CLC level 3

CLC Level 3	C_factor
213	0.15
221	0.3363
222	0.2188
223	0.2145
231	0.0906
241	0.2323
242	0.1302
243	0.1195
244	0.0881
311	0.0012
312	0.0012
313	0.0012
321	0.0403
322	0.042
323	0.0623
324	0.0229
333	0.2581
334	0.3427

Results

Application cookbook

Figure 3.3.1. C-factor map calculated from crop declaration and CLC 2018.

Figure 3.3.2. K-factor map.

Figure 3.3.3. Estimated soil erosion rate ($t\ ha^{-1}yr^{-1}$) using the RUSLE method.

Comparison

In France, the comparison of these results is possible with two maps: a map of the erosion risk estimation based on the MESALES model (Therond O. et al., 2017) and a map at the European scale of the soil erosion rates based on field plot measurements (Cerdan et al., 2010).

In the presented results, the mean erosion rate is $4.16\ t\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$ (± 19.33). According to Cerdan et al. (2010), the mean erosion rate is $1.5\ t\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$ (± 5) in France. Results from Therond et al. (2017) are not directly comparable because it provides a risk. The discrepancy between results of this report and those provided by Cerdan et al. (2010) have different explanations: for example, the slope effect in the RUSLE method is overestimated.

In particular, in some areas like the lowlands of the Loire valley, eastern Brittany or Normandy, the erosion rates are underestimated compared to measurements results and have discrepancy with the estimation of soil erosion risk in these areas.

Recommendations

The RUSLE method is one of the most used models to estimate soil erosion (Borrelli et al., 2021). When a data set for calibration is available, RUSLE method is a very relevant model, but this kind of data set is rarely available. In France, we don't have enough data to calibrate this type of model (empiric model) at the national scale. Nevertheless, application of the RUSLE method is possible, but we have to expect some discrepancy between the soil erosion estimates from RUSLE and reality. Discrepancy between the Cerdan et al. (2010) results and the RUSLE method have been discussed in many commentaries on Panagos et al. (2015) (Evans and Boardman, 2016; Fiener and Auerswald, 2016 e.g.). Evans and Boardman, (2016) in a commentary on Panagos et al. (2015), said : "Policy decisions should not be taken based on such a model. Erosion must be assessed in a better way with a large field-based element". Nevertheless, the RUSLE method remains a fast method to estimate soil erosion at large scale (national) but it has to be used with a critical eye when we talk about public policy or it would have to be improved and/or complemented with other soil erosion modelling solutions.

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3.4 Hungary

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Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
Climate (R-factor)	based on yearly precipitation data of CARPATCLIM database, and AGRI4CAST MARS	100 * 100 m	Not publicly available.
Soil (K-factor)	sand-, silt-, and clay content: DOSoReMI.hu (Pásztor et al. 2020) SOC content: presented in this SERENA report	100 * 100 m	Not publicly available.
Topography (LS-factor)	ESDAC LS-factor for the EU (Panagos et al. 2015a)	100 * 100 m	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/ls-factor-slope-length-and-steepness-factor-eu
Land use / vegetation (C-factor)	ESDAC Cover Management factor for the EU (Panagos et al. 2015b)	100 * 100 m	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/cover-management-factor-c-factor-eu
P-factor	ESDAC Support Practices factor (P-factor) for the EU (Panagos et al. 2015c)	100 * 100 m original resolution: 1 * 1 km	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/support-practices-factor-p-factor-eu

Methods

Data preparation

R-factor

R-factor was calculated according to Waltner et al. (2020). Climatic information was derived primarily from the CARPATCLIM database (Szalai et al., 2013), with the addition of AGRI4CAST MARS data (<https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/mars>) where the former was not available. The two datasets have been merged and re-interpolated for a 100 m * 100 m grid via Ordinary Kriging in SAGA GIS. Yearly precipitation data were used, where the extreme nature of the 2010 precipitation was represented as a 20-years return frequency. Calculation of R was based on the method proposed by Renard and Freimund (1994), by the combined use of the following equations:

$$R = 0.04830 P^{1.610} \quad (1)$$

$$R = 587.8 - 1.219 P + 0.004105 P^2 \quad (2)$$

where P is the mean annual precipitation. Equation 1 has been applied where $P < 850$ mm, while Equation 2 has been applied for $P > 850$ mm.

K-factor

K-factor was calculated according to the EPIC model (Sharpley and Williams, 1990). For sand-, silt-, and clay content [%] data, 0-30 cm depth maps of the DOSoReMI.hu database (Pásztor et al. 2020) were used. The SOC content map was compiled in the framework of SERENA project. The SOC map also refers to 0-30 cm depth, and the unit was converted from [g kg⁻¹] to [%]. The year of observation was 2016 for the SOC map, when the reference data were obtained.

LS-factor

ESDAC Slope Length and Steepness factor for the EU (Panagos et al. 2015a) data were used for the topographic component of the model.

C-factor

ESDAC Cover Management factor for the EU (Panagos et al. 2015b) data were used for the C-factor component of the model.

We could have only applied land use data for calculation of the C-factor, because no national data were available for either crop or management (tillage, residues, cover). Although a higher spatial resolution map would have been available for land use (25 m, Tanács et al. 2022), in order to fit the other factors of the model, we decided to use the 100 m resolution ESDAC C-factor (Panagos et al. 2015b) layer.

P-factor

ESDAC Support Practices factor for the EU (Panagos et al. 2015c) data were used for the P-factor component of the model.

Application cookbook

The Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) model was applied according to the specification of the cookbook. We thought that nationwide data for R- and K-factor were significantly more accurate than EU data. For LS- and C-factor we found the ESDAC data to be adequate. Although we were not satisfied with the pattern and spatial resolution of the P-factor, we lack nationwide data to replace it. For the soil erosion control, the difference between the erosion map with 'C-factor = 1' (soil erosion without vegetation) and C-factor according to Panagos et al. (2015b) (soil erosion with vegetation) was calculated:

Soil erosion control = Soil erosion without vegetation - soil erosion with vegetation

Both of the erosion maps (with-, and without vegetation) were categorized according to the proposed method:

- 0-2 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹: no soil erosion (0)
- 2-5 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹: slight soil erosion (1)
- 5-10 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹: moderate soil erosion (2)
- 10 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹: severe soil erosion (3)

Based on the combination of the two maps (with-, and without vegetation), the erosion control result map shows how many categories the pixel has changed when vegetation is taken into account.

Comparison results

The result erosion map was compared to the estimated erosion rate map of Pásztor et al. (2016). A difference map was compiled according to the difference between the former-, and the present map.

Results

Application cookbook

Soil erosion by water according to RUSLE was calculated for the territory of Hungary (excluding the urban areas, lakes and rivers). The distribution of the erosion categories within land use categories is shown in Table 3.4.1. Within agricultural land use, the model estimates slight erosion for the largest part of the area (39.6 %), and each one of the other erosion categories covers between 18-23 % of the agricultural areas. Most of the forest and semi natural areas (86%) fall into the no soil erosion category, and the other categories ranging from 3-6% by area. This reflects the role of the C-factor, as forests have a lower value of the cover management factor than agricultural areas.

Table 3.4.1. Distribution of the erosion category proposed in the cookbook within land use categories

	no soil erosion 0-2 t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	slight soil erosion 2-5 t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	moderate soil erosion 5-10 t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	severe soil erosion > 10 t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹
Agricultural areas	18.4	39.6	22.5	19.5
Forest and semi natural areas	86.0	5.8	3.6	4.6

The spatial distribution of the soil water erosion in Hungary can be seen in Figure 3.4.1. The highest erosion rates mostly occur in hilly regions and foothills, such as in Northern Hungary, or Southern Transdanubia. Besides having steep slopes these areas are usually cultivated, thus they have high erosion potential. Although mountainous areas also have steep slopes, the core areas of these regions are nature conservation areas covered by forests and (semi)natural habitats, therefore low erosion values were calculated due to the role of the C-factor mentioned above. The sandy soils in the Danube–Tisza Interfluve (in middle of the country), and the Nyírség (East/North-East part of the country) is classified into no erosion category. However, we would also expect lower erosion in the rest of the Great Hungarian Plain.

Figure 3.4.1. Soil water erosion map of Hungary according to the RUSLE model

The erosion control result map (Figure 3.4.2) shows how many categories the pixel has changed when vegetation is taken into account. 15 % of the total area ‘remained’ unchanged, 28 % has ‘improved’ by one-, 32 % by two-, and 25 % by three categories due to the role of vegetation. According to the spatial pattern, the categories of the pixels mostly remain in the hills and foothills, while the greatest change can be observed in the upland forests. The patterns of the C-factor are also reflected here.

Figure 3.4.2 Erosion control map of Hungary. The classes show how many categories the pixel has changed when vegetation is taken into account. (0: the pixel is in the same category in both maps, 1: minor role of vegetation, 2: moderate role of vegetation, 3: significant role of vegetation).

Comparison

The difference map, compared to the estimated erosion rate map of Pásztor et al. (2016), can be seen in Figure 3.4.3. The smallest differences are in the Danube–Tisza Interfluve (in middle of the country), the Nyírség (East/North-East part of the country), and the core areas of the mountainous regions, while the largest differences are found in hilly areas and foothills. The differences may occur due to the use of different data (e.g. former map: SOC data from 1992, different calculation method of LS-, C-, and P-factor), furthermore the different model application (former map: ensemble model of USLE and PESERA). It would require further analysis to determine which of these differences have the largest effect on the resulting map.

Figure 3.4.3. Comparison of the erosion map of present report and the erosion risk map of Pásztor et al. (2016). Yellow: the difference is less than $2\ t\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$, purple shades: former map value is greater, green shades: present map value is greater.

Recommendations

It is beneficial that the cookbook provides possibilities for using European data in case no national data are available.

Gully erosion, and sedimentation is not taken into account, even though it can cause serious damage. In the longer term, it would also be advised to take them into account, however, currently we would not be able to map these nationwide due to lack of data.

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3.5 Ireland

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Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
R-Factor	We used the R-factor map from the Global Rainfall Erosivity Database (GloReDa), which includes data from 3,625 meteorological stations in 63 countries, and clipped it to Ireland using QGIS	1km * 1km	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/global-rainfall-erosivity
K-Factor	The soil properties, including particle sizes and organic carbon, were sourced from the Irish Soil Information System's National Soil Map, established in 2008.	1:250,000	https://data.gov.ie/dataset/irish-soil-information-system-national-soils-map
LS-Factor	As per the cookbook	25 * 25 m	Panagos, Panos, Pasquale Borrelli, and Katrin Meusburger. 2015. "A New European Slope Length and Steepness Factor (LS-Factor) for Modeling Soil Erosion by Water." <i>Geosciences</i> 5 (2): 117–26. https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences5020117 .
C-Factor	Land use map	100 * 100 m	https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/corine-land-cover
P-Factor	As per the cookbook	100 * 100 m	Panagos, Panos, Pasquale Borrelli, Katrin Meusburger, Emma H. van der Zanden, Jean Poesen, and Christine Alewell. 2015. "Modelling the Effect of Support Practices (P-Factor) on the Reduction of Soil Erosion by Water at European Scale." <i>Environmental Science & Policy</i> 51 (August): 23–34. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.03.012 .

Country boundary	Vector shape file	https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/eea-reference-grids-2/gis-files/ireland-shapefile
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Methods

Data preparation

All input data was harmonized to fit a mirrored extent by the clipping process in QGIS. Coordinate reference system (CRS) re-projections were conducted for EU data to the Irish Transverse Mercator (EPSG 2157) to ensure all data aligned.

Application cookbook

The RUSLE (Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation) was calculated using the raster calculator in QGIS, with each required factor (R, K, LS, C, and P) derived from sources listed above. All processing following the cookbook methodology. The RUSLE equation, $R * K * LS * C * P$, incorporates the factors representing rainfall erosivity (R), soil erodibility (K), topographic factor (LS), cover management (C), and support practice (P). The resulting values indicate the potential average annual soil loss in tons per hectare per year, as illustrated in Figure 3.5.6.

R-Factor:

In our assessment, due to the scarcity of data in Ireland, we utilized the R-factor values from ESDAC. This dataset, produced between 2013 and 2017, is freely available upon request from <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/global-rainfall-erosivity>. Subsequently, this map was clipped to the extent of Ireland using QGIS (Figure 3.5.1).

Figure 3.5.1: R-Factor for Ireland

K-Factor:

The soil properties values including soil particle sizes and organic carbon utilized in this study were sourced from the Irish Soil Information System National Soil Map of the Republic of Ireland (Irish SIS) project, established in 2008 (Figure 3.5.2).

Figure 3.5.2: K-Factor for Ireland

LS-Factor:

The LS factor, representing slope length and steepness, was applied using the methodology outlined by Panagos et al. (2015a). This approach uses a detailed calculation of slope gradient and contributing area to model soil erosion by water (Figure 3.5.3).

Figure 3.5.3: LS-Factor for Ireland

C-Factor:

We employed the CORINE Land Cover map for Europe and clipped the extent corresponding to Ireland via QGIS. To estimate the C-factor for different land covers in Ireland, we initially utilized the values suggested for European countries as outlined in Panagos et al. (2015b). However, it became evident that these values were not accurate and deviated significantly from the expected values for Ireland. Subsequently, we assigned the C-factor for various land covers based on values outlined in a research paper conducted in several Irish catchments (Rymaszewicz et al., 2015) (Table 3.5.1 and Figure 3.5.4)

Table 3.5.1: C-factors per land use in Ireland

Land Cover	C-factor
Woodland	0.001
artificial land	0.3
Cropland	0.3
shrub land	0.01
Grassland	0.01
bare land	0.6
water bodies	0.001
Wetland	0.56

Figure 3.5.4: C-Factor for Ireland

P-Factor:

We utilized the P-factor map acquired from the ESDAC database, which has a resolution of 1 km ([Support Practices factor \(P-factor\) for the EU - ESDAC - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/table.do?tab=table&init=1&language=en&plugin=1)). However, it should be noted that the P-factor values based on the layer obtained from the ESDAC database are not accurate for Ireland and no alternatives were available. Furthermore, there are significant regions where data is lacking (identified by white in the map), resulting in undefined data in corresponding areas of the final erosion map. This was most evident in the western regions where there are large peat extents.

Figure 3.5.5: P-Factor for Ireland

Results

Application cookbook

To generate the soil loss map, raster layers of R, K, LS, C, and P factors were processed and multiplied in QGIS using raster calculation methods.

Panagos et al. (2020) established a threshold of $2 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for sustainable soil loss and $11 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for severe erosion. Baritz (EEA, 2023) suggested $2 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ as a suitable threshold for shallow soils and $4 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for deep soils. Additionally, as discussed in Baritz (EEA, 2023), other authors consider $5\text{-}10 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ as moderate erosion and $>10 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ as severe erosion.

Based on these findings, the following classification for the legend of the soil erosion map was:

- 0-2 $\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$: no soil erosion
- 2-5 $\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$: slight soil erosion
- 5-10 $\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$: moderate soil erosion
- > 10 $\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$: severe soil erosion.

Figure 3.5.6: Soil loss map for Ireland

Comparison

Currently, there is no comprehensive national map estimating soil erosion in Ireland. The created soil erosion map for Ireland (Figure 3.5.6), derived from the cookbook methodology, reveals several inaccuracies due to inconsistencies in the P-factor and R-factor data sourced from the ESDAC database. Despite these limitations, the map remains a valuable tool for managers and farmers to address soil loss from water erosion and develop appropriate protective measures.

The RUSLE model simulates rates of rill and inter-rill erosion but excludes gully erosion, streambank erosion, and deposition. Therefore, RUSLE results should not be directly compared to sediment yield data from catchments without considering these additional processes, such as by making assumptions about sediment delivery ratios.

The map indicates the highest soil loss rates along Ireland's borders, particularly in the west, with lower erosion rates in the central regions. The western, south-western, north-western, and south eastern areas exhibit a larger cohort of moderate to severe soil erosion, while the central regions generally show slight to no erosion. These patterns suggest a need for focused soil conservation efforts in western Ireland.

An analysis of the contributing factors indicates that all factors, except the P-factor, have higher values along the borders and lower values in the central regions. The inverse pattern of the P-factor likely contributes to the inaccuracies of the European map for Ireland. Notably, the western regions, which are most susceptible to soil loss, have significant gaps in data. However, sporadic available data in these areas identify several regions with soil loss rates exceeding 10 tons per hectare per year.

Recommendations

Further research into the P-factor and R-factor values is necessary to produce a more reliable erosion map for Ireland. This would enhance the accuracy of soil erosion assessments and support more effective soil conservation strategies.

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3.6 Italy

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Region: Tuscany Region

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
Land use	Regional Land use map (2018)	Vector, 1:10.000	freely available at: https://www502.regione.toscana.it/geoscopio/usocoperturasuolo.html
Land use	F-cover	100 m	freely available: Google Earth Engine (images 2018)
Soil	Regional Soil database	Vector 1:50.000	freely available at https://www502.regione.toscana.it/geoscopio/pedologia.html
Soil	Sand, silt, clay, and O.C. (%) maps (map were built from 4.000 soil profiles, following FAO’s methodology (GSP-GSOC map)	100 m	Not freely available (Lamma Consortium)
Climate	Meteorological parameters database: spatialized minimum and maximum daily air temperature; spatialized cumulative daily precipitation. (Spatialization model details: 1) algorithm: improved version of Daymet algorithm (Thornton et al. 1997) that interpolates	250m	Not freely available. database of meteorological parameters spatialized over Tuscany region (period 1990–2022, Lamma Consortium); thermometric and pluviometric stations (Ufficio idrografico di Pisa, Genova, Parma, Bologna e Roma, Servizio Idrologico

	meteorological values using DTM. The original algorithm was calibrated for the Tuscany region;2) input data: dataset collected from 1995 to 2017, in 965 thermometric stations and 1403 pluviometric stations)		della Regione Toscana, ARSIA, Aeronautica Militare, LaMMA Consortium, UCEA, and other minor networks).
DEM	DEM 10 of Tuscany	10m	freely available at https://www502.regione.toscana.it/geoscopio/cartoteca.html
Conservation Practices	Terraced areas (2020)	Vector, 1:10.000	Not freely available (database of terraced areas (2020), Lamma Consortium)

Methods

Data preparation

Climate: Daily precipitation data for the period from 1990 to 2020 spatialized across the region at 250m resolution were aggregated into annual average data and subsequently scaled to 50 m resolution.

Soil: Sand, silt, clay, and O.C. % maps were downscaled at 50m by means of bilinear algorithms

Land use: Vector regional land use map was rasterized at 10m resolution; F-cover was downscaled from 100 m to 50 m by means of bilinear algorithms.

Conservation practices: Vector geodatabase of terraced areas was rasterized at 50m resolution.

Application cookbook

R Factor: Linear regression of R and mean annual precipitation (P) for the period 1990-2020 from local data collected every 30 min in 11 sites (CNR_IRPI 2004); equation: $R = -739.0118 + 2.4787P$.

K Factor: The soil erodibility factor K is calculated following Torri et al. (1997). The regression equation was applied to the maps at 100 m of the input data. Then, K Factor is downscaled from 100 m to 50 m by bilinear algorithms.

LS Factor: Desmet & Govers (1996) SAGA tool was applied at 10 m and upscaled to 50 m by bilinear interpolation.

C Factor: ESDAC method (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2015.05.021>) was applied at 10 m resolution and upscaled to 50 m by bilinear algorithms. For arable land, the coefficient of crop types was multiplied by the same management coefficient value for all Tuscany. For not arable lands, C factor was obtained as: $C_{min} + (C_{max} - C_{min}) \times (1 - F_{COVER})$.

P factor: For terraced areas a multiplication factor of 0.5 was considered (expert evaluation).

Comparison results

The following comparison does not refer to results in D3.1.1, but to the input data currently available at national level (namely EU, ESDAC data).

R factor

R factor from empiric linear equation (CNR_IRPI 2004) was compared with R factor by ESDAC (500 m), downscaled to 100 m by bilinear algorithm (ESDAC). The comparison showed a very different distribution. Modelling R factor at regional level seems able to capture extreme values more than the EU model, although the spatial distribution of higher and lower values is the same (Figure 3.6.1).

Figure 3.6.1. R factor maps and values distribution (a) distribution of values; b) ESDAC elaboration; c) TOS elaborations

K Factor

As for R, Soil erodibility calculated using the regional soil dataset resulted in higher values than ESDAC (Figure 3.6.2). This may be due to the large difference in data availability for the two approaches.

Indeed, for the TOS map the layers used were sand, silt, clay, SOC % maps estimated from 4.000 soil profiles, following FAO’s methodology (GSP-GSOC map). Moreover, even the used methods are different: Torri et al. in TOS map, while in ESDAC, soil erodibility was calculated for the LUCAS survey points using the nomograph of Wischmeier and Smith (1978).

Figure 3.6.2: K factor maps: a) ESDAC elaboration; b) TOS elaborations

LS Factor

The LS Factor from ESDAC (the original file produced with Desmet & Govers , 1996, SAGA tool at 25 m was upscaled at 100m) and CNR (Desmet & Govers , 1996, SAGA tool applied at 10 m and upscaled at 100 m by bilinear interpolation) resulted in very similar outputs (Figure 3.6.3).

Figure 3.6.3. LS factor maps and values distribution (a) distribution of values; b) ESDAC elaboration; c) TOS elaborations

C factor

For the C factor, the ESDAC method was applied on regional data (regional land use, 10 m resolution). ESDAC and regional C factors seem similar when values are grouped into broad classes (Figure 3.6.4). However, when the lower values are aggregated in classes with a smaller range of values, the two elaborations are very different (Figure 3.6.5), probably due to the fact that the C factor values are widely dispersed. These differences showed to have a strong impact in the calculation of potential erosion and in the differences between potential erosion and actual erosion. It was particularly evident in non-arable lands where the C factor is influenced by F_{COVER} . In fact, a different distribution of data between ESDAC and CNR is highlighted where huge ranges of C factor reference table occur (e.g. forests' C value ranges between 0.0001 to 0.003, a factor of 30 that, since a difference is translated directly in a difference in estimated erosion, matters a lot).

Figure 3.6.4: C factor maps: a) ESDAC elaboration; b) TOS elaborations

Figure 3.6.5. C factor aggregation in classes with a different range

P Factor

Different typologies of data were used for P factor calculations, indeed, while contour farming, stone walls, and grass margins were taken into account by ESDAC P factor, the Terraced areas layer was adopted at regional level, with a value of 0.5 assigned to the presence of terrace areas. Consequently, the differences between the two approaches are significant (Figure 3.6.6).

Figure 3.6.6: P factor maps: a) ESDAC elaboration; b) TOS elaborations

Results

SOIL EROSION

The Actual erosion maps have similar patterns of distribution of high -low erosion values (Figure 3.6.7). However, the use of regional datasets improves the Identification of areas with high erosion rates (Figure 3.6.8). The histogram of pixel distribution shows the wider areas under higher RUSLE values in TOS, than in ESDAC (see classes: 100-500 Mg/ha/y and 10-100 Mg/ha/y)

Figure 3.6.7. Soil map erosion according to ESDAC (a) and TOS (b) elaborations

Figure 3.6.8. Distribution of values of erosion according to ESDAC and TOS elaborations

SOIL EROSION CONTROL

Soil erosion control was calculated as the difference between potential and actual soil erosion (SES, ecosystem service of soil erosion protection, i.e. soil eroded mass retained by vegetation, Mg/ha/y). Both of the maps showed that vegetation plays a large role in preventing erosion. Figure 3.6.9 shows the distribution values of the reduction of erosion in the two elaborations, and it is possible to see in some parts of the area reduction amounts to 400 t/ha/yr.

Figure 3.6.9. Distribution of soil erosion control values (t/hayr) according to ESDAC and TOS elaborations

TOS map in general showed higher values than ESDAC (Figure 3.6.10). In particular, SES differences are very high in correspondence with differences in R factor. In the NW sector, characterized by high coastal mountains, with the highest precipitation values of the region, TOS SES is much higher than the ESDAC one. While in a limited mountain sector in the southern part (Amiata Mountain), ESDAC SES is higher than TOS one, probably due to a higher K factor, without great difference in C factor.

Recommendations

The comparison carried out highlights that the use of different datasets as well as the difference in models lead to differences that in some cases and in some specific areas can be also very important. Due to the lack of possibility of a true validation, it is not possible to rigorously state which is the best result. However, the use of regional dataset may improve the ability in describing all the conditions of the territory, due to the high amount of data.

Figure 3.6.10. Soil erosion control maps according to ESDAC (a) and TOS (b) elaborations and differences between the two SES elaboration (c)

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3.7 Lithuania

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Data used:

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
Rainfall data for R-factor	Precipitation data (mm) of 61 meteorological stations from the Lithuanian Hydrometeorological Service. In decades, 2022.	10 * 10 m	The data is not publicly available.
Soil erodibility factor (K-factor)	K-Factor raster (100*100m) from the European Soil Data Centre.	10 * 10m	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-erodibility-k-factor-high-resolution-dataset-europe
LIDAR Data (2016) for LS-Factor	The DTM Data model has been generated. Based on his data, a layer of the length and steepness of slope was generated, 2016.	10 * 10m	The data is not publicly available.
Land use data (2023) for C-Factor	Land use data layer, in which all types of land use are generalized to the following classes: cropland, forest, grassland, shrubland, bare land, water land, settlements, 2023.	10 * 10m.	Primary data is available to registered Lithuanian users at www.geoportal.lt
Crop declaration data (2023) for P-Factor	Crop declaration data includes agricultural land according to crop rotation and perennial meadows and other agricultural land.	10 * 10m.	NMA – National Paying Agency. Primary data is available to registered Lithuanian users at www.geoportal.lt
Tillage practices data (2023) for P-Factor	Agricultural land under no-plough (all tillage practices that do not use the plough) and conventional tillage.	10 * 10m.	NMA – National Paying Agency. The data is not publicly available.

Methods

Data preparation

The RUSLE equation is used for the modeling of Lithuanian soil erosion potential,

$$A=R \times K \times LS \times C \times P,$$

This equation (its factors) was adapted to Lithuanian conditions and available data.

The **R-factor** was calculated according to the following formula:

$$R = \sum_{i=1}^9 1.735 \times 10 \left(1.5 \times \log_{10} \left(\frac{P_i^2}{P} \right) - 0.08188 \right)$$

P – amount of precipitation of warm period of the year (nine months) (mm), P_i – monthly precipitation (mm).

Data for the year 2022 were used (liquid precipitation: 03 - 11 months). Only March (from the third decade) to November (until the third decade) precipitation data were used for the analysis, i.e. the period when liquid precipitation falls according to multi-year norms in Lithuania.

The European Soil Data Center soil erosion data in 100*100m cells detail was used for the **K-factor**. Because the simulation was done with 10*10m cell detail, this data was transformed using Bilinear resampling technique. These data are used because we do not have national texture fraction data at a detailed scale. The modeled spatial data, based on the average values of the texture classes, cannot ensure reliability, because there is no possibility to estimate the geomorphological factor of the distribution of fractions.

LS – Factor calculated using the Lithuanian high-resolution DEM (10 m), ArcGIS model builder, and raster algebra algorithm:

$$(flowass \times [cellresolution]/22.1,0.4) \times Power\left(\frac{\sin(\text{slope raster in deg} \times 0.01745)}{0.09,1.4}\right) \times 1.4$$

C – Factor spatially differentiated according to the Lithuanian georeferenced land use data. Land use classes are aggregated into 7 subfactors:

Land use	C - Factor
Cropland	0.24
Forest	0.01
Grassland	0.05
Shrubland (abandoned agriculture land)	0.2
Bare land	0.6
Waterland	0
Settlements	0.15

P – Factor, as a support practice, was adapted to Lithuanian conditions, because contouring, stripping, and terracing (as default subfactors) is not applied in Lithuanian agricultural territories as an erosion limiting factor. In the case of the territory of Lithuania, the application of perennial grassland and no-till (no-plough) agriculture is relevant. Therefore, using the NMA (National Paying Agency) crop, arable (conventional tillage)/no-till (no-plough) agriculture declaration data (declarations cover about 85% of all agricultural land), as well as the missing agricultural land by overlaying information from the Lithuanian georeferenced base (land use data), a P-Factor layer was generated and given the following meanings:

Support practice	P – factor values
Convention tillage	1
Ploughless tillage	0.85
Perennial grasses	0.65
Other Agro-green zones	0.15

Comparison results

We cannot compare the results of the analysis with previous work at national scale because RUSLE modeling is being performed for the first time on the territory of Lithuania. There are no scientific studies of soil erosion modeling performed by other methods. It is known from previous studies of soil erosion in Lithuania and attempts to calculate the areas affected by soil erosion that in agricultural areas the average value varies between 16-19%.

According to DirvDR10LT GIS database (Lithuanian soil GIS database, scale 1:10000) 15.64% of agricultural land is affected by erosion. This is about 770 922.1 ha. Of these, 50.77% (391 429.73 ha) are slightly eroded, 37.64% (290 149.81 ha) are moderately eroded, and 11.59% (89 351.55ha) are strongly eroded or destroyed soils.

The averages obtained during the RUSLE simulations do not fundamentally contradict these data.

Results

Figure 3.7.1. Soil erosion potential of the territory of Lithuania according to the RUSLE equation, in the cells 10x10m

Applying the RUSLE model and national Lithuanian data (free available official sources), the erosion risk factor of Lithuanian soil cover was calculated. The analysis was performed only for agricultural territories, which cover 54.91% of the territory of Lithuania. According to these calculations, it was determined that a weak risk of erosion (up to 2t/ha/year) is characteristic of 81.32% of the area of Lithuanian agricultural territories (2 915 294.82 ha). Of these, as many as 56.77 percentage points belong to areas where the risk of erosion is only up to 0.5t/ha/year.

In the context of the territory of Lithuania, the intensity of soil erosion up to 2t/ha/year is considered irrelevant. In fact, these are areas where the dominant inclination of the surfaces is $<3^\circ$ (the dominant is flat surfaces with an inclination of up to 1°) and soil erosion does not actually take place here. The erosion potential is generated by the RUSLE equation in these areas due to agricultural activities. In these areas (especially in the moraine plains of Central Lithuania) soil erosion due to the wind is actually a more important process than soil erosion by water.

In terms of soil erosion, according to the applied RUSLE equation, the relevant areas cover about 18.68% of agricultural lands. In principle, surfaces with an inclination angle of $>3^\circ$ dominate here, and economic activity is dominated by various tillage systems and crop rotation.

The average risk of erosion (2-5t/ha/year) is characteristic of 10.85% of agricultural territories. This amounts to 390 393.58 ha. Strong erosion risk ($>5t/ha/year$) is characteristic of 7.79% of agricultural territories (279 257.42 ha). The largest areas of potential erosion risk are concentrated in the agrarian hilly morainic uplands, and this corresponds to the actual declared areas of eroded soils according to the DirvDR10LT GIS database.

Comparison

Figure 3.7.2. Soil erosion potential of the territory of Lithuania (based on data of European Commission) according to the RUSLE equation, in the cells 100x100m

Table 3.7.1. Comparison of results using different cell sizes and datasets.

Erosion risk classes according to map legend, t/ha/year	RUSLE			
	EU, 100x100m		LT, 10x10m	
	ha	%	ha	%
<i>Error*</i>	-	-	132.55	0.00
0 – 0.50	3 658 331.00	60.70	2 035 300.93	56.77
0.51 – 1.00	1 415 311.00	23.48	469 530.52	13.10
1.01 – 2.00	708 911.00	11.76	410 463.37	11.45
2.01 – 5.00	228 531.00	3.79	390 393.58	10.89
5.01 – 10.00	14 360.00	0.24	166 839.63	4.65
10.01 – 20.00	1 228.00	0.02	74 427.72	2.08
20.01 – 50.00	44.00	0.00	28 278.71	0.79
> 50.01	-	-	9 711.36	0.27
<i>The share of the area from the total area of Lithuania (6 528 648.30 ha)</i>	6 026 716,00	92.31	3 585 078.37	54.91
<i>Agricultural use (2023)</i>	3 382 583.87		3 382 583.87	

*The LT DTM model generated from LT LIDAR data has errors related to surface generation.

Using the RUSLE model and data provided by the European Commission (from the European Soil Data Center), the erosion risk factor of Lithuanian soil cover was calculated. According to these calculations,

it was determined that a weak risk of erosion (up to 2t/ha/year) is characteristic of 95.94% of the studied area of Lithuania (5 782 553 ha). However, this is a very wide range, of which even 60 percentage points fall on areas where the risk of erosion is only up to 0.5t/ha/year. The average risk of erosion (2-5t/ha/year) is characteristic of 3.79% of the studied territory of Lithuania. This amounts to 228531 ha. Strong erosion risk (>5t/ha/year) is characteristic of only 0.26% of the territory of Lithuania (15 632 ha). In terms of soil erosion, according to the applied RUSLE equation and using data from the European Commission, the relevant areas cover about 4.05% of surveyed lands.

As we can see, the areas of relevant territories in terms of erosion risk, when applying different data sets and cell sizes, differ significantly and vary from 4.05% (when a 100x100m cell is used) to 18.68% (when a 10x10m cell is used). There are several reasons for this:

1. As the cell size increases, the degree of generalization of the data values increases (the averaging effect appears), the number of extreme values decreases.
2. When calculating the factors based on EU data, the RUSLE model uses CORINE data, which contains generalized land use data, in which forests are not eliminated according to the C-factor. Meanwhile, the application of Lithuania land use data ensures the most accurate assessment of the land use situation and the elimination of areas where soil erosion does not occur (forests, Settlements, roads, water lands). This automatically changes the statistical situation of soil erosion risk assessment.
3. When applying Lithuania data and 10x10m cells, the RUSLE model is automatically applied only to agricultural land, while with data of Europe Union, the assessment also includes forest areas.
4. According to data of Europe Union, the P-factor is not objectively applied to the territory of Lithuania, so it distorts the results.

Recommendations

1. Recommendations for R-factor calculation should be clarified, i.e. what intensity of precipitation and what time periods are used for modeling; how to deal with snowfall?
2. The official P-factor and C-factor classifier tables of the RUSLE model applied in the territory of the European Union should be provided. This would help avoid interpretations.

3.8 Netherlands

Martine Trip, Joost Cruijssen, Rudi Hessel

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
Land use	Land use map	100 * 100 m	Cover Management factor (C-factor) for the EU https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/cover-management-factor-c-factor-eu
Soil	Clay, Sand, Silt contents	500 * 500 m	Topsoil physical properties for Europe (based on LUCAS topsoil data)

	of the soil (%)		https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/topsoil-physical-properties-europe-based-lucas-topsoil-data
<i>Soil</i>	Soil organic carbon (%)	25 * 25 m but transferred to 500 * 500 m	Soil organic carbon stock in the top 30 cm soils in the Netherlands (Alterra, Wageningen UR) https://www.atlasnatuurlijkkapitaal.nl/bodemkoolstofvoorraad-in-heel-nederland
<i>Climate</i>	Cumulative monthly rainfall	1000 m * 1000 m	Precipitation - Long term average 1981-2010 - Average monthly precipitation (KNMI database) https://dataplatform.knmi.nl/dataset/rd3-4
<i>P-factor</i>	JRC EU-wide map for P-factor	1000 * 1000 m	JRC data obtained per request form https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/support-practices-factor-p-factor-eu
<i>LS-factor</i>	JRC national map for LS factor	25 * 25 m	JRC data obtained per request form https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/ls-factor-slope-length-and-steepness-factor-eu (Panagos et al., 2015a)

Methods

Data preparation

The datasets used have different spatial extents, coordinate reference systems and grid resolutions. They were all reprojected to EPSG: 28992 and resampled to a resolution of 25 m, which is the highest resolution available among the input datasets.

K-factor was calculated based on maps of soil fractions (% clay, silt and sand) and a map of soil organic carbon stock.

R-factor was calculated by long term average monthly rainfall data, as provided by KNMI (after retrieving an API key, the data can be downloaded).

The C, P and LS factors were downloaded from the ESDAC website.

Application cookbook

The different factors for the RUSLE model were calculated using the script in R. However, different error messages showed up, as not all maps were the same size (some extended up to parts of the North Sea, and some did not cover the complete map) in the further calculation of erosion. Therefore, the next steps were performed in QGIS, instead of R, namely the calculation of the 'A' (soil losses). This was done with the raster calculator.

Comparison results

No earlier map was available; hence no comparison could be performed.

Results

Application cookbook

The cookbook was applied according to the instructions. The resulting erosion map can be found in Figure 3.8.1.

Figure 3.8.1 Map of potential soil loss for the Netherlands

As the map was created with QGIS, instead of R, it might seem different. The same colours were used for the scaling as proposed in the R-script.

It is visible in the map that the potential for erosion is generally fairly low, which is because The Netherlands are generally quite flat. The highest values are found in areas where there is some slope, such as in Southern Limburg. Southern Limburg also has erodible loess soils, so that potential erosion is higher there than in the rest of the country. A close up of this area can be found in Figure 3.8.2.

Figure 3.8.2 Close up of the potential soil loss due to water erosion in province of Limburg, the Netherlands.

Due to the small differences in erosion potential in the Netherlands, another map was created with an extra class of erosion potential: smaller than 0.1 Mg ha-1 yr-1 (Figure 3.8.3). In this map, slightly more differences become visible. Comparison with the maps of the individual RUSLE factors suggests that lowest values are found in regions with low K and/or low C values.

Figure 3.8.3 Map of potential soil loss for the Netherlands, with additional class in comparison to Figure 3.8.1.

Recommendations

- It takes a lot of time to find the right data files and prepare (adjust extent, CRS, resolution, origin, etc.) the raster files for the calculations. It would be helpful if some tips and tricks on how and where to find the right data, could be provided.

3.9 Poland

Sylwia Pindral

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
Land use	Land use map	100 * 100 m	https://land.copernicus.eu/en
Soil	Maps of SOC, sand, silt, and clay content were prepared using DSM approach (QRF and GWR algorithms)	100 * 100 m	Not available for the public use.
Climate	Historical data of 2013. This source was chosen to have harmonized data for climate change scenario modelling. Mean monthly precipitation was calculated as a mean from daily data.	1km * 1 km	https://opendap.4tu.nl/thredds/catalog/data2/uuid/e940ec1a-71a0-449e-bbe3-29217f2ba31d/catalog.html
LS-factor	The same source used as in the cookbook.	25 * 25 m	Panagos, Panos, Pasquale Borrelli, and Katrin Meusburger. 2015. "A New European Slope Length and Steepness Factor (LS-Factor) for Modeling Soil Erosion by Water." <i>Geosciences</i> 5 (2): 117–26. https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences5020117 .
P-factor	The same source used as in the cookbook.	100 * 100 m	Panagos, Panos, Pasquale Borrelli, Katrin Meusburger, Emma H. van der Zanden, Jean Poesen, and Christine Alewell. 2015. "Modelling the Effect of Support Practices (P-Factor) on the Reduction of Soil Erosion by Water at European Scale." <i>Environmental Science & Policy</i> 51 (August): 23–34. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.03.012 .

Methods

Data preparation

Before the application of the cookbook, all input data was harmonized to fit the same extent and resolution. The process was done using R 4.3.1. The resolution of the rasters was changed to national crs=2180, clipped and masked to the existing national maps of SOC, sand, silt, and clay content. For Poland we evaluated soil erosion by water only for agricultural area (arable land, pastures, meadows).

Application cookbook

We corrected the C factor. We reclassified LULC raster according to the values that were provided in script that came with the cookbook, but also, we added more values for crops and built-up areas according to the Polish studies on erosion (Hołub, 2007).

Comparison results

Two soil erosion maps (previous approach (Wawer and Nowocień, 2007) and a map according to the SERENA cookbook) were compared visually and quantitatively. However, due to the different methodology and potential difference in soil erosion classes breaks, the comparison must be interpreted as a general comparison. Below we present the comparison of the spatial distribution of soil erosion classes between two approaches, and the correlation between RUSLE model factors and the final result of soil erosion modelling.

It must be noted the main difference between two compared approaches. In the Wawer and Nowocień model three factors were taken into account: slope, soil texture informing about soil susceptibility to erosion, and land use. In RUSLE, we include also precipitation data, land management, SOC content.

Results

Application cookbook

Table 3.9.1. Spearman correlation matrix between SERENA soil erosion map and RUSLE factors

	R_factor	EROSION	C_factor	LS_factor	P_factor	K_factor
R_factor	1.00					
EROSION	0.51	1.00				
C_factor	-0.11	0.18	1.00			
LS_factor	0.56	0.60	-0.19	1.00		
P_factor	0.07	0.02	-0.10	0.08	1.00	
K_factor	0.24	0.30	-0.06	0.17	-0.09	1.00

Among all calculated soil erosion factors, we can see that the biggest influence on the distribution of soil erosion factors has the relief – LS factor, secondly, we can see that precipitation – R factor has moderate correlation with erosion. The less significant was P-factor that was not correlated neither with soil erosion loss nor with the other factors (Table 3.9.1).

Figure 3.9.1. RUSLE factors calculated for agricultural area in Poland.

Figure 3.9.2. Soil erosion loss by water calculated in two variants: with C factor according to the current land use and for C factor =1.

Figure 3.9.3. Histogram of the soil erosion loss by water according to the current land use

For the Polish agricultural soils, land cover plays a significant role in the erosion control. We can observe that the area of the slight, moderate and severe soil losses increased in Poland, except central part of the country, where arable land has the biggest share in the agricultural soils. It is also a relatively homogeneous area taking into account land use and the mean area of the agricultural parcels/fields is the highest in this region. All these factors influence a relatively low difference between two maps (Figure 3.9.2). The big share of pastures in the southern Poland and also orchards and plantations cause higher differences between C-factors values. The same situation occurs in the northern Poland. In this region more pastures and meadows occur, hence the C factor is lower (Figure 3.9.1, 3.9.2).

Figure 3.9.4. Histogram of the soil erosion loss by water with C factor = 1.

Comparison

Wawer and Nowocień, 2007

Results of the application of the cookbook

Figure 3.9.5. Comparison of the two approaches of the modelling soil erosion by water. Note: The classes of soil erosion may differ due to the application of different soil loss ranges.

Spatially two maps are highly related with each other. We can see that the highest value of soil loss occurs in southern Poland (mountain area and loess plateaus). However, RUSLE model is more accurate and sensitive for the northern part of Poland that geologically and morphologically was formed in the Vistulian glaciation. The erosion processes may occur in these regions as well (Pindral and Świtoniak, 2017; Świtoniak 2014, Świtoniak et al. 2013). The biggest similarities we can observe in south-east of Poland. The highest in the Karkonosze Mountains in the south-west of Poland. The soil erosion classes from RUSLE map are the most related to the actual soil erosion made by Wawer and Nowocień (2007) (Table 3.9.2).

Table 3.9.2. Percentage share of the soil erosion classes in three maps.

Soil erosion		negligible	very slight	slight	moderate	severe
Wawer & Nowocień, 2007	potential	67.1	15.3	11.8	4.7	
	actual	81.6	1.9	9.4	4.4	2.7
SERENA		85.3	8.0	4.7	1.4	0.5
SERENA C factor=1		46.0	26.3	17.3	5.1	5.4

Despite the Spearman correlation results (Table 3.9.1), the comparison of two approaches with the change of C factor shows that the final result and spatial distribution of soil erosion classes strongly depends on the land use. For the map with C factor =1 the area of severe erosion increased by almost 5%, moderate by almost 4%, slight erosion by 12%, and very slight by 18% (Table 3.9.2). The map with C factor =1 is related in some way to the potential soil erosion map made by Wawer and Nowocień (2007), where the land use was not taken into account in the modelling of potential soil erosion (Table 3.9.2).

Figure 3.9.6. Soil erosion by water and soil erosion control.

Figure 3.9.7. Histogram of the soil erosion control.

Table 3.9.3. Descriptive statistics of the three maps created according to the SERENA cookbook.

	mean	min	max	sd	median	1st Q	3rd Q	skewness	kurtosis	cv
erosion	0.71	0.0	122.1	1.6	0.29	0.13	0.64	131.96	8.46	224.98
erosion max	2.85	0.0	942.8	6.7	1.10	0.60	2.21	102.81	7.48	89.81
erosion control	2.14	0.0	864.7	5.8	0.73	0.37	1.55	137.29	8.69	74.80

According to the calculated statistics we can see a few important findings. First of all, the mean for maximal erosion (C factor =1) is close to the erosion control. This means that the land use reduces water erosion significantly. Secondly, the potential erosion (without specific land use protection) occurs in every area of Poland (minimal value = 3.28 à slight soil losses). High skewness and kurtosis inform about the right-skewness and the biggest share of values within the lowest values range. This is also visible in the low median, 25th and 75th percentile values (Table 3.9.3). The graphical representation of the values distribution is visible on the Figures 3.9.3, 3.9.4, 3.9.7.

Recommendations

The cookbook provided reliable results of soil erosion in Poland. One modification can be considered on the national/regional level application. C-values can be modified according to the national studies on erosion. But this was suggested in the cookbook.

Literature

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3.10 Slovakia

Boris Pálka, Jarmila Makovníková

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
Climate (rainfall data for R factor)	Precipitation minute data (mm) of 100 meteorological stations from Slovak Hydrometeorological Service	5x5 m	Nonpublic data
Soil (K factor)	Soil Erodibility in Europe High Resolution dataset (500m) version 14	500x500 m	Soil Erodibility (K- Factor) High Resolution dataset for Europe - ESDAC - European Commission (europa.eu)
Digital elevation model (LS factor)	The LS-calculation was performed using the original equation proposed by Desmet and Govers (1996) and implemented using the System for Automated Geoscientific Analyses (SAGA), which incorporates a multiple flow algorithm and contributes to a precise estimation of flow accumulation.	25x25 m	LS-factor (Slope Length and Steepness factor) for the EU - ESDAC - European Commission (europa.eu)
Cover crop map (C factor)	LPIS 2023 (Agricultural Paying Agency)	5x5 m	geoportal.gov.sk
P-factor	The same source used as in the cookbook.	100 x 100 m	Panagos, Panos, Pasquale Borrelli, Katrin Meusburger, Emma H. van der Zanden, Jean Poesen, and Christine Alewell. 2015. "Modelling the Effect of Support Practices (P-Factor) on the Reduction of Soil Erosion by Water at European Scale." <i>Environmental Science & Policy</i> 51 (August): 23–34. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.03.012 .
Soil depth	Vector and raster layer of agricultural soil depth	5 x 5 m	https://portal.vupop.sk/portal/apps/webappviewer/index.html?id=d89cff7c70424117ae01ddba7499d3ad

Methods

Data preparation

R factor - we used data from 100 automatic rain stations on minute rainfall for about 10-year period.

$R = E \cdot I_{30} / 100$ (Wischmeier, Smith 1978)

R ... R factor ($\text{MJ} \cdot \text{ha}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$)

E ... total kinetic energy of the rain ($\text{J} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$)

I_{30} ... max. 30 minutes intensity of rain ($\text{cm} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$)

$E = \sum_{i=1}^n E_i$

E_i ... kinetic energy of the i-th rain section

$E_i = (206 + 87 \log i_{si}) \cdot H_{si}$

i_{si} ... intensity of i-th rain section ($\text{cm} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$)

H_{si} ... summary of i-th rain section (cm)

K factor – we used the source proposed in the cookbook from ESDAC dataset: Soil Erodibility (K-Factor) High Resolution dataset for Europe

LS factor – we used the source proposed in the cookbook from ESDAC dataset: LS-factor (Slope Length and Steepness factor) for Slovakia

C factor – we used LPIS database-this has information about crops on agricultural soil. We have values of C factor for all crops.

P factor – we used the source proposed in the cookbook from ESDAC dataset: P factor for Slovakia. This map has values about 0.99 for Slovakia, so P-factor does not have much effect on the resulting erosion.

Pre-processing

Before the application of the cookbook, all input data was harmonized to fit the same extent and resolution. The process was done using ArcGis software. The resolution of the rasters was changed to national, clipped and masked to the existing national maps of factors. Layers R factor and C factor is in national coordinate system S-JTSK_Krovak_East_North. Other factor layers are in other coordinate systems. Before calculating the erosion, it was necessary to make all input layers uniform. We used geoprocessing function “Projekt raster” to change the coordinate system. The layers had different resolutions, so it was necessary to resample them. For this we used the resample geoprocessing tool. The resulting soil erosion loss calculation was done in a raster calculator.

Pre-processing data and calculation were performed in ArcGis software.

Comparison results

Comparison with D3.1.1:

D3.1.1 was with a resolution of 20 m (Figure 3.10.2), now we have a DTM available with 5 m resolution. Factor R was the same as D3.1.1., but is updated with resolution 5 m. We used the same source as in the cookbook from ESDAC (European Soil Data Centre) dataset: K factor and LS factor. C factor was updated with actual LPIS data. For comparison, we present the areas of the soil loss categories.

Results

Map of application cookbook

Applying the RUSLE model and national Slovakian data, we calculated the erosion risk factor of the Slovakia soil. The analysis was performed only for agricultural soils, which cover 37% of the Slovakian territory. Slovakia is a very heterogenic territory, where flat areas alternate with hilly areas. In general, the southern areas are flat and intensively used for agriculture, and the northern areas are mountainous and used as pastures. According to the calculations, it was determined that a weak risk of erosion (up to $2 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) is characteristic of 84.1% of the area of Slovakia's agricultural territories (1 528 600.1 ha). About 15.8% of the agricultural soil is threatened by erosion. The slight risk of erosion ($2\text{-}5 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) is characteristic of 9.5% of agricultural soil. This amounts to 172 815.8 ha. Moderate erosion risk ($5 - 10 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) is characteristic of 4.6% of agricultural territories. And severe erosion risk ($> 10 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) is on 1.8 % of agricultural soil. The result map resolution is 500 x500 m (Figure 3.10.1).

Figure 3.10.1. The result map of water erosion after cookbook application

Table 3.10.1. Areas of erosion categories after cookbook application

Erosion categories ($\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)	Area (ha)	% from agricultural soil
No soil erosion (< 2)	1528600.1	84.1
Slight soil erosion (2 - 5)	172815.8	9.5
Moderate soil erosion (5 - 10)	83271.2	4.6
Severe soil erosion (> 10)	33084.9	1.8
Summary	1817772.0	100.0

Comparison

Figure 3.10.2. Map of D3.1.1 with 20 m resolution and national classification of erosion categories

Table 3.10.2. D3.1.1 (20 m resolution and national categories of soil loss)

Erosion categories (Mg ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	Area (ha)	% from agricultural soil
No or low soil erosion (< 4)	1584569.5	87.2
Medium soil erosion (4 - 10)	127482.6	7.0
High soil erosion (10 - 30)	81755.6	4.5
Extreme soil erosion (> 30)	23964.4	1.3
Summary	1817772.2	100.0

Figure 3.10.3. Map of D3.1.1 with high resolution 5x5 m and cookbook classification of erosion categories

Table 3.10.3. D3.1.1. (resolution 5 m and cookbook categories) vs. D3.3.3 (500 resolution and cookbook categories)

Erosion categories (Mg ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	Area (ha)	D3.1.1 (Map 3.) % from agricultural soil	Area (ha)	D3.3.3 (Map 1.) % from agricultural soil
No soil erosion (< 2)	1446364.5	79.6	1528600.3	84.1
Slight soil erosion (2 - 5)	173826.1	9.6	172815.8	9.5
Moderate soil erosion (5 - 10)	91861.5	5.1	83271.2	4.6
Severe soil erosion (> 10)	105720.1	5.7	33084.9	1.8
Summary	1817772.2	100.0	1817772.2	100.0

We use a different categorization of the soil loss by water erosion in national policies. For comparison, we categorized original soil loss layer (D.3.1.1) into the categories used in the cookbook and we applied a more precise resolution of 5x5 m (Figure 3.10.3). Categories slight and moderate soil erosion came out similarly in both assessments. The class no soil erosion has a higher percentage in the output of the cookbook, while the class severe soil erosion covers a smaller area. For the R factor, the maps used in the national map and in the cookbook were very similar, as the values in the national map are close to the values from the ESDAC layer. We used K factor and LS factor from the European dataset and these have lower resolution and lower values than we have in the national layer of K factor. It is very probable that the lower values of the K factor and LS factor influenced the values of severe erosion. We used the same C factor for the national map and for the cookbook map.

In our national legislation, we have lower criteria for soil threatened by erosion, because the relief of Slovakia is very heterogeneous and sloping areas dominate. Our organization focuses only on modeling potential and real soil erosion at the national and regional level. Therefore, we mostly use the RUSLE model to predict water erosion. We do not monitor erosion events and we do not collect erosion data from the field.

SES: Soil Erosion Control

In our institute, we establish the potential of the soil ecosystem service soil erosion control based on the ratio of the potential soil loss (soil erosion without vegetation) to allowable soil loss. We applied this methodology as well as the methodology proposed in the cookbook and compared the results. Determining the potential for soil erosion control involves two steps in the Slovak methodology. The first step is to calculate the ratio of potential soil erosion to allowable soil loss:

Potential soil erosion ratio = soil erosion without vegetation / allowable soil loss

Where soil erosion without vegetation is calculated by RUSLE without C and P factor only on agricultural soil and allowable soil loss is determined based on soil depth.

According to Decree 59/2013 of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic, the limit values of soil loss by soil depth are as follows:

Table 3.10.4. Limit values of allowable soil loss and areas of soil depth

Soil depth	Limit for soil loss (Mg ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹)	% of agricultural soil
Shallow soils (up to 0.3 m)	5	22.4
Medium deep soils (0.3 – 0.6 m)	10	15.6
Deep soils (0.6 – 0.9 m)	15	62.0
Very deep soils (above 0.9 m)	20	

Figure 3.10.4. Soil depth

In Slovakia deep soils dominate (62% from agricultural soils) (Table 3.10.4). They are mainly soils in the flat areas, where the risk of soil erosion is lower (Figure 3.10.4). Medium deep soils are found in uplands (15.6%). Shallow soils (22.4%) are in hill land. These ecosystems have high risk of soil erosion and low potential to erosion control. When we recalculate the permissible soil loss with soil erosion, we find that 7%.

Figure 3.10.5. Potential of ecosystem of soil erosion control (Slovak methodology)

The results of the equation above are shown in the Table 3.10.5. A potential for soil erosion control is then assigned to the different categories of the potential soil erosion ratio using the principle that the

higher this ratio, the more difficult it will be to control erosion. Hence high erosion values mean low soil erosion control potential, and low erosion values mean high erosion control potential.

Table 3.10.5. Result is classified in 5 categories of soil erosion control potential (Slovak methodology)

Categories	Potential soil erosion ratio	Potential of soil erosion control	% of agricultural soil
1	>2.60	Very low	5,4
2	2.21 – 2.60	Low	1,9
3	1.81 –2.20	Medium	2,7
4	1.40– 1.80	High	3,5
5	< 1.40	Very high	86,5

7.3 % from agricultural soil has a very low and low potential for reducing soil erosion. High and very high potential to regulate soil erosion have 90% of agricultural ecosystems (Table 3.10.5).

Figure 3.10.6. The result map of water erosion control after cookbook application (absolute Mg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹)

About 60% represents no change (Table 3.10.6), they are mainly arable soils in the flat areas. Cereals are mainly grown here, which they have a higher C factor (approaching 1) and do not significantly reduce the risk of erosion. A small decrease is found in uplands, where the grown of cereals and fodder alternates yearly in crop plan. About 30% shows a large decrease; there are hill lands, where grasslands are mostly found. Grassland has very good anti-erosion effect. There are similar changes when comparing classes.

Table 3.10.6. Soil erosion control (cookbook)

Absolute (Mg ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)			Classes		
values	legend	%	values	legend	%
< -5	Large increase	0,0	-3	Large increase	0,0
-5 - -1	Small increase	0,0	-2	Moderate increase	0,0
-1 - 1	No change	57,8	-1	Small increase	0,0
1 - 5	Small decrease	14,0	0	No change	61,6
> 5	Large decrease	28,2	1	Small decrease	10,1
			2	Moderate decrease	13,5
			3	Large decrease	14,8

Figure 3.10.7. The result map of water erosion control after cookbook application (Classes)

The Slovak method for evaluating the ecosystem service of erosion control is based on a comparison of the permitted ratio of potential erosion and allowable soil erosion, and the cookbook method is based on the protective effect of vegetation. In both methods (Slovak & cookbook), factors that are correlated with the altitude and slope of the territory come to the fore. In mountainous areas, there are higher values of changes and also lower potential for preventing soil erosion = higher susceptibility to soil erosion. In lowland areas, there is a higher potential for erosion control and even smaller changes according to the cookbook.

Recommendations

The official P-factor and C-factor classifier tables of the RUSLE model applied in the territory of the European Union should be provided. This would help avoid different interpretations.

The limit and categories of soil loss should adapt to the MS conditions.

Further reading

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3.11 Spain

Emilio Doñate, Sabina Asins

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
Cover Management factor	This C-factor was estimated for a) arable lands based on crop composition and for b) all other land uses (non-arable) based on the vegetation density and land cover type. The management practices (reduced tillage/no till, plant residues and winter cover crops) were taken into account in estimating C-factor in arable lands.	100 * 100 m	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/cover-management-factor-c-factor-eu
Global rainfall erosivity	This map provides a complete rainfall erosivity dataset for the whole World based on 3,625 precipitation stations and around 60,000 years of rainfall records at high temporal resolution (1 to 60 minutes). Gaussian Process Regression(GPR) model was used	30 arc-seconds	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/global-rainfall-erosivity

	to interpolate the rainfall erosivity values of single stations and to generate the R-factor map.		
Soil Erodibility	This map provides a complete picture of the soil erodibility derived from the LUCAS 2009 point survey exercise and the European Soil Database.	500 * 500 m	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-erodibility-k-factor-high-resolution-dataset-europe
Support Practices factor	At European level, the effect of support practices (compulsory for farmers to receive incentives under the CAP-GAEC) on soil loss were assessed by P-factor estimation taking into account contour farming, maintenance of stone walls and, grass margins.	100*100 m	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/support-practices-factor-p-factor-eu
LS-factor (Slope Length and Steepness factor)	The LS-calculation was performed using the original equation proposed by Desmet and Govers (1996) and implemented using the System for Automated Geoscientific Analyses (SAGA), which incorporates a multiple flow algorithm and contributes to a precise estimation of flow accumulation.	100*100 m	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/ls-factor-slope-length-and-steepness-factor-eu
Laminar Erosion	Soil losses per unit area for the time period considered.	25 * 25 m	https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/biodiversidad/temas/inventarios-nacionales/inventario-nacional-erosion-suelos/estado_actual.html

Methods

Data preparation

To prepare the data for the RUSLE model calculation, the first step was to reproject all raster layers to the same coordinate reference system (EPSG:25830) and ensure they all had a consistent cell size of 100x100 meters. Then, each raster was clipped to the boundaries of Spain using a vector layer of the country. Finally, it was verified that the units of the R and K factors were consistent with the required $\text{MJ mm ha}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$ and $\text{t ha h ha}^{-1} \text{MJ}^{-1} \text{mm}^{-1}$ respectively, to maintain uniformity in the dataset before proceeding with the RUSLE calculation.

Application cookbook

The RUSLE (Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation) was calculated using the raster calculator in QGIS. The equation used was $\text{RUSLE} = R * K * LS * C * P$, where each factor represents rainfall erosivity (R), soil erodibility (K), topographic factor (LS), cover management (C), and support practice (P). After ensuring all input raster layers were reprojected, resampled, and clipped to the same extent and resolution, they were multiplied together to produce the final soil erosion risk map. The resulting RUSLE values represent the potential average annual soil loss in tons per hectare per year.

Results

Application cookbook

Figure 3.11.1 Soil erosion estimation using RUSLE, following the Cookbook instruction

Comparison

Figure 3.11.2 Soil erosion from National Soil Erosion Inventory (INES-Inventario Nacional de Erosión de Suelos): https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/biodiversidad/temas/inventarios-nacionales/inventario-nacional-erosion-suelos/estado_actual.html

Table 3.11.1. Spanish surface of soils affected by sheet and rill erosion in relation to different erosive levels. Source: Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación (2021), https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/desarrollo-rural/participacion-publica/211130-esae-pepac_informacion-publica_tcm30-582415.pdf (page 46)

	EROSIVE LEVEL (Mg ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)					TOTAL
	0-25	25-50	50-100	100-200	>200	
Spanish surface (ha)	43 732 741.61	2 719 104.96	1 476 057.13	710 108.37	285 846.8	48 923 858,87

3.12 Synthesis

Table 3.12.1 provides an overview of the use of member state (MS) and EU data for the RUSLE applications in the different countries.

Table 3.12.1. Use of member state (MS) and EU data for the different RUSLE factors

Member State	R	K	LS	C	P
Austria	MS	MS (SOC) & EU (texture)	EU	MS (land use) & EU (C-factor table)	EU
Belgium	MS	MS	EU	MS	Not used
Denmark	No results provided				
France	EU	MS	MS	MS (crops) & EU (other)	EU
Hungary	MS	MS	EU	EU	EU
Ireland	EU	MS	EU	EU	EU
Italy	MS	MS	MS	MS	MS
Latvia	No results provided				
Lithuania	MS	EU	MS	MS	MS
Netherlands	MS	EU (texture) & MS (SOC)	EU	EU	EU
Poland	MS	MS	EU	EU	EU
Slovakia	MS	EU	EU	MS	EU
Spain	EU	EU	EU	EU	EU
MS	8	8	3	6	8
EU	3	3	8	5	2

Table 3.12.1 shows that almost all MS have used a combination of MS and EU data, the only exceptions being Italy (only MS data) and Spain (only EU data). MSs data were mainly used for R, K and P factors whereas EU data were largely preferred in the case of LS factor. This could be explained by the fact that relief is a widely well-known information, and that the expected enhancement due to the use of national data is quite low as EU maps have 25 m resolution at MS level. Nearly half of the MS used their own data for the C factor. In Austria, France and the Netherlands, a combination of EU and MS data was used to estimate K and/or C factors.

This shows, on the one hand, that cookbook application has been successful in using MS data when these were available, but on the other hand Table 3.12.1 also shows that hardly any MS applied the cookbook in the same way. Though this hampers a comparison of results between MS, the main aim of the cookbook application was to compare cookbook results with earlier results for the different MS. For that aim, variability in application between MS is not a problem.

Table 3.12.2 provides a summary of the qualitative comparison between maps resulting from the cookbook application and maps resulting from earlier assessment of soil erosion at MSS scale. Similarities and differences in simulated values and in simulated patterns were analysed. It should be realised that differences in values should only be looked at if the same method has been used in the earlier assessment as in the cookbook. Differences in patterns can always be assessed, at least in a qualitative way. Logically, this comparison was not possible for MSs not having former information: Ireland and the Netherlands.

Table 3.12.2. Differences between cookbook application and earlier results from member states.

Member States	Difference type (S, V, P, V&P*)	Comments on differences (Cookbook versus former map)	Possible explanations of differences	Spatial resolution of former map (m)
Austria	P	Higher erosion in mountainous areas	Importance of LS and C factors in RUSLE, RUSLE to be applied only in arable land	25?
Belgium	V	Importance of LS factor: higher values in the hilly areas of the south	Averaging due to the resolution of the EU data; various magnitude of the factors implying higher importance of LS and R factors	5
France	V&P	Lower erosion in areas well-known for erosion: Normandy, Brittany, Loire Valley... and higher erosion in the south of France	The importance of the slope seems overestimated in RUSLE. Results not directly comparable with a previous work which has estimated not an erosion rate but an erosion risk.	90
Hungary	V	The largest differences found in hilly areas and foothills.	Different data and methods for factors calculation + former map results from and ensemble model of USLE and PESERA.	1ha plots
Italy (Tuscany)	V	Comparison of maps with EU data only or regional data only. Higher values with regional data	Importance of R factor, which is better characterized at local scale, in mountainous area.	10?
Lithuania	S	Low erosion risk, whatever the data	Higher risk of erosion when the resolution of data decreases. National information of C factor in more accurate in elimination of areas where erosion does not occur.	10
Poland	S	Highest values in the south (mountainous and loess plateau areas)	RUSLE more sensitive and accurate in the northern part	?
Slovakia	V	Overall low erosion in the country, lower severe erosion	Lower values of K and LS factor in EU dataset, and consequently lower erosion	5
Spain	V&P	Higher values in mountainous areas of the north;		25

		lower value in the south-center		
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* S: Similar; V: difference mainly in values; P: difference mainly in patterns; V&P: difference in values & patterns

In 6 out of MSs, the main differences concern the values, meaning that globally the patterns are similar between the different evaluations. Except in Slovakia where erosion is globally low, it was observed that the differences occur mainly in hilly areas. This underlines the importance of the LS factor. Because it is a distributed variable, the resolution of the digital elevation model used and the way of calculation of this factor is crucial. Yet, for all MSs except France and Hungary, the resolution of earlier national map was substantially lower than for the cookbook application. This implies differences in the results, mainly for the steepest areas.

MSs exhibiting similar patterns and values, Poland and Lithuania, are not much affected by moderate or severe erosion.

In this section, differences in results between earlier assessment and cookbook application have been summarized, and some possible factors explaining these differences have been identified. However, the analysis presented here does not provide answers to questions like:

- Which of the two maps is better?
- Are the results realistic?

Such questions are hard to answer, as this would require independent information. Such information is, however, rarely available and even if there are for example soil erosion measurements it is questionable whether these can be directly compared to model results. Reasons for that include:

- The scale at which erosion measurements are done might not match the pixel size that is used in the model
- Erosion in the field is determined by true rainfall and rainfall erosivity, while in the model climatic data are used
- Measurements have their own issues in terms of representativeness. For example, there is a tendency for erosion plots to focus on areas in which erosion is perceived as a problem.
- Measurements of soil loss are the net result of all erosion processes that occur in the measured area, including also deposition. RUSLE on the other hand only models sheet and rill erosion. Whether or not this is an issue does depend on the scale of the measurement too. If the scale is close to the standard plots that have been used for the development of RUSLE (about 22 m length) it may not be such an issue since the measurements that have been used to develop RUSLE than also represented the sum of all erosion processes & deposition in the plot.

For all these reasons, only expert/stakeholder opinion can be used to assess which map is better. Besides, stakeholder involvement is also crucial to determine whether the maps produced are actually useful in practice. Therefore, the factual comparison presented here will be supplemented by a stakeholder evaluation in WP1 of SERENA.

4 SOC loss

Soil organic carbon stock (SOCS) loss (Mg C ha^{-1}) was selected as ideal indicator of the SOC loss threat (Montagne et al., 2024), but the application of such an indicator assessments would require the SOC data availability for at least two moments in time. As this was not the case, SOC concentration (often referred to as content) (g C kg^{-1} soil or %, which amounts to $\text{g C } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$ soil) was selected as pragmatic indicator of the SOC loss threat (Montagne et al., 2024), though it is clear that SOC content is not always a good proxy for SOC loss.

Therefore, the assessment of the SOC loss indicator at the EU Member State level is nothing more than the extension of SOC concentrations measured at selected sampling points to unsampled locations in each Member State. Details are provided by the D2.3.2 (Buttafuoco et al., 2024). The following sections present the results of cookbook applications for SOC content that have been done within the framework of SERENA.

4.1 Belgium

Katrien Oorts, Davor Josipovic and Dries Luts

Region (if not national scale): Flanders

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ⁿ¹	Availability data
<i>SOC monitoring data</i>	625 points for 2021-2024 of the regional soil organic carbon network of Flanders (Cmon)		Not available (more info in Oorts et al., 2024)
<i>Land use</i>	Landgebruiksk kaart 2022 and landgebruiksbestand Vlaanderen niveau 1 2022	10 * 10 m	https://metadata.vlaanderen.be/srv/dut/catalog.search#/metadata/e95731c2-4493-5266-81e4-01fea178ff74
<i>Soil</i>	Digitale bodemkaart van het Vlaamse gewest	Vector data 1:20.000	https://www.dov.vlaanderen.be/geonetwork/srv/dut/catalog.search#/metadata/a1547a01-b9fc-40fa-a2eb-009a39c02c7b
<i>Soil</i>	WRB Soil Units 40k: Bodemkaart van het Vlaamse Gewest volgens het internationale bodemclassificatiesysteem World Reference Base op schaal 1:40.000	Vector data 1:40.000	https://www.dov.vlaanderen.be/geonetwork/srv/dut/catalog.search#/metadata/83c46eae-a202-454c-b063-a858be3e4335

<i>Climate</i>	Climate data of the climate portal of Flanders		A selection of https://kaartencatalogus.toepassingen.vmm.vlaanderen.be/
<i>Relief</i>	Digitaal Hoogtemodel Vlaanderen II, DTM, raster, hydrocorr	5 * 5 m	https://metadata.vlaanderen.be/srv/dut/catalog.search#/metadata/9b0f82c7-57c4-463a-8918-432e41a66355 : version that is not corrected (corrected version not online available)
<i>Relief</i>	GHG (Gemiddeld Hoogste Grondwaterstand) and GLG (Gemiddeld Laagste Grondwaterstand)		
Parent material	Tertiair geologische kaart	Vector data 1:50.000	https://www.dov.vlaanderen.be/geonetwork/srv/dut/catalog.search#/metadata/06d1a1d7-d46c-43d6-96aa-25225b57dd8b
Vegetation	Bodembedekkingskaart (BBK), 1m resolutie, opname 2018		https://metadata.vlaanderen.be/srv/dut/catalog.search#/metadata/7e89f7df-8cca-4fd6-a954-735bcc6e7930

Methods

Data preparation

Soil data from the regional soil organic carbon network Cmon in Flanders were processed in order to obtain a value for the 0-20 cm soil layer based on the data of the 0-10 and 10-30 cm soil layers. Vector maps were rasterized on a resolution of 100m.

Application cookbook

The Digital Soil Mapping method (DSM) proposed in EJP SOIL WP6 (<https://shiny.wur.nl/content/71ff48b3-6e26-4b6b-8d07-ec9a05c64cc8/>) was used. This is a Digital Soil Mapping workflow developed at ISRIC. This workflow starts from standardised inputs, it organises data for modelling, performs modelling with Random Forest and creates soil maps as final outputs, including pixel based uncertainty. In EJP SOIL WP6 DSM different scenarios of different combinations of input data and covariables are proposed.

Comparison results

The existing map of soil organic carbon for Flanders is the [Soil Organic Carbon Stock Map for Belgium](#) which was the basis for Belgian for the Global Soil Organic Carbon stock (GSOC) map. This existing map could not be compared with the result of the SERENA cookbook application because the GSOC map was based on measurements from the 1947-1975 period whereas the SERENA map was based on measurement from the 2021-2023 period. Moreover, the GSOC map represents soil organic carbon stocks in contrast to the SERENA map representing soil organic carbon concentrations.

Results

Application cookbook

The DSM resulted in the map shown in Figure 4.1.1. The resulting map is the first map that is based on recent measurement of soil organic carbon in Flanders. The input data of soil organic carbon

concentration in Flanders was very variable with even extreme outliers. These outliers were analysed and were found to be correct and realistic and were thus left in the dataset.

For the DSM of soil organic carbon concentration in Flanders, the scenario including the combination of the use of regional point data of organic carbon concentration and regional covariates gave much better model results compared to the scenario with only LUCAS soil point data and European wide data covariates. This means that for SERENA the DSM with the use of only regional data was selected. The resolution of the used regional covariates was higher than 100 m for all covariates as Belgium (Flanders) because Flanders has a high spatial variability in land use and soil characteristics. The DSM resulted finally in a 100m resolution map.

Due to the very high variability of the input data, DSM mapping of soil organic carbon concentration for Flanders is difficult resulting in moderate model metrics. Therefore, the resulting map cannot be used at local level, but it gives a realistic idea of the geographical distribution of soil organic carbon concentrations across Flanders.

OC mean 0-20cm

OC Q0.05 0-20cm

Figure 4.1.1: Digital soil map of soil organic carbon concentration (g/kg) (0-20 cm soil layer) in Belgium (Flanders) for the period 2021-2024 (mean, Q0,05 and Q0,95).

Recommendations

In EJP SOIL WP6 DSM every country will provide DSM maps for soil organic carbon concentration all using the same script. In contrast in SERENA, countries used according to the cookbook different methodologies for the modelling of soil organic carbon concentration. Therefore, it is recommended to use the DSM derived maps of EJP SOIL WP6 DSM that will become available in November 2024 as final maps for soil organic carbon concentration for the entire EJP SOIL project and not the more diverse results of SERENA in order to avoid publishing different maps for the same property.

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4.2 Estonia

Elsa Putku, Tambet Kikas

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
Land use	agricultural land of EE, also used as a mask	100 * 100 m	derived from Estonian Topographic Database: https://geo-portaal.maaamet.ee/index.php?lang_id=2&page_id=618
Soil	1037 point data of measured SOC (%)	point data	not available

Climate	Temperature (2m); Total precipitation; Runoff; Total evaporation; Surface net solar radiation	100*100 m	ERA5-Land Monthly Averaged - ECMWF Climate Reanalysis https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-land-monthly-means?tab=overview Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM). 10.5067/GPM/IMERG/3B-MONTH/06
Topography	Elevation	100*100 m	MERIT DEM a high accuracy global DEM at 3 arc second resolution. https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GL072874
Parent material	dominant and secondary parent material	100*100m	European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC), https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/european-soil-database-v20-vector-and-attribute-data

Methods

Data preparation

SOC data available for agricultural soils were obtained from the PANDA database, which contains regular soil monitoring and voluntary soil sampling data by farmers. Soil sampling data collected from agricultural lands for the period 2015–2021 was used in cookbook application and the database is managed by the Centre of Estonian Rural Research and Knowledge. Composite soil samples in the PANDA database were collected by licensed personnel following the same prescribed sampling strategy (prescribed sampling route and sampling density, depth, and volume) and analyzed in the same laboratory using the wet oxidation method (sulfochromic oxidation, similar to Walkley-Black). All soil samples from arable lands were collected in late summer or autumn at minimum 2–3 months after last fertilization and, in case of winter crops in crop rotation, before the sowing of crops. In the case of application of organic fertilizers, the soil samples were collected not earlier than 6 months after fertilization. The same field was resampled every 4–5 years. To achieve the aim for accounting SOC loss in agricultural soils, re-visited locations were used to calculate the change in SOC stock. The selection of temporal pairs of data resulted with 1037 paired points where the interval between second sampling was more than 5 years.

The SOC stocks were calculated for the depth of 20 cm using the following equation:

$$\text{SOC stock (t ha}^{-1}\text{)} = \text{BD (g cm}^{-3}\text{)} * \text{D (cm)} * \text{SOC (g kg}^{-1}\text{)}$$

where BD is soil bulk density, SOC is soil organic carbon concentration, and D is the depth of soil layer.

As the bulk density was not measured, the bulk density values were estimated by Adams (1973) equation:

$$\text{BD (g cm}^{-3}\text{)} = 100 / (\text{SOM} / 0.244 + (100 - \text{SOM}) / 1.64)$$

where BD is calculated soil bulk density, SOM is soil organic matter concentration in percent (%), 0.244 is bulk density of soil organic matter (SOM), 1.64 is the bulk density of soil mineral matter. It was assumed that SOM contains 58% SOC.

The calculated SOC stock for time0 and time2 (> 5 years resampled locations) were used as input point for digital soil mapping. The covariates in the EU scale were used (except for land use covariates): The

list with the URLs can be found [here](#). After the prediction of SOC stock on Estonian agricultural soils in two time points, the sequestration rate for 5 year period was calculated using the following equation:

absolute sequestration rate ($\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ a}^{-1}$): $(\text{SOC stock}_{t_2} - \text{SOC stock}_{t_0})/5$

Application cookbook

The methodology designed by ISRIC (Genova, G., Poggio, L., Kempen, B., & Colman, B. DSM Workflow Seedling. ISRIC - World Soil Information. <https://doi.org/10.17027/ISRIC-FSX2-2691>) was used as cookbook, but replacing Copernicus Global Land Cover Layers covariates with national covariate of agricultural land.

Comparison results

Earlier results refer to D3.1.1, were the absolute sequestration rates (ASR) ($\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) in Estonia were shown.

Results

SOC stock loss is more dominant in soil with higher organic carbon concentrations. Carbon stock has increased in soils with naturally lower carbon. The maximum SOC loss in the estimation was $-1,52 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ y}^{-1}$ and maximum increase in SOC stock was $0,81 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ y}^{-1}$ with an total average of $-0,02 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ y}^{-1}$. This results in accordance with calculation from actual measurements and analysis made in the country.

Figure 4.2.1. SOC stock change in Estonian agricultural land.

Comparison

Previously, the change in SOC stock has been quantified using the methodology developed by FAO using ROTC model (Peralta et al 2022). As this map has errors for Estonia as the organic soils are included in the modelling but RothC model cannot be applied for organic soils. Therefore the results are biased and can't be used. Nevertheless, for comparison the same range of ASR was visualized in the FAO map although the actual range is much wider and wrong (-69...1,57 t C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹). The results with the new map are not compatible: the highest increase is in the northern coast of the country opposite to the results of the new map.

Figure 4.2.2. Absolute sequestration rate using RothC model in the FAO GSOC seq framework (business as usual scenario- SOC stock in 2020)

Recommendations

DSM workflow developed by ISRIC is very easy to use however the cookbook for SOC loss needs further to be developed as the SIRIC cookbook was not designed for calculating SOC loss or SOC stocks.

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4.3 France

Nicolas Saby

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
Soil Carbon content data	Observations of soil carbon content down to 20 cm harmonized using a equal area spline approach	Ca 30 000 soil profiles	Data not available
EJP Covariates	Covariates provided by ISRIC within the T6.2 of the EJP project	90 m	Contact ISRIC
French covariate	Covariates produced by Dobarco et al ((2019)) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2019.02.036	90 m	

Methods

Data preparation

The observations were produced through soil mapping programs in France. Soil observations collected in the field at the horizon support were harmonized to produce estimates of the soil organic carbon content for the 0-20cm soil layer. For this, we use the equal area splines approach (V. L. Mulder et al., 2016).

Application cookbook

We followed the framework proposed within the EJP T6.2

Comparison results

There are already 5 existing soil carbon content or stock maps ready to use. The first one was produced by (Arrouays et al., 2001) using a simple statistical approach. Then 4 digital soil mapping approaches were implemented (Martin, 2019; Meersmans et al., 2012; V.L. Mulder et al., 2016; Suleymanov et al., 2024). However, none of these previous results met the specifications of the cookbook. This is then the most up to date version of the soil carbon content map for 0 to 20 cm as it is based on recent digital soil mapping algorithm and recent covariates. By way of comparison, we can refer to the results of the map from (V.L. Mulder et al., 2016), which show validation results of the same order of magnitude than the one of the cookbook, i.e. an Model efficiency coefficient of around 0.3.

Figure 4.3.1. Topsoil carbon content in France

Results

Application cookbook

It is clearly visible in the map (Figure 4.3.1) that vegetation and topography were overall the most important drivers of SOC content variation in mainland France but that the set of most important covariates varied greatly among locations and carbon-landscape zones. An extended discussion can be found in Wadoux et al. (2023)

Comparison

We found no notable difference in results with previous studies investigating the mapping and the controlling factors of SOC (Arrouays et al., 2001) and SOC stock variation in France (e.g. Martin et al., 2011; Mulder et al., 2015).

Recommendations

The use of the digital soil mapping pipeline developed by ISRIC within of the EJP task 6.2 allows to produce harmonized results

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4.4 Hungary

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Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
Soil	Soil type map of Hungary (Pásztor et al., 2018)	100 * 100 m	Available for browsing at https://dosoremi.hu/en
Climate	Long-term mean annual - evapotranspiration, - evaporation, - precipitation, - temperature (Szentimrey et al., 2007)	100 * 100 m	Not publicly available
Organisms	CORINE Land Cover 2012	100 * 100 m	Available at https://doi.org/10.2909/a84ae124-c5c5-4577-8e10-511bfe55cc0d
Relief	EU-DEM and derivatives	25 * 25 m	Available at https://www.eea.europa.eu
Parent material	Geological map of Hungary (Gyalog & Síkhegyi, 2005)	1:100,000 vector	Available for browsing at https://map.mbfisz.gov.hu/fdt100/

Methods

Data preparation

SOC data was derived from the Hungarian Soil Information and Monitoring System (SIMS) launched in 1992. SIMS is a countrywide soil monitoring system, consists of 1236 monitoring sites, and provides biological, physical and chemical information on the status and temporal change of Hungarian soils. In the framework of SIMS, SOC data are available from 1992, 1995, 1998, 2000, 2004, 2007, 2010, 2013, and 2016. Until 2000, the sampling was carried out according to the genetic horizons, however, since 2000, the sampling was carried out for depths 0-30 cm, 30-60 cm, and 60-90 cm by 9 boreholes within a 50 m radius of the point. For the present mapping of SOC concentration, the 0-30 cm depth of 2016 SIMS data was used.

The selection of environmental covariates, which are then used to model and map SOC content, was based on the ‘scorpan’ model (McBratney et al., 2003). The model consists of (s) soil properties, (c)

climate, (o) organisms, (r) relief, (p) parent material, (a) age and (n) spatial coordinates, which are groups of variables used to describe the relationship between the soil and the environment. The environmental covariates were resampled into a common geographic reference system with a resolution of 100 * 100 meters.

Application cookbook

Random forest kriging (RFK) (Keskin & Grunwald, 2018; Szatmári & Pásztor, 2019) was used for the prediction of the SOC concentration. RFK is a combination of the random forest machine learning algorithm (Breiman, 2001) and the kriging technique (Webster and Oliver, 2007). In RFK, first a random forest model is fitted between SOC concentration and the environmental covariates, then it is used for predicting the deterministic part of the spatial variation. Second, representing the stochastic part of variation kriging is carried out based on the random forest residuals, and then it is added to prediction given by the random forest. The prediction performance was investigated by a 10-fold cross-validation (Szatmári et al., 2019). The prediction of SOC concentration was carried out using the 'sp' (Pebesma & Bivand, 2005), 'gstat' (Pebesma, 2004), 'rgdal' (Bivand et al., 2023), 'raster' (Hijmans et al., 2013) and 'randomForest' (Liaw & Wiener, 2002) R packages.

The 100 m * 100 m resolution grid system of the environmental covariates served also as the target grid into which the predicted values for the SOC concentration (g kg^{-1}) map of the topsoil (0-30 cm) were to be calculated. Urban areas, lakes and rivers were excluded from the predicted map.

Comparison results

The maps reported in D3.1.1 referred to SOC stock, which show how much organic carbon is stored in the soils per unit area for a given soil layer, thus the result map cannot be directly compared with them.

The soil organic matter (SOM) map of the [DOSoReMI.hu](https://dosoremi.hu) database (Pásztor et al. 2020) can be the basis of comparison with the new SOC concentration map, where the SIMS data referred to the year 1992. The methodology for compilation of both maps was the same, only the data used (reference data and auxiliary variables) were different. The values of the previously predicted SOM map were converted into SOC concentration, based on the assumption that soil organic matter contains 58 % carbon. Furthermore a unit conversion is needed from the [%] to [g kg^{-1}].

Results

Application cookbook

According to the SOC concentration result map for the topsoil (0-30 cm) of Hungary (Figure 4.4.1), the sandy soils in the Danube–Tisza Interfluve (in middle of the country), and the sandy soils of the Nyírség (East/North-East part of the country) have the lowest organic matter content. The highest SOC content values are found in the mountainous regions (e.g. Transdanubian Mountains, North Hungarian Mountains), however, it should also be taken into account that the rooting depth is relatively shallow there, and these areas are generally not under agricultural cultivation, but covered by forests or (semi)natural habitats, they are mostly nature conservation areas.

Figure 4.4.1. SOC concentration (g kg^{-1}) map for the topsoil (0-30 cm) of Hungary (SIMS2016)

Comparison

According to the difference map (Figure 4.4.2) between the SOC concentration map based on the dosoremi.hu database (SIMS1992, Figure 4.4.3), and based on the present report (SIMS2016, Figure 4.4.1), in 88 % of the mapped area the difference is less than 5 g kg^{-1} . SIMS2016 value is greater than SIMS1992 in 8 % of the pixels, and SIMS1992 value is greater than SIMS2016 in 4 % of pixels. However, the difference is greater than 10 g kg^{-1} in less than 2 % of the pixels.

The locations where SIMS1992 shows higher values than SIMS2016 occur mostly in peat soils or areas with high organic matter content, which are more sensitive and prone to change. On the other hand, most of the areas where SIMS2016 shows higher values are forests, which can store soil organic carbon well.

Although the methodology for compilation of both maps was the same, not only the reference data, but also the environmental co-variables were different. Consequently the difference between the two maps cannot necessarily be attributed to the change over time alone. For comparison over time more accurate results are available (Szatmári et al. 2019, 2021), although these are for SOC stock and not SOC concentration.

Figure 4.4.2. Difference between SIMS1992 and SIMS2016. Yellow: the difference is less than 5 g kg^{-1} ; green shades: SIMS2016 value is greater than SIMS1992 in the given pixel; purple shades: SIMS1992 value is greater than SIMS2016 in the given pixel

Figure 4.4.3. SOM content (%) map for the topsoil (0-30 cm) of Hungary based on the dosoremi.hu database (SIMS1992)

Recommendations

It is beneficial that the cookbook is flexible in terms of the methods as well as the data to be used. In the long term, it would be the most appropriate to map and to analyze the ideal indicator (SOC stock change), not just the SOC concentration at a given year.

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4.5 Ireland

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Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
SOC database	Soil organic carbon data (0-0.30 m)	141 locations (Figure 4.5.1)	LUCAS 2018 TOPSOIL data - ESDAC - European Commission (europa.eu)

Figure 4.5.1: Soil sample locations (Red filled diamonds)

Methods

Data preparation

The distribution of SOC data was highly skewed. Therefore, before the application of the approach, SOC data were transformed into a Gaussian distribution using a Gaussian anamorphosis (Wackernagel, 2003) and then back transformed into raw data after the spatial interpolation.

Application cookbook

A map of SOC concentrations for the Republic of Ireland was produced using a geostatistical approach. Particularly, ordinary kriging (Chilès & Delfiner, 2012) was used to map SOC concentration (%) at national scale.

Comparison results

No direct comparison was possible because there was no previous SOC map. The Indicative Soil Organic Carbon Stock Map of Irish Agricultural Soils (0-50cm) by Creamer et al. (2016) offers an indicative comparison, although it is not directly comparable.

Results

Application cookbook

The variographic analysis (Figure 4.5.2) based on SOC Gaussian values showed that the variation occurred at two scales: the first at around 25 km and the second at 129 km.

Figure 4.5.2: Experimental variogram (filled green dots) and fitted theoretical model (solid red line) of Gaussian soil organic carbon values. The experimental variance (black dashed line) is also reported.

Moreover, there is a different slope between the first part of the variogram and the second, indicating a very fast variation in the first part (short range) and a slower variation in the second part (long range). The explanation could be attributed to orographic factors, land use, etc.

The fitted variogram model and Gaussian data were used with ordinary kriging to predict SOC values at the node of a 50 m x 50 m grid and obtain a map of Gaussian SOC values. These values were back transformed to raw values (Figure 4.5.3).

Figure 4.5.3: Map of SOC obtained by using ordinary kriging

Evaluation

The reliability of the SOC map varies across Ireland due to the spatial disparity of sampling points (shown in Figure 4.5.1). In areas with a higher frequency of sampling points, particularly in the south central, southeast, and east of Ireland, the map shows a higher resolution and sensitivity of SOC content. These areas of higher sampling frequency also identify a distinct area of high SOC peatlands located around the Wicklow/Dublin Mountains despite the majority of surrounding soils being $< 78.79 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$ SOC. Evidently, SOC concentration values for these regions are relatively reliable due to the abundance of data points supporting the interpolation.

However, in regions with more sparse or no SOC measurements, the reliability evidently decreased. For example, County Donegal (North West of Ireland) has only four sampling points over an area of 4,860 km². Donegal shows a near continuous mask of very high SOC concentrations. Peatlands and high SOC soils are widespread here, although the SOC concentrations have likely been overtly influenced by the four sampling points, masking several known pockets of lower SOC soils. On the other hand, Figure 4.5.3 shows suspiciously low SOC content in substantial peatland areas along the west coast of Galway and Mayo which again coincide with significant gaps in sampling points (Figure 4.5.1). Despite this, peat extents are largely represented well on the map.

Due to the inconsistent and spatially diverse sampling points, which neglect a number of large areas within the country, the map is not overtly useful for SOC analysis at a local or regional scale, but does give a display of the general geographical distribution of SOC concentrations across Ireland.

Comparison

The comparison between the Indicative Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) Stock Map of Agricultural Soils (0-50 cm) by Creamer et al. (2016) (Figure 4.5.4) and the SOC map of Ireland derived from LUCAS data (Figure 4.5.3) reveals several critical differences which highlights both maps' distinct approaches to illustrating SOC distribution across Ireland. The Creamer et al. (2016) map exhibits SOC content for mineral and organo-mineral soils and excludes peat soils. Their methodology combines modal profile and bulk density data, either measured directly in the field or estimated through pedotransfer functions.

Conversely, the LUCAS SOC map does include SOC concentrations for peatlands. This inclusion is particularly relevant given that peatbogs comprise approximately 13.8% of Ireland's land cover according to the Central Statistics Office (2019). However, the LUCAS map's reliability is uneven due to the spatial inconsistencies in sampling points. Regions like the south-central, southeast, and east of Ireland, where sampling is more frequent, show more reliable SOC data. In contrast, areas with fewer sampling points, such as County Donegal, seem to display 'masked' or more uniform SOC concentrations with less spatial sensitivity.

While the LUCAS map offers broader coverage, including valuable data on peatlands, its reliability at local or regional scales is compromised by these sampling inconsistencies. The Creamer et al. (2016) map, although more restricted in scope, provides more precise data for mineral and organo-mineral soils. The two maps do share a modest similarity in SOC distribution (excluding peats), but they are difficult to directly compare. Both maps underscore the necessity for a denser, more uniform sampling framework across the country to improve the reliability of SOC estimates. The integration of comprehensive peat soil data would also enrich the accuracy of future SOC maps for Ireland

Figure 4.5.4: Indicative soil organic carbon stock map of agricultural soils (0-50cm). Creamer et al. (2016)

Recommendations

The availability of data is crucial, and the LUCAS database in its various editions appears to be a key contribution at least to having a general overview of the organic carbon content in soils. Unfortunately, at national scale no covariate was suitable to improve the estimation of SOC concentration at unsampled locations.

The availability of SOC databases of adequate quality and sample size should also be urgently addressed at national level.

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4.6 Italy

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Region (if not national scale): Tuscany Region

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
SOC database	Soil organic carbon data (0-0.30 m)	4727 sample locations (Figure 4.6.1)	Tuscany Region database (Gardin et al., 2021). Not freely available (Lamma Consortium). More information and requests to: info@lamma.toscana.it

Figure 4.6.1. Soil sample locations

Methods

Data preparation

The distribution of SOC data was highly skewed and before the application of the approach, SOC data were transformed into a Gaussian distribution using a Gaussian anamorphosis (Wackernagel, 2003) and back transformed into raw data after the spatial interpolation.

Application cookbook

A map of SOC concentrations for the Tuscany Region was produced using a geostatistical approach. Particularly, ordinary kriging (Chilès & Delfiner, 2012) coupled with local geostatistics (LGS) were used

to map SOC concentration (%) at regional scale in Tuscany Region (Italy). Local geostatistics (LGS) approach (Chilès & Delfiner, 2012) was used as an alternative to a global model of spatial dependence. According the LGS approach, the geostatistical parameters involved in variogram-based modelling were locally (within a 20-km grid mesh) optimized ensuring a better adequacy between the geostatistical model and the data.

Comparison results

The SOC map obtained in this application was compared with the one obtained using random forest according to the FAO Soil Organic Carbon Mapping Cookbook (FAO, 2018). Random forest was applied using the same SOC dataset and some morphometric and climatic attributes as covariates (elevation, aspect, diffuse and direct insolation, length and slope RUSLE factor, plan and profile curvature, slope, aridity index, annual average precipitation, Fournier index, Bagnouls Gausson index, etc.). The comparison was made by looking at SOC maps in particular areas and by mapping the differences between the two SOC maps.

Results

Application cookbook

In Figure 4.6.2 is shown the map of SOC obtained by using ordinary kriging coupled with LGS, whereas in Figure 4.6.3, the map of the standard deviation of errors obtained by the application of ordinary kriging for predicting SOC at unsampled locations.

Figure 4.6.2. Map of SOC obtained by using ordinary kriging coupled with LGS.

Figure 4.6.3. Kriging standard deviation of SOC

Comparison/evaluation

The SOC map obtained in this application was compared with the one obtained using random forest according to the FAO Soil Organic Carbon Mapping Cookbook (FAO, 2018). Random forest was applied using the same SOC dataset and some covariates (morphometric and climatic attributes).

Figure 4.6.4. Map of SOC obtained by using random forest according to the FAO SOC cookbook. Italian soil regions are also reported.

Figure 4.6.5. Map of SOC obtained by using ordinary kriging coupled with LGS with the same SOC classes of Figure 4.6.4. Italian soil regions are also reported.

The comparison between the two approaches has been focused on some specific areas. The first comparison has been carried out on the Pratomagno area (Figure 4.6.6), whereas the second (Figure 4.6.7) on a coastal area around Pisa and Lucca:

Figure 4.6.6. Map of SOC for Pratomagno area obtained by random forest (a) and ordinary kriging (b).

Figure 4.6.7. Map of SOC for a coastal area around Pisa and Lucca area obtained by random forest (a) and ordinary kriging (b).

From the analysis of the SOC maps of the two areas, in addition to the differences in SOC values, the pattern of SOC variation is worthy of being shown. Maps of the two areas obtained with the use of ordinary kriging, show the typical smoothed pattern and the presence of rounded shapes (Figs 4.6.6b and 4.6.7b). In contrast, maps obtained from random forest using covariates and, in particular, morphometric attributes, more closely reproduce the orography of the two areas (Figs 4.6.6a and 4.6.7a).

The map of differences in SOC concentrations for the two approaches is shown in Figure 4.6.8.

Figure 4.6.8. Map of differences in SOC concentrations obtained by random forest and ordinary kriging.

The areas characterized by the greatest differences in SOC content between the two spatial interpolation methods are shown in red in Figure 4.6.8. For enhanced identification of these areas, they are shown at a larger scale in Figure 4.6.9.

Figure 4.6.9. Map of differences in SOC concentrations obtained by the two approaches for Pratomagno area (a), the coastal area around Pisa and Lucca (b), and mountainous areas of Apuan Alps (c).

The greatest differences between the two approaches occurred in areas with higher organic carbon concentrations in which there are peat (Massaciuccoli, Bientina, Fucecchio) and mountain areas (Apuane, Amiata, Apennine ridge). In these areas, ordinary kriging underestimates compared to random forest. In the areas where ordinary kriging slightly overestimates compared to random forest, this would seem to be due to local differences in land use (e.g., agricultural areas with wooded areas around them) and in the inland valley bottoms (Lunigiana, Abetone valley bottom, Casentino).

The map of SOC obtained by random forest relies, sometimes sharply, on limits of soil, land use, morphology, altitude and exposure. Whether or not these aforementioned covariates are correlated, at a regional level, with the SOC, the map of SOC would be more detailed and should better respond to an expected (or predictable on pedological basis) logical-theoretical pattern.

Recommendations

Each mapping application must necessarily be adapted to the availability of data on the property or attribute of interest and covariates to be used in the procedure of digital soil mapping. A very critical issue is the availability of covariates at the scale/resolution at which one is working. Moreover, these covariates must be of appropriate quality for the specific digital soil mapping approach. Furthermore, in the absence of independent validation data, the involvement of local/national stakeholders cannot be disregarded.

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4.7 Lithuania

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Data used

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
<i>Vector database of soil typological units of Lithuania</i>	Dirv_DR10LT-1554 database. Spatial contours of soil typological units according to the Lithuanian LTKD-99 classification harmonized with the FAO 1998 system. M 1: 10 000; converted to raster. 2021	10 * 10m.	Primary data is available to registered Lithuanian users at www.geoportal.lt
<i>SOC measurement data in points</i>	<i>Armolaitis K. 2016. Evaluation of National Organic Carbon Stocks and the Determination of Stock Values in Organic and Mineral Soils in Forest and Non-Forest Land. XLS Data Base.</i>	242 samples	Primary data is available in the Ministries of Environment and Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania.
	<i>Žydelis R., Volungevičius J., Amalevičiūtė-Volungė K. 2021-2022. Topsoil (0-10cm) SOC data from EJP soil project STEROPES.</i>	275 samples	Primary data is available at the EJP project executors.

Methods

Data preparation

The SOC map was compiled based on the contours of the Lithuanian soil GIS database (Dirv_DR10LT-1554, 2022, scale 1:10,000). We prepared the map using the IGA (Integrated Geographical Approach) methodology, which is currently submitted for publication. 275 samples from the Central plains of Lithuania agricultural soil cover were collected and 242 (arable land samples from the total sample – 745) points from the official scientific report on which the publication was based were used. In total, 517 points were used to create the map. The sample of soil samples is formed in such a way that it represents the variety of soil typological units according to the soil typological group, moisture regime and degree of moisture prevailing in Lithuania. Anthrosols were not used in the mapping because Anthrosols are identified in urbanized areas that were not mapped during this study. Samples were taken only from agricultural land that was not covered with vegetation, choosing the location of the point in such a way that it was at least 100m away from roads, forests, or other lands. Calculated average values of SOC, were related to soil contours. The following data were used for the cartographic basis of the map: National Land Service under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania: Dirv_DR10LT-1554 2021-02-24.

Application cookbook

When performing modeling and mapping of SOC in the topsoil layer, we did not use the cookbook recommendations, because the method in the cookbook (kriging) is less suitable in your case, and that our approach made optimal use of the available data.

The main principles of our method:

1. During the analysis, each soil sample was related to the name of the soil typological unit, based on the soil contours of the Dirv_DR10LT database and the refinement of their position in the area.
2. In the next step, the name of the soil typological unit was deconstructed into the type of moisture regime and degree of moisture.
3. Finally, average SOC values were calculated by additionally evaluating the degree of soil erosion.
4. Based on these identifiers, a statistical analysis of the SOC data was performed, during which the reliability and statistical differences of the data were evaluated.

For comparison, we present the results of SOC modelling using the classical geostatistical method (kriging) and our polygon analysis method described above.

Comparison results

The spatial differentiation of the amount of SOC depends not only on the continuous (most natural factors: mineral base, relief, moisture, vegetation cover) changing natural environment, but also on discrete natural (soil material and the related layout of wetlands) and human economic activity measures and as a result emerging land use structure. The classic geostatistical methods (e.g. Kriging) do not give a sufficiently accurate result, because these methods cannot estimate the spatial unevenness (discretion) factor of the soil cover properties of the mapped area and the structure of land features (non-mapped land: forests, lakes, water reservoirs, built-up areas, etc.). Interpolation methods are also unable to estimate 132 localised “extreme” SOC values, such as the localisation of soil erosion areas and peat soils. Both the Kriging method and the IGA (polygon analysis) methods we used essentially use the principle of averaging. However, the Kriging method, without being able to distinguish between background mean values and extreme values, applies the same averaging principles to all of them, thus distorting the ranges of extreme values, either by greatly increasing or decreasing them. In contrast, the averaging principle used in our IGA method applies the averaging principle to the expected (polygonal) range of the extreme values, and therefore does not distort the ranges of the extreme values.

Figure 4.7.1. The average content of SOC (%) in the topsoil (0-10cm) according to the type of soil moisture regime and the degree of erosion in the cells 10x10m.

Table 4.7.1. Distribution of SOC in the topsoil (0-10cm) layer according to soil moisture and erodibility groups.

The groups of moisture regime and the degree of erosion*	Area, ha		Average SOC content, %
	ha	%	
Automorphic, slightly eroded (AU (e3))	87621.11	1.78	0.66
Automorphic, moderately eroded (AU (e2))	277129.74	5.62	0.86
Automorphic, severely eroded (AU (e1))	344857.68	7.00	0.99
Automorphic (gleyic, deeper than 200cm) (AU)	1066060.50	21.63	1.36
Automorphic (gleyic, 100-200cm) (AU (g0, g1, j2))	211687.16	4.29	1.58
Semi-hydromorphic (gleyic, 50-100cm) (SH (g4, j6))	167372.38	3.39	1.86
Semi-hydromorphic (gleyic, up to 50cm) (SH (g8, j3, j7))	1557155.39	31.60	2.11
Semi-hydromorphic (gley, 50-100cm) (SH (g5))	47732.40	0.97	2.84
Semi-hydromorphic (gley, up to 50cm) (SH (G))	685492.05	13.91	2.89
Semi-hydromorphic (murshic, gley up to 50cm) (SH (Gfo))	30907.10	0.63	5.05
Semi-hydromorphic (peat, gley up to 50cm) (SH (Ghi))	35410.90	0.72	9.26
Hydromorphic (peat soils) (H)	416756.22	8.46	34.72

*AU – automorphic (gleyic, deeper than 200cm), AU(g0, g1, j2) – automorphic (gleyic, gley, stagnic 100 - 200cm), SH(g4, j6) – semi-hydromorphic (gleyic, stagnic 50 - 100cm), SH(g8, j3, j7) – semi-hydromorphic (gleyic, stagnic, stagno, up to 50cm), SH(G) – semi-hydromorphic (gley, up to 50cm), SH(Gfo) – semi-hydromorphic (folic, gley, up to 50cm), SH(Ghi) – semi-hydromorphic (histic, gley, up to 50cm), H – hydromorphic (Histosols), e1 – weakly eroded, e2 - moderately eroded, e3 – severely eroded.

Results

The SOC map is modeled only for agricultural territories, which cover about 55% of the territory of Lithuania. SOC distribution in these territories is directly correlated with the main agroecosystems in

the territory of Lithuania: hilly morainic uplands, clay lowlands (plains dominate) and sandy lowlands (plains dominate). Also, as a separate specific agroecosystem, river valleys can be distinguished, where intensive agricultural activities are also carried out and which occupy an intermediate position between lowlands and uplands in the context of SOC distributions. They have specific features of SOC distribution.

Clay lowlands (which are dominated by ground moraine areas) are dominated by semi-hydromorphic moisture regime soils, which are characterized by a gleyic and gley soils. Therefore, regardless of the typological unit of the soil, in these regions (the lowlands of Central Lithuania, Western and Southwestern part of Lithuania), soils with SOC in the topsoil layer of more than 2% dominate. Meanwhile, automorphically irrigated soils are characterized by relatively lower SOC values, with average values below 2%. This is determined not only by lower moisture content, which weakens the processes of humification and SOC accumulation, but also by soil erosion. Due to the intensive agriculture activities, which were carried out in the second half (Soviet period) of the 20th century, these soils were strongly eroded (AU, e3-e1 soil groups), so the SOC content in their topsoil (0-10cm) layer does not exceed 1% on average.

In the agro-ecosystems of river valleys, there is a double effect: the accumulation of SOC takes place in the alluvial part of the valley (Fluvisols) (Table 4.7.2.) and the loss of SOC takes place in the upper part of the slope of the valley due to intensive tillage and expansion of cultivated areas. Therefore, the river valleys in Central part of Lithuania are characterized by dominant soils with low SOC content.

The agro-ecosystems of sandy lowlands, which prevail in the Southeastern part of Lithuania, are dominated by sandy soils, which are less productive due to their texture. They have an average SOC of less than 1.5%. Also, most of these soils are forested and therefore not mapped.

Table 4.7.2. SOC content according to the main soil groups in Lithuania.

Soil groups	Average SOC content in the topsoil 0-10cm, %
Regosols	0.788
Retisols	1.015
Arenosols	1.515
Planosols	1.546
Luisols	1.675
Podzols	1.805
Cambisols	1.950
Fluvisols	2.061
Gleysols	4.228
Histosols	19.224
Leptosols	No data
Anthrosols	No data

The conducted research and the created map made it possible to generalize the results of the SOC content in the context of soil typological groups (names given according to WRB 2022). According to the amount of humus (after recalculation of SOC values) and the gradation used in Lithuania, soils containing more than 1.74% of organic carbon are considered to be high organic carbon soils. Therefore, such soils include: Cambisols, Gleysols, Fluvisols, partly Luisols and Podzols (Table 4.7.2.). The result is logical, because these are the dominant soils of the most fertile Lithuanian agro-ecosystems, formed in moraine loam deposits. Podzols falling on agricultural land are an exception. They are associated with wetter areas and are therefore not considered in this context. Soils with lower SOC are classified as: Regosols, Retisols, and Planosols (in which lower SOC content is related to erosion); Arenosols (lower SOC content is related to texture).

In summary, it can be stated that SOC rich soils (>1.74%) in Lithuanian agricultural land account for 59.68% of all agricultural land.

We did not perform a spatial analysis of the map (Figure 4.7.2) generated by the Kriging method, as it is not appropriate due to the obvious geographical illogicality of the results. The reasons for these results are discussed in the methodological part of the report.

Figure 4.7.2. SOC map using Kriging method. Map raster generated by G. Buttafuoco, Data: Armolaitis K. 2016. Evaluation of National Organic Carbon Stocks and the Determination of Stock Values in Organic and Mineral Soils in Forest and Non-Forest Land. XLS Data Base; Žydelis R., Volungevičius J., Amalevičiūtė-Volungė K. 2021-2022. Topsoil (0-10cm) SOC data from EJP soil project STEROPES.

The spatial differentiation of SOC in the territory of Lithuania is characterised by the following principles, which should not be neglected when modelling the spatial distribution of SOC:

1. The hilly upland areas are characterised by low SOC content because the soils are naturally less productive and have been intensively used for agriculture for about 70 years, which has led to severe soil erosion. This principle is more or less reflected in south-eastern Lithuania (Figure 4.7.2). However, it is distorted in north-eastern Lithuania (Figure 4.7.2). And it is practically not reflected in western Lithuania - the Samogitian uplands.
2. The clay lowlands are characterised by a high SOC content, as the soils are naturally productive, and the flat surface and the higher moisture content create natural conditions for SOC preservation. This principle is partly visible in central and northern Lithuania (Figure 4.7.2). However, it is distorted in the uplands of western Lithuania. The distortion is particularly strong in the Nemunas delta and the Curonian Spit. Here, the Kriging method extends the local high SOC values over a large area and covers atypical areas.

3. The local peat soil distribution areas are typical for the whole territory of Lithuania and their distribution is determined by local processes of glaciogenesis. The majority of the soil cover OC of the whole territory of Lithuania is concentrated here, but classical interpolation methods are not suitable for its assessment, as they distort the real situation very much.
4. Erosion areas are mainly concentrated in the hilly uplands, which means that the soils here are characterised by a moderately low SOC content, but sandy soils are also characterised by a low SOC content, which are concentrated in southern Lithuania and where the low SOC content is due to the natural conditions that formed these soils. At the same time, eroded soils are also present in central Lithuania, but their habitats are very localised and are the result of mistakes made by farming activities. Thus, the spread of low SOC soils in Lithuania is determined by different factors and cannot be assessed using the same interpolation principle.

Recommendations

Our research on the spatial distribution of SOC and general soil mapping shows that automatic interpolation mechanisms do not work, so we must look for ways that combine the following principles:

1. Compilation of a system of typical representative point selection principles.
2. Formation of objective statistical samples taking into account dominant soils and their properties.
3. Compilation of an algorithm of contouring principles and criteria, which would allow correct spatial interpolation of received statistically reliable data.

4.8 Poland

Sylwia Pindral

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
SOC monitoring data	Over 40'000 points for 2018 + over 4000 points for organic soils for 2018 (Density map below)	-	Not available for public use.
<p>SOC national</p> <p>Points per hexagon (250 km²)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0 1 - 20 21 - 40 41 - 60 >60 			
Land use	Land use map	100 * 100 m	https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/

<i>Soil</i>	Sand, silt, clay content, texture agronomy classes, bulk density	100 * 100 m	Not available for public use.
<i>Coarse fragments (> 2mm)</i>	ISRIC data	250m * 250 m	https://data.isric.org/geonetwork/srv/pol/catalog.search#/home
<i>Climate</i>	Historical data of 2013 and three GCMs for RCP 4.5 and 8.5 for 2050. This source was chosen to have harmonized data for climate change scenario modelling. Mean monthly precipitation was calculated as a mean from daily data.	1km * 1 km	https://opendap.4tu.nl/thredds/catalog/data2/uuid/e940ec1a-71a0-449e-bbe3-29217f2ba31d/catalog.html
<i>Relief</i>	Polish DEM and 20 covariates produced in the SAGA GIS software: Aspect, Convergence Index, Elevation, General Curvature, LS-factor, Midslope position, Multiresolution index of the ridge top flatness, Multiresolution index of valley bottom flatness, Normalized height, Plan Curvature, Profile Curvature, Slope, Slope height, Standardized height, Texture, Topographic Position Index, Topographic Ruggedness Index, Valley Depth	100 * 100 m	https://www.geoportal.gov.pl/pl/dane/numeryczny-model-terenu-nmt/
<i>Vegetation</i>	NDVI – 3 years monthly mean, plus yearly min and max value. Copernicus Data: Soil Surface Moisture Index, 3-year monthly mean for NDVI (March-October), 3-year mean, minimum, and maximum (March-October): Leaf Area Index, Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation, Fraction of green vegetation cover, Gross Dry Matter Productivity, Dry Matter Productivity	100 * 100 m (NDVI) 250m * 250 m (Copernicus data)	Google Earth Engine Sentinel-2 data (2018-2020); https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/vegetation

Methods

Data preparation

All covariates listed in the table were harmonized to soil covariates. We changed the coordinate system to crs=2180, cropped and masked all rasters to the extent of the soil texture map.

For the mapping of SOC stocks we used two databases at the national scale from 2018.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 862695

Application cookbook

We used caret package that was suggested in the FAO Soil Organic Carbon Mapping Cookbook 2nd Edition. To map SOC content we used QRF (Quantile Regression Forests) algorithm. We also used all covariates that were available at the national scale.

To calculate the possible SOC losses we prepared maps of SOC content and SOC stocks for 2050 in two climate change scenarios (RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5). Using the maps for 2050 and 2018 we calculated relative changes between them to forecast the SOC loss.

Comparison results

The newly applied method differs significantly from earlier SOC maps at national scale in many points of the analysis. Despite the use of the same soil monitoring data, we included more explanatory covariates and used a different approach for mapping. We calculated two different models, separately for organic and mineral soils, while the previous maps assessed all soils in one model. We used DSM method and Quantile Regression Forests algorithms, while in the previous maps, values from point locations were interpolated by assigning weighted average values of the interpolated parameter to each polygon on a soil-agricultural map at a scale of 1:100 000. The last important difference between these two approaches was that the previous maps presented soil organic matter content, while for our maps we choose soil organic carbon content. To prepare a spatial distribution of these values comparable, we use the SOM maps ranges divided by 1.72.

Results

Application cookbook

Figure 4.8.1. Density scatter-plots of predicted and observed values for the current SOC content map

Figure 4.8.2. Results of SOC cookbook application, Poland

According to the presented maps (Figure 4.8.2), there are no or only slight losses of SOC. However, it needs to be highlighted, that the performed analysis included only climate changes scenarios, hence the calculated SOC losses is a forecast that might be biased. According to long-term soil monitoring, and studies on the properties of organic soils (Zimnoch et al. 2024), the SOC content decreases in organic soils due to the mineralization processes caused by soil drainage and the transformation of Fibric/Hemic/Sapric Histosols to Murshic Histosols. However, in mineral soils the SOC content does not change significantly, hence the changes for 2050 are in the range from -10 to 10% both for RCP 4.5 and 8.5. This might be caused by the decades of agricultural use of these soils, where the SOC achieved the stable form.

Comparison

Figure 4.8.3. Comparison of SOC results, Poland

To make map comparison possible, we used the SOC ranges as close as possible to the maps presented in the Deliverable 3.1.1 of SERENA EJP-Project. For this reason, we created SOC ranges that corresponds to previously made SOM map ranges (for example 1% of SOM = 1% / 1.72 ≈ 0.58%). The biggest differences occur in the distribution of the lowest ranges of SOC (<0.58, 0.58-0.87) and SOM (0.2-1.0, 1.0-1.5). On the map produced using the SERENA cookbook (Figure 4.8.3 – right), we can see that the lowest range is not visible on the map, while the range 0.58-0.87 has significantly lower extend, mostly in two regions in central Poland. The applied approach (DSM using QRF algorithm) seems to deal better with the extreme values in the database. This means that in the SERENA map, the ranges of the lowest and the highest value will be less frequent. This is visible especially for the lowest range of values. On the SERENA map the range of SOM < 1% and SOC < 0.58% occurs locally, while, on the previous map (Figure 4.8.3 - left) we can see the visible spots of these values (central Poland). This observation can be applied for two analyzed years of SOC/SOM monitoring in Poland.

Recommendations

To assess covariate importance, we would recommend to use two packages that allow to make a decision which of the set of covariates is the most important for the modelling. Some of the most commonly used R packages are *Boruta* and *rfe*. For SOC mapping in Poland we used the *Boruta* package. The method that can be considered for mapping soil texture and SOC as well (we achieved similar results for Poland) is Geographically weighted regression (GWR) that allows to avoid local multicollinearity. This algorithm can be applied in ArcGIS, QGIS, and R. We used this method to map soil texture: clay, sand, silt content.

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4.9 Portugal

Gabriele Buttafuoco (CNR, IT) and Nádia Castanheira (INIAV, PT)

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
SOC database	Soil organic carbon data (0-0.30 m)	4727 locations (Figure 4.9.1)	LUCAS 2018 TOPSOIL data - ESDAC - European Commission (europa.eu)

Figure 4.9.1. Soil sample locations (LUCAS 2018)

Methods

Data preparation

The distribution of SOC data was highly skewed and before the application of the approach, SOC data were transformed into a Gaussian distribution using a Gaussian anamorphosis (Wackernagel, 2003) and back transformed into raw data after the spatial interpolation.

Application cookbook

A map of SOC concentrations for Portugal was produced using a geostatistical approach. Particularly, ordinary kriging (Chilès & Delfiner, 2012) was used to map SOC concentration (%) at national scale in Portugal.

Comparison results

No comparison was possible because there was no previous SOC map.

Results

Application cookbook

Figure 4.9.2 shows the map of SOC obtained by using ordinary kriging, whereas Figure 4.9.3 shows the map of the standard deviation of errors obtained by the application of ordinary kriging for predicting SOC at unsampled locations.

Figure 4.9.2. Map of SOC (g kg^{-1}) obtained by using ordinary kriging.

Figure 4.9.3. Kriging standard deviation of SOC (g kg^{-1})

Recommendations

The availability of data is crucial, and the LUCAS database in its various editions appears to be a key contribution at least to having a general overview of the organic carbon content in soils. Unfortunately, at national scale no maps of covariates that could help in improving the estimation of SOC concentration at unsampled locations were available.

The availability of SOC databases of adequate quality and sample size should also be urgently addressed at national level.

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4.10 Summary and Synthesis

Table 4.10.1 Differences between cookbook application and earlier results from member states.

Difference	Member States
Small difference	France
Values different	Hungary, Poland
Patterns different	
Values and patterns different	Ireland (comparison only just qualitative and not much reliable because of difference in methods and data), Italy, Lithuania,

Table 4.10.2. Differences in application between earlier assessment and cookbook, for those MS for which a difference in results was observed

Member State	Difference type (V, P, V&P)*	Assessment	Soil data	Auxiliary data	Methods	Spatial resolution (m)
Belgium (Flanders)	n.a.	Cookbook	Flanners database (0-20 cm)	Flanders datasets	Random Forest within the DSM Workflow	100
Estonia	n.a.	Cookbook	National database	National database land use; ERA5 climate data; Merit DEM Topography; Parent material ESDAC	Random Forest within the DSM Workflow	100
France	V	Earlier (Mulder et al. 2016) At different depths	French Soil Monitoring Network (RMQS) and French Soil Inventory programmes (IGCS)	Different sources	Cubist	90
		Cookbook	National database (0-20 cm)	National covariates (https://doi.org/10.1016/j	Random Forest or cubist within the DSM Workflow	90

				geoderma.20 19.02.036)		
Hungary	V	Earlier	DOSoReMI.hu database (Pásztor et al. 2020)	DOSoReMI.hu database (Pásztor et al. 2020)	Random Forest combined with Kriging (RFK)	100
		Cookbook	National database (0-30 cm)	National database (soil, climate, parent mat., ecc.), Corine Land cover and EU DEM derivatives	Random Forest combined with Kriging (RFK)	100
Ireland	V&P	Earlier (only mineral soils were considered and no real comparison would be possible)	Indicative Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) Stock Map of Agricultural Soils (0-50cm) by Creamer et al. (2016)			
		Cookbook	LUCAS 2018 TOPSOIL data ESDAC (0-30 cm)	None	Ordinary Kriging	50
Italy (Tuscany)	V&P	Earlier	Tuscany Region database (Gardin et al., 2021) (0-30 cm)	A few regional terrain and climatic predictors	FAO Cookbook 2018 (Random Forest)	50
		Cookbook	Tuscany Region database (Gardin et al., 2021) (0-30 cm)	None	Ordinary Kriging with local parameters	50
Lithuania	V&P	Earlier	XLS Data Base (Armolaitis K. 2016.) and SOC data STEROPES project (0-10 cm)		Based on the contours of the Lithuanian soil GIS database (Dirv_DR10LT- 1554, 2022, scale 1:10,000)	10

		Cookbook	SOC data STEROPES project (0-10 cm)	None	Ordinary Kriging	50
Poland	V	Earlier	National database 1997	No information	No information	100 (?)
		Cookbook	National database 2018	Land use and vegetation (www.copernicus.eu), texture, BD, and relief (national database), climatic attributes (opendap.4tu.nl)	FAO Cookbook 2018 (Quantile Regression Forest)	100 (?)
Portugal	n.a.	Cookbook	LUCAS 2018 TOPSOIL data ESDAC (0-30 cm)	None	Ordinary Kriging	50

*n.a. = not available, S = similar, V = values are different, P = patterns are different

Some general issues have been identified based on application of the SOC cookbook:

1. Often the national database consists of data from multiple years and/or methods of analysis and quality of data (e.g. done by several laboratories). This means there are other factors than spatial ones that can cause differences in the resulting map.
2. Even highly spatial autocorrelated soil properties like SOC are poorly structured or lacking in spatial structure (pure nugget effect).
3. In these cases, the availability of soil data is crucial, and the LUCAS database in its various editions appears to be a key contribution at least to having a general overview of the organic carbon content in soils.
4. Unfortunately, in the applications, at national scale using LUCAS database, no covariate in geostatistical approaches proved useful in improving the estimation of SOC concentration at unsampled locations.
5. Applying the DSM flowchart developed in EJP SOIL WP6 requires specific training sessions to make it easier to use.
6. Uncertainty is an important issue. Uncertainty in input data values will result in uncertainty in the final map too. Though this is well-known, the resulting uncertainties are not often quantified.

5 GHG and climate regulation

Based on the previous evaluation of SERENA T2.3 (Montagne et al 2023), the Net Ecosystem Productivity (NEP) has been proposed as the pragmatic indicator of GHG assessment. NEP is defined as the difference between the gross primary productivity (GPP) and the total ecosystem respiration (in the gas flux measurements framework this is also called net ecosystem exchange, NEE). The overall NEP calculation considers GPP (gross primary productivity), and . ecosystem respiration (Reco) as follows:

$$\text{NEP} = \text{GPP} - \text{RECO}$$

The cookbook for GHG and climate control provides a detailed description of how GPP and RECO were modelled using observed GPP/RECO from Fluxnet and environmental covariates to estimate NEP (NEPpred). (D2.3.2I). NEPpred is specific for wheat fields as it is the crop where Fluxnet data is available from. The following sections present the results of cookbook applications for GHG and climate control that have been done within the framework of SERENA.

5.1 Czech Republic

Jessica Reyes Rojas

Data used:

Category	description	Availability data
Czech Republic national boundary	administrative boundaries for Czech Republic:	https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/eea-reference-grids-2/gis-files/czech-republic-shapefile

Methods

Data preparation

The cookbook's methodology and scripts were applied

Application cookbook

As stated in the cookbook, using the R script.

Comparison results

There is a lack of applications in the literature for this indicator in the Czech Republic.

Results

Application cookbook

In this report, I present the spatialization of the net ecosystem productivity representative of winter season, calculated for a period within an 8-day span, with a focus on the wheat crop (Figure 5.1.1).

Winter wheat is the crop with the largest total cropped area in the Czech Republic (*Matějka, 2021*). Therefore, this indicator is appropriate for commonly grown crop in the Czech Republic, as wheat occupies more than a quarter (28.9%) of our study area. The analysis focused on the Moravia region, located in the southeast of the Czech Republic. This region is known for its long history of agricultural production.

I applied the indicator in two steps. First, I applied it for the whole Czech Republic considering forest and agriculture land (Figure 5.1.1a). In a second step I selected the Moravia region and used the EURO-CROP 2018 raster to select the agricultural plots that correspond to wheat crop.

Overall, The forest areas such as national parks and protected landscape area presented high NEP (Figure 5.1.2 a,b). NEP negative values closest to zero suggest that these forests are functioning as low net carbon sources. This implies that the forests are releasing a low amount of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere.

The wheat cropland plots in the Moravia region during the winter season are dominated by areas with negative NEP values that are not close to zero, indicating that these areas are releasing a substantial amount of carbon dioxide, nearly offsetting the carbon uptake through crop photosynthesis (Figure 5.1.1b).

The NEP model for wheat crop successfully captured the indicator in the croplands of the Czech Republic. Figure 5.1.1c clearly depicts the cropland plots where the indicator was predicted. Despite the successful spatialization of the indicator, a salt-and-pepper effect is still visible in the neighbouring plots.

Figure 5.1.1. The final NEP indicator for the Czech Republic on a. Winter (January); b. Spring (April); c. Summer (June); d. Autumn (October). Each representative indicator is for the first 8-d of the month in 2014.

Figure 5.1.2. a. Forest national parks and protected landscape areas. b. NEP in forest national parks and protected landscape areas.

Comparison

There is a lack of studies mapping net ecosystem productivity for the Czech Republic that makes difficult the comparison.

Recommendations

This indicator was chosen to represent each season because the yearly indicator showed high bias. Analyzing by representative climatic seasons yields better results. I recommend this approach because presenting the indicator annually ignores crucial information on the variability associated with the crop calendar, which, as indicated in the results, influences the indicator significantly from one season to another.

References

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5.2 Estonia

Liia Kukk, Alar Astover

Region (if not national scale): Peipsiääre municipality

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
GPP	2014 MODIS gross primary productivity (GPP)	500 m	MOD17A2HGF available at MODISTools in R
Soil	2014 daily soil moisture	1000 m	Available from Zhang et al. 2023
Climate	2014 maximum monthly temperature	2.5'	Available at World Climate datasets

Climate	2014 minimum monthly temperature	2.5'	Available at World Climate datasets
Cropland	2018 cropland, filtered for wheat	10 m	Sentinel-1 and LUCAS observations
Regional boundaries	The boundaries of the municipality	Vector	Vector data is available at Republic of Estonia Land Board's Geoportaal

Methods

Data preparation

Data used for NEP analysis was not prepared separately.

Application cookbook

NEP analysis was performed according to the GHG Cookbook.

Comparison results

NEP as an indicator for GHG analysis has not been previously estimated in this region and therefore cannot be compared to earlier results.

Results

Application cookbook

An example of the 8-day NEP analysis in winter wheat fields in Peipsiääre municipality (Figure 5.2.1) was carried out at the beginning of the vegetation period using soil moisture data from April 24, 2014, to May 1, 2014, and the average temperature of April 2014. During this period, NEP values ranged from -8 to 25.3 gC m⁻², with a weighted average of 8.68 gC m⁻² per 8 days in Peipsiääre municipality (Figure 5.2. 2).

Figure 5.2.1. Peipsiääre municipality in Estonia.

Figure 5.2.2. The 8-day NEP in wheat fields in Peipsiääre municipality.

During the active growing period from April to August, the highest NEP values are observed in May, corresponding with the peak of the summer growing season (Figure 5.2.3). The area-weighted average NEP values in Peipsiääre municipality are as follows: 35 gC m⁻² in April, 208 gC m⁻² in May, 148 gC m⁻² in June, 205 gC m⁻² in July, and 29 gC m⁻² in August.

Figure 5.2.3. Histogram of NEP values in April, May, June, July and August.

Figure 5.2.4. NEP in wheat fields of Peipsiääre municipality during May.

During May (from May 2 to June 2, covering four 8-day intervals in the current GHG Cookbook application), NEP ranged from 56.35 to 355.5 gC m⁻² (Figure 5.2.4), with a total range of 299.15 gC m⁻². Approximately one-third of the wheat-growing fields had NEP values clustered between 190 and 210 gC m⁻².

Discussion

The GHG Cookbook application indicated that carbon uptake was initially low at the start of the growing season, which is a typical pattern observed in early spring. NEP values increased significantly in May, aligning with the peak activity period of wheat fields. This increase is consistent with the known dynamics of plant growth and carbon uptake during the summer months. May and July were identified as the most productive months for carbon assimilation. However, NEP values in June were lower compared to May and July, suggesting that further analysis is needed to understand this mid-season fluctuation. By August, NEP values had declined, indicating a reduction in ecosystem productivity, a trend commonly observed as the growing season progresses towards its latter stages.

Conclusion

The current application of the GHG Cookbook across Europe offers a useful framework for evaluating general GHG dynamics. However, for more accurate future assessments, it is crucial to incorporate detailed site-specific factors, including management practices, local environmental conditions, and soil properties. Validation of data to account for Estonia's pedoclimatic conditions will further enhance precision of GHG assessment. Despite these needs for refinement, the GHG Cookbook and its methodology represent a significant advancement in GHG calculations, effectively utilizing MODIS data.

Recommendations

We have the following recommendations:

- 1) Additional NEP analysis could be conducted taking into account more comprehensive details regarding the growing season, management practices, and site-specific conditions.

- 2) More detailed RECO modeling based on site-specific covariates could provide deeper insights into the relationships between NEP and GHG dynamics.

5.3 Ireland

Alan Fahy, Giulia Bondi, Lilian O’Sullivan

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
GPP	2014 MODIS GPP	500 m	MOD17A2HGF available through MODISTools in R Studio
Soil	2014 daily soil moisture	1000 m	Available from Zhang et al. 2023
Climate	2014 maximum monthly temperature	2.5'	Available at World Climate datasets
Climate	2014 minimum monthly temperature	2.5'	Available at World Climate datasets
Cropland	2018 cropland, filtered for wheat	10 m	Sentinel-1 and LUCAS observations
Regional boundaries	Ireland and Co. Meath vector shapefile		https://data-osi.opendata.arcgis.com/search?tags=boundaries

Methods

Data preparation

Data for NEP analysis was provided through the Microsoft Teams shared folder. However, MODIS data was obtained using the MODISTools R package in RStudio (R 4.3.1). Nine MODIS tiles to cover the extent of Ireland were merged and exported to QGIS for analysis.

Application cookbook

The NEP application was performed exactly as outlined in the GHG cookbook.

Comparison results

NEP as an indicator of GHG analysis has not been previously studied here and therefore cannot be compared to alternative results.

Results

Application cookbook

An 8-day NEP analysis was conducted for the entirety of the Republic of Ireland under wheat crop from 02-09 of January. However, wheat production in Ireland is largely centred around several key regions in the east/central-east due to the relative dominance of grassland and alternative agricultural regimes elsewhere. This resulted in quite a sparse visualisation at national scale. As such, we subsequently

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 862695

performed a refined analysis for the same period in County Meath, a region which consistently has the largest area under wheat crop in Ireland (Central Statistics Office, 2020). The study areas are depicted in Figure 5.3.1.

Figure 5.3.1: Study area of the Republic of Ireland, with County Meath depicted in red

The NEP calculation was performed for the period 02 to 09 of January. Further NEP calculations for 8-day periods in April, July, and October (as representations for each of the four seasons) were due to be performed, although errors were encountered and there was insufficient time to diagnose the problem. Despite this, the results for the 8-day analysis for January are presented below.

National

NEP over the analysis period ranged between -13.34 and -6.34 g C m^{-2} , with the majority of values falling within -10.41 to -11.38 g C m^{-2} . The distribution of NEP values is portrayed in Figure 5.3.2. A noticeably lower frequency of values were experienced from -8.5 g C m^{-2} to the tail end of -6.34 g C m^{-2} (Figure 5.3.3). Large areas of missing data along the west coast and several areas within the mainland can be associated to areas where the production of wheat is not suitable (peatlands etc.), or where other agricultural practices dominate (e.g. extensive grasslands).

Figure 5.3.2: Modelled NEP in Ireland from January 02 to 09. Values correspond to areas classified as wheat in the Eurocrop Map 2018 product

Figure 5.3.3: Histogram of the January 8-day NEP of wheat fields in the Republic of Ireland

Regional

Figure 5.3.4: Modelled NEP in County Meath from January 02 to 09. Values correspond to areas classified as wheat in the Eurocrop Map 2018 product

Figure 5.3.5: Histogram of the January 8-day NEP of wheat fields in County Meath

NEP values for Meath had a narrower range compared to the national level, ranging from -11.41 to -7.21 g C m^{-2} . This narrower range is to be expected given the smaller spatial extent and modest environmental conditions here. The majority of NEP values for County Meath are clustered around the most common national range of approximately -11 g C m^{-2} . However, there is a notable steep decline

in frequency for values lower than $-11.25 \text{ g C m}^{-2}$. Conversely, there is a gradual and proportional decrease in the number of NEP values as they increase from -11 g C m^{-2} towards -7 g C m^{-2} on the histogram (Figure 5.3.5).

Discussion:

The negative NEP values seem to align with the plant-environment dynamics for January in Ireland, characterized by low plant photosynthesis and high respiration rates. It must be noted that this is a single 8-day period analysis, while the indicator has a large temporal and seasonal variability.

Recommendations / remarks:

Due to the resolution of the soil moisture data for Ireland failed to cover areas directly along the perimeter of the coastline. In some instances, soil moisture data was only available several kilometers inland. This highlights the benefit of using high resolution data where possible, or interpolation / gap filling techniques going forward.

References

Central Statistics Office 2020. Census of Agriculture 2020 - Preliminary Results. Land utilization Summary. Available at: <https://www.cso.ie/en/releasesandpublications/ep/p-coa/censusofagriculture2020-preliminaryresults/landutilisation/>

5.4 Italy

Medina-Roldán, Eduardo, Lorenzetti, Romina, Ungaro, Fabrizio

Region (if not national scale): Emilia-Romagna lowland plains (see map from wiki-commons below, Figure 5.4.1)

Figure 5.4.1. Emilia-Romagna Region

Data used

Apart from the data input specified in the cookbook.

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
Emilia-Romagna Region political boundary	Borders of the Emilia-Romagna Region, this layer was then cropped for the plain area only with a vector of soil properties, and re-projected to various reference/coordinated systems	NA	Can be downloaded at: https://geoportale.regione.emilia-romagna.it/download/dati-e-prodotti-cartografici-preconfezionati/tutti-download-preconfezionati/limite_pianura_collina-montagna_wgs84.zip/@@download/file/Limite_pianura_collina%20montagna_WGS84.zip

Methods

Data preparation

As stated in the cookbook.

Application cookbook

As stated in the cookbook, using the R script and then QGIS (from step 12). Then, NEP data for 5 years (2010-2014) were averaged (per location, Figure 5.4.2) in order to select 3 representative 8-day periods that could capture the seasonal variation in NEP across a year (since the aggregation of individual 8-day periods to calculate an annual indicator produced annual estimates with a large error). It was concluded that annual variability could be summarised by 3 seasons: summer, winter and spring-autumn.

Figure 5.4.2. Empirical density distribution of NEP data for each 8-d period averaged over 2010-2014. The x-axis is NEP ($\text{gCm}^{-2}8\text{d}^{-1}$) and the y-axis is the relative frequency of values in the Emilia-Romagna Region.

The next step involved selecting individual 8-d periods for each of the 3 seasons based on the distribution of NEP values (Figs. 5.4.3-5.4.5)

Figure 5.4.3. Empirical density distribution of NEP data for 8-d periods in summer averaged over 2010-2014. The x-axis is NEP ($\text{gCm}^{-2}8\text{d}^{-1}$) and the y-axis is the relative frequency of values in the Emilia-Romagna Region.

Figure 5.4.4. Empirical density distribution of NEP data for 8-d periods in winter averaged over 2010-2014. The x-axis is NEP (gCm⁻²8d⁻¹) and the y-axis is the relative frequency of values in the Emilia-Romagna Region.

Figure 5.4.5. Empirical density distribution of NEP data for 8-d periods in spring-autumn averaged over 2010-2014. The x-axis is NEP ($\text{gCm}^{-2}\text{8d}^{-1}$) and the y-axis is the relative frequency of values in the Emilia-Romagna Region.

Based on the long-term average for the different seasons, it was decided to select the following dates:

- 1) May the first as the representative summer NEP conditions, when NEP values are at the highest
- 2) December the 3rd as representative of winter NEP conditions, when NEP values are low
- 3) September the 22nd as representative of spring-autumn NEP conditions, when distribution of NEP values is less skewed

Comparison results

A similar indicator is not available for our AOI. Thus, we compared our results with a vegetation-based index (NDVI) that is available.

Results

Application cookbook

The spatial distribution of NEP values for the selected seasons in the region is shown in the figures below (Figs. 5.4.6-5.4.8).

Figure 5.4.6. NEP (gCm⁻²8d¹) spatial distribution for the selected 8-days period in summer (April 24 to May 01) at the Emilia-Romagna Region. Because the indicator is rendered spatial in association only with wheat fields (either common or durum), several “gaps” are present. Other big gap in the Eastern part of the regions appears as a result of a data gap in the soil moisture product.

Figure 5.4.7. NEP ($\text{gCm}^{-2}8\text{d}^{-1}$) spatial distribution for the selected 8-days period in spring/autumn (September 15 to September 22) at the Emilia-Romagna Region. Because the indicator is rendered spatial in association only with wheat fields (either common or durum), several “gaps” are present. Other big gap in the Eastern part of the regions appears as a result of a data gap in the soil moisture product.

Figure 5.4.8. NEP ($\text{gCm}^{-2}\text{8d}^{-1}$) spatial distribution for the selected 8-days period in winter (November 26 to December 03) at the Emilia-Romagna Region. Because the indicator is rendered spatial in association only with wheat fields (either common or durum), several “gaps” are present. Other big gap in the Eastern part of the regions appears as a result of a data gap in the soil moisture product.

NEP negative values for the period in question represent a total C sink, and can be interpreted as a period when MODIS GPP values and mean monthly temperatures are both low (Figure 5.4.9).

Figure 5.4.9. Contour plot of modelled GPP and RECO values. The area under the red curve presents negative NEP values. Conditions when NEP is either negative or positive can be seen (taken from the Modified from the SERENA GHG emissions cookbook). Note that there is an area (gray shade) where the model does not have biophysical sense (this is negative GPP at high temperature and low MODIS GPP values).

The effect of average 8-d volumetric soil moisture is shown on Figure 5.4.10. For a given MODIS 8-d GPP value, higher soil volumetric moisture reduces slightly the value of predicted GPP and as such the value of predicted NEP.

Figure 5.4.10. Contour plot of modelled GPP and RECO values. The area under the red curve presents negative NEP values. Conditions when NEP is either negative or positive can be seen (taken from the cookbook).

Comparison

There is no such indicator from previous exercises reported in the indicated deliverables/milestones for our region of interest. For Italy as a country, the assessment reported is on the loss of carbon sequestration potential as a result of soil sealing (more accurately soil consumption or “consumo di suolo”). A correlation analysis between the NEP indicator for the period reported above, and a 5-years median value of an indicator of ground biomass (derived from NDVI) for the region produced a low correlation value. Note however that there is still need to find a practical way to express the NEP indicator in a way that it is practical (such as the average of the indicator for particular periods with similar conditions such as annual seasons) without introducing large bias/errors.

Recommendations

There are several main aspects to incorporate as a user:

- 1) To incorporate implicitly the wheat growing season calendar in the model
- 2) A part of the region cannot be evaluated as one of the data layers (that of moisture) does not cover it, try to see if a gap-filling approach might be feasible
- 3) Is it extrapolating indicator values to other vegetation types (such as grasslands, other crops, etc.) advisable or a specific empirically-derived indicator would be necessary to other crops?
- 4) To determine the long-term relation between the variation of the NEP indicator and soil C stock changes

5) The annual indicator based on the sum of each 8-d period produces a NEP value too different to the annual NEP observed in the different Fluxnet stations used for the training dataset. This is because the relatively small variations of modelled NEP for each 8-d period accumulate when summed up and the annual value differs substantially. As such there needs to be a way to try to express the indicator in a way that it reflects its intra-annual variation, yet does not have the problem of error accumulation. This was done with the present approach showing representative seasonal single 8-d period 5 years mean values distribution to express NEP in summer autumn and winter.

5.5 Netherlands

Martine Trip, Joost Crujisen

Data used

Data	Description	Variable	Units	Spatial resolution	Dates	CRS	File format	Comments	How to get it?
MODIS MOD17A2HGF Collection	8-day composite GPP product derived from the MODIS algorithm (a light absorption efficiency family)	GPP	kgC/m ² /8day	500 m	2001-2014	Sinusoidal	Raster	The version 6 of the collection was decommissioned from the LP DAAC Centre, yet it is the one used on this cookbook as the new version 6.1 dates are not in the temporal range of the Fluxnet data	From R MODIRTools package ¹
Daily soil moisture data derived from Zhang et al. 2023	Daily volumetric soil moisture	Wv	g ³ of moisture per g ³ soil	1000 m	2014	Sinusoidal, but it has its own definition	Raster	The dataset has some important gaps in high latitude areas. As a result, gap filling needs to be carried out with long-term year average	From Teams sharepoint ²
Daily soil moisture data CRS information	CRS of the moisture dataset in which other variables need to be projected	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	text	Wkt file	From Teams sharepoint ²
World Climate tmax	Maximum monthly temperature	WClim tmax	°C	2.5' (around 4600 m at the low EU latitudes)	2014	WGS84	Raster	A daily database could be eventually be used	From Teams sharepoint ³
World Climate tmin	Minimum monthly temperature	WClim tmin	°C	2.5' (around 4600 m at the low EU latitudes)	2014	WGS84	Raster	A daily database could be eventually be used	From Teams sharepoint ⁴
EU 2018 croplands	Derived from Sentinel-1 and LUCAS 2018 observations, filtered here for wheat	EU18	Crop classes (unitless)	10 m	2018	WTRS89-Extended / LAEA Europe	Raster	The data layer is either distributed as a heavy raster file (7 Gb), or as 1600 raster tiles. Because of this, 23x23 tiles were created, and converted to vector format to be used in the final mask for rendering the final indicator spatial distribution	From Teams sharepoint ⁵
Political regional boundaries	Region to be analysed	Area of interest	unitless	Variable and particular for each MS	Variable	Variable	Vector	It is suggested to reproject the AOI to match with soil moisture layer	To be acquired by each MS

The necessary data as mentioned in the cookbook was used for the cookbook application. The data was obtained in the way mentioned in the cookbook. Political boundaries (vector) of the Netherlands were obtained from the PDOK plug-in in QGIS.

Methods

Data preparation

The pre-processing of the data was done as proposed in the cookbook.

Application cookbook

The steps as described in the cookbook were executed. However, in step 12 another strategy had to be picked as the processing capacity of the computer that was used was insufficient. Therefore, the transformation of the EU-2018-crop tiles into a logical raster (in the raster calculator) was done in R instead, by the following lines of code:

```
setwd("C:/Users/.../Cookbook_GHG/input")
r <- raster("wheat18_1109.tif")
r[r[] != 1] = NA
writeRaster(r, 'wheat_log_1109.tif')

r <- raster("wheat18_1209.tif")
r[r[] != 1] = NA
writeRaster(r, 'wheat_log_1209.tif')

r <- raster("wheat18_1208.tif")
r[r[] != 1] = NA
writeRaster(r, 'wheat_log_1208.tif')

r <- raster("wheat18_1309.tif")
r[r[] != 1] = NA
writeRaster(r, 'wheat_log_1309.tif')

r <- raster("wheat18_1308.tif")
r[r[] != 1] = NA
writeRaster(r, 'wheat_log_1308.tif')
```

This results in a map of NEP (Net Ecosystem Productivity) at 500 m resolution, for wheat fields only.

Comparison results

No earlier results are known so far.

Results

Application cookbook

The cookbook was applied to almost all parts of the Netherlands for the period 2014-01-02 until 2014-12-27. Due to gaps in underlying data (mainly soil moisture data), some parts are not completely covered, such as the north of Groningen and Friesland, the North West part of Flevoland and parts of Zeeland. Furthermore, the map shows distributed pixels as results are only shown for pixels that had wheat in 2014.

The complete map of the NEP values in the Netherlands during the period from 18th of June to the 26th of June in 2014 can be found in Figure 5.5.1. A zoomed-in map of the North Eastern part of the Netherlands can be found in Figure 5.5.2.

*Figure 5.5.1 Map of the NEP values ($g\ C\ m^{-2} * 8\ days$) calculated for the Netherlands in the period 2014-06-18 to 2014-06-26, for areas with wheat.*

*Figure 5.5.2. Zoomed-in map of the NEP values ($\text{g C m}^{-2} * 8 \text{ days}$) calculated for the North Eastern part of the Netherlands in the period 2014-06-18 to 2014-06-26, for areas with wheat.*

Remarks

The used EU-crop-layer tiles represent wheat grown in the Netherlands in one year. However, due to crop rotations with many different crops in the Netherlands (often 3 to 8 crops rotate on one field), the area of wheat grown in one year is relatively small. Therefore, a lot of fields show no NEP value at all.

Many negative values are present in the map. Although only one 8-day period is shown in Figures 5.5.1 and 5.5.2, it can be seen in the raster histogram that these negative values are quite common (Figure 5.5.3). Negative NEP values represent a total C source, meaning that respiration is larger than production. This can occur in periods when MODIS GPP values and mean monthly temperatures are both low.

Figure 5.5.3 Raster histogram of the frequency of occurrence of each NEP value for the different bands (each band is an 8-day period).

5.6 Poland

Sylwia Pindral

Data used

Apart from the data input specified in the cookbook.

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
area of the interest – raster	The raster was prepared based on the vector soil-agricultural map and	100m*100m	Can be downloaded at:

of AOI chosen for the SERENA projects	Corine Land Cover (CLC) 2018. We converted vector layer into simple raster with the value 1. To update this map, we have chosen agricultural use from CLC and reclassified raster into 1- agricultural area, and NA – the rest of land use classes. Finally, we mosaic these two rasters.	https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/corine-land-cover/clc2018 soil-agricultural map – private resources of IUNG-PIB
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Methods

Data preparation

All the steps were done following the cookbook.

Application cookbook

Most of the steps were done in RStudio (R 4.3.1). In QGIS we prepared a polygon of tiles to download MODIS data using MODISTools R package. For this reason, we needed 19 tiles of 100km*100km extend.

Comparison results

So far, there is no map of NEP for Poland, hence the comparison with the other approaches is unavailable.

Below, we present monthly means and sum of NEP from the 8-daily data.

Results

Application cookbook

Figure 5.6.1. Modelled net ecosystem productivity in agricultural land in Poland and the histogram of the indicator values.

We can see that in the northern Part of Poland, the area by the sea, a disturbance in continuity of values occurs. This is caused by the gap in soil moisture products. Taking into account the distribution of the sum of values for 2014, we can observe that the distribution is close to normal, slightly right-skewed. The descriptive statistics are presented in the table below.

Table 5.6.1. Pearson correlation coefficient between NEP and soil and environmental variables (for 2018)

	Mean	Standard deviation	Median	0.25 quantile	0.75 quantile	Kurtosis	Skewness	CV
2014 NEP	-770.68	65.99	-774.56	-816.56	-724.73	-0.45	0.15	-8.56

Monthly means

January 2014

February 2014

March 2014

April 2014

May 2014

June 2014

July 2014

August 2014

September 2014

October 2014

November 2014

December 2014

Figure 5.6.2. Monthly mean values of NEP.

Histograms for monthly means

January 2014

February 2014

March 2014

April 2014

May 2014

June 2014

July 2014

August 2014

September 2014

October 2014

November 2014

December 2014

Figure 5.6.3. Histograms of NEP values for the monthly means for 2014. Different colors of histograms indicate seasons.

As can be seen in Figure 5.6.3, the data distribution for March, June, September, and December is right skewed, while the other months have a distribution approaching normal. We cannot unambiguously indicate the difference between seasons and months, not with the histograms and maps presented in Figure 5.6.2. This may suggest that further discussion on application of the method is needed. For a further step, it is needed to calculate the correlation between mean NEP, and mean NPP, GPP, SOC stocks.

Comparison

To make a comparison, due to the lack of the previous studies on mapping GHG in Poland, we calculated the Pearson correlation of coefficient between calculated NEP and independent soil properties. The results are shown below.

Table 5.6.2. Pearson correlation coefficient between NEP and soil and environmental variables (for 2018)

	mean NDVI	SOC content	TWI	mean LAI	mean NPP	sand content	pH – H2O	bulk density
NEP	0.0321	0.1705	0.0211	0.0101	-0.1060	0.1247	-0.1351	-0.1405

As can be seen in table 5.6.2, the correlation between NEP and other selected parameters is low or very low and does not exceed 0.2. However, this should be repeated by comparing covariates from 2014 (especially LAI, NDVI, NPP). All the others are relatively stable and do not change significantly throughout 10 years.

Recommendations

There are several main aspects to incorporate as an user:

- 1) No technical issues detected. I can strongly recommend to harmonize all rasters to the one that covers the area of interest (AOI). In the case of Poland we used tmax and tmin, that were already prepared for the purposes of modelling CC scenarios. We reprojected, resampled, cropped and masked all the other rasters to tmax and tmin to cover AOI (agricultural area in Poland).

- 2) To model areas larger than 100km*100km (the maximum area to process MODIS data at once), we suggest to prepare a grid of the extend 90km * 90 km, calculate the longitude and latitude of the centroid of each tile, and download 100km *100km MODIS tiles. Then all downloaded tiled can be mosaic together and cropped to the AOI.

5.7 Spain

Emilio Doñate, Sabina Asins

Region (if not national scale): Villena, Alicante

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
Boundaries (vector)	Boundaries of the Spanish municipalities	1:25000	https://www.idee.es/csw-inspire-idee/srv/spa/catalog.search#/metadata/spainLLM

Methods

Data preparation

In the data preparation phase, a layer with the corners of the municipal boundary extension has been created (Figure 5.7.1). To do this, a layer with the square that forms the extent of the municipality (in green) was first created using a QGIS tool. Subsequently, the corner points and centroid of this square were extracted, all using QGIS tools. These steps were essential to establish an accurate geographic base and facilitate subsequent spatial analysis in the project.

Figure 5.7.1.- In red, boundaries of Villena (Alicante). In green, square that forms the extent of the municipality.

Application cookbook

The municipality of Villena has been chosen because it has the largest amount of wheat crops in the Valencian Community (Figure 5.7.2). In addition, its extension of 345 km² makes it large enough to

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 862695

occupy a complete tile. All the steps indicated in the Soil GHG Cookbook have been followed. However, some modifications were made due to difficulties encountered in step 10, where certain points had to be omitted because negative values were not obtained (Figures 5.7.3 and 5.7.4). These adaptations were necessary to continue the process and ensure accurate results consistent with the objectives of the study.

Figure 5.7.2.- Wheat crops and other crops in the municipality of Villena, year 2014. Source: <https://centrodedescargas.cnig.es/CentroDescargas/catalogo.do?Serie=SIOSE>

Figure 5.7.3.- Raster obtained from Gross Primary Productivity, 02 to 09 January, 2014. Source: Included in the GHG Cookbook (SERENA).

Figure 5.7.4.- Raster obtained from Gross Primary Productivity, 02 to 09 January, 2014 as obtained in Figure 5.7.3 but including soil sealed areas (the urban area of Villena corresponds with the white pixel in Figure 5.7.3).

Comparison results

It is important to note that a direct comparison could not be made since no GHG map was presented in the D3.1.1 report.

Results

Application cookbook

Here is the result of the analysis in the municipality of Villena for the week of 2-9 January, 2014. Along with this result, the location of the municipality within the map of Spain has been included to provide

a clear geographical context (Figure 5.7.5). This selection and presentation allow a detailed NEP in a significant agricultural area.

Figure 5.7.5- Net Ecosystem Productivity in wheat areas (Villena, Alicante).

Comparison

A direct comparison with other results cannot be made as no GHG map was presented in the report D3.1.1.

5.8 Summary and Synthesis

Table 5.8.1. Differences in application between earlier assessment and cookbook. For those MS for which no earlier data were available a summary of the cookbook application is provided.

Member State	Difference type (V, P, V&P)	Assessment	Soil data	Auxiliary data	Methods	Spatial resolution (m)
Czech Republic	n.a.	Cookbook	Global moisture product	Global monthly soil temperature, Global MODIS MOD17A2HG F	Spatial ecological production function	Not reported, but the cookbook final resolution is at 500 m resolution
Estonia		Earlier	Not reported in cookbook report			

		Cookbook	Global moisture product	Global monthly soil temperature, Global MODIS MOD17A2HG F	Spatial ecological production function	Not reported, but the cookbook final resolution is at 500 m resolution
Ireland		Earlier	Not reported in cookbook report			
		Cookbook	Global moisture product	Global monthly soil temperature, Global MODIS MOD17A2HG F	spatial ecological production function	Not reported, but the cookbook final resolution is at 500 m resolution
Italy (Emilia-Romagna)		Earlier	Not reported in cookbook report			
		Cookbook	Global moisture product	Global monthly soil temperature, Global MODIS MOD17A2HG F	spatial ecological production function	Not reported, but the cookbook final resolution is at 500 m resolution
The Netherlands	n.a.	Cookbook	Global moisture product	Global monthly soil temperature, Global MODIS MOD17A2HG F	Spatial ecological production function	Not reported, but the cookbook final resolution is at 500 m resolution
Poland		Earlier	Not reported in cookbook report			
		Cookbook with modifications	Global moisture product	Global monthly soil temperature, Global MODIS MOD17A2HG F	Spatial ecological production function (sensu)	Not reported, but the cookbook final resolution is at 500 m resolution*
Spain		Earlier	Not reported in cookbook report			
		Cookbook	Global moisture product	Global monthly soil temperature, Global MODIS MOD17A2HG F	Spatial ecological production function	Not reported, but the cookbook final resolution is at 500 m resolution

*Technically whereas the final NEP product produced through raster algebra is at a 500 m resolution, the final spatial realisation of the indicator with the eurocrop layer is at 10m.

Shortcomings/Recommendations:

- To harmonize all rasters to the one that covers the area of interest (AOI).
- Due to data availability, all MS who evaluated NEP used 2014 MODIS data. However, it turned out that 2014 was not an average year but had very low values in MODIS. As a result, the resulting NEP was negative in all applications.
- For areas larger than 100km*100km, to prepare a grid of the extend 90km * 90 km, calculate the longitude and latitude of the centroid of each tile, and download 100km *100km MODIS tiles. Then all downloaded tiles. can be mosaic together and cropped to the AOI.
- The used EU-crop-layer tiles represent wheat. Due to crop rotations (often 3 to 8 crops rotate on one field in Netherlands), the area of the indicator is relatively small in any particular year. This can either be accepted as reflecting the actual situation in that year, or the method could be applied to all areas where wheat can be grown, resulting in a potential NEP

Potential feasible improvements:

- To incorporate wheat growing season in the model.
- Gap-filling soil moisture layer (or use another product).
- To figure out how to extrapolate the indicator (as a "potential" condition/similar crops).
- To use daily predictors to increase model goodness-of-fit (reducing error aggregation for annual indicator); or find another appropriate temporal rendition (seasonal average).
- To determine the long-term relation between the variation of NEP indicator and soil C.
- To relate the indicator to soil properties.

6 Soil sealing

The selected indicator was degree of soil sealing (D2.3.2). By evaluating this degree at two moments in time, the change in soil sealing can be determined.

The cookbook for soil sealing provides a detailed description of how sealing was calculated (D2.3.2), and provides information on two methods called level 1 and level 2. Level 1 is based on classification of multitemporal satellite images and photointerpretation, while level 2 uses a machine learning model. The following sections present the results of cookbook applications for soil sealing that have been done within the framework of SERENA.

6.1 Austria

Cecilie B. Foldal

Region (if not national scale): Vorarlberg

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
Orthophoto	Geoland basemap orthophoto of 2022	2 x2 m	https://maps.wien.gv.at/basemap/1.0.0/WM/TSCapabilities.xml
Political districts	Austria	Vector	https://www.data.gv.at/katalog/de/dataset/osterreichische-karte-1-500-000-politisch
Imperviousness	Copernicus imperviousness layer for 2018	10 * 10 m	https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/high-resolution-layer-imperviousness/imperviousness-density-2018#download
Grid 2x2 km	Shapefile to support the photointerpretation	Vector	

Methods

Data preparation

We prepared the needed data for the analysis as described in the cookbook. Figure 6.1.1 shows the prepared layers of the province Vorarlberg.

Figure 6.1.1 A) 2x2 km grid of the selected province Vorarlberg. B) with Copernicus Land Monitoring Service High Resolution Layer Imperviousness for 2018.

Application cookbook

We followed the cookbook and could in the photo-interpretation phase easily identify new buildings where there were none before. However, we did not classify the new artificial areas according to the suggested legend, as this would require a more accurate assessment with details from local government. It was not possible to tell from the orthophoto whether a road or square was covered with impervious material or not.

Comparison results

In the SERENA D3.1.1 (Michel and Niedźwiecki, 2022) we describe two different approaches to measuring land use and changes in soil sealing areas applied in Austria. Both differ significantly from the SERENA cookbook approaches. Nevertheless, in this SERENA exercise, we compare the results of applying the soil sealing cookbook with the Austrian Environment Agency's method for the year 2018 for Vorarlberg in western Austria.

Vorarlberg is a mountainous region with few, but highly productive soils and the land is expected to become a more important agricultural region in future scenarios. Vorarlberg has had a steadily growing population for decades, and is close to an attractive labour market, including in neighbouring countries. In 2018, 67,000 ha of land in Vorarlberg was covered by building land and traffic and transport areas. The total land consumption (including areas for recreation etc.) was 40.5% of the permanent settlement area. The permanent settlement area describes all land except steep mountains, rivers and water bodies, and represents only 22.5% of the total area of the federal province Vorarlberg (Umweltbundesamt, 2022)(Table 6.1.1).

Table 6.1.1. Overview of land use in Austria in 2018 (BEV, 2019)

Federal State	Federal Province's area	Population	Permanent settlement area ¹	Permanent settlement area per Federal Province's area	Building land - total ²	Sealed building land ³	Traffic and transport areas ⁴	Sealed Area for transport purposes ⁵	building and traffic/transport ⁶	Sealed building land and traffic and transport areas	Degree of sealing in built-up area ⁷	Recreational areas	Excavation areas	Industrial and commerce areas	Cemeteries	Land consumption ⁸	Land consumption per permanent settlement area	Sealing degree ⁹	Sealed area in [m ²] per inhabitant
Burgenland	3.965	292.160	2.438	61,5%	199	63	155	80	354	144	32%	18	9	28	2	382	15,7%	38,8%	507
Carinthia	9.537	560.852	2.308	24,2%	281	90	209	108	489	199	32%	18	10	55	2	518	22,4%	39,2%	362
Lower Austria	19.179	1.667.630	11.202	58,4%	893	320	629	339	1.522	659	36%	64	53	181	5	1.640	14,6%	41,3%	406
Upper Austria	11.983	1.469.187	6.539	54,6%	618	225	358	201	976	426	36%	38	22	131	2	1.037	15,9%	42,0%	296
Salzburg	7.155	550.976	1.433	20,0%	177	72	104	58	281	130	41%	19	8	51	1	308	21,5%	43,8%	245
Styria	16.399	1.238.067	4.910	29,9%	570	191	357	195	927	386	33%	33	29	108	2	989	20,1%	39,9%	319
Tyrol	12.648	748.186	1.492	11,8%	214	81	146	81	361	162	38%	19	9	41	1	389	26,1%	42,9%	223
Vorarlberg	2.602	390.296	586	22,5%	112	39	49	28	161	67	35%	8	2	17	0	171	29,1%	40,5%	177
Vienna	415	1.877.719	316	76,1%	158	69	61	34	220	103	43%	27	1	23	5	247	78,4%	43,8%	58
Austria	83.882	8.795.073	31.223	37,2%	3.222	1.150	2.070	1.125	5.292	2.275	36%	244	144	635	21	5.681	18,2%	41,2%	266

Areas in km²

¹ Permanent settlement area: land use categories: settlement, agricultural used land, gardens, vineyards, roads, road affiliated areas, parking lots, railways, industry- and commerce areas, excavation sites, sport- and leisure facilities, cemeteries
² Building land: buildings + building affiliated areas + gardens + industry- and commerce areas + cemeteries
³ sealed building land: buildings (100%), building affiliated areas (75%), industry- and commerce areas (60%), cemeteries (35%)
⁴ traffic and transport areas: roads, road affiliated areas, parking lots, railways
⁵ sealed traffic and transport areas: roads (100%), road affiliated areas (15%), parking lots (80%), railways (50%)
⁶ Building and traffic/transport: building land, roads, road affiliated areas, parking lots, railways
⁷ Degree of sealing: sealed building land / building land
⁸ Land consumption: total building land+ Traffic and Transport areas + recreational areas + excavation areas
⁹ sealing degree: sealed building land + sealed traffic and transport + recreational areas (20%) + excavation areas (10%) / land consumption

Source – population: Statistics Austria, population based on yearly average, year: 2017, query date: January 2019
 Source – area statistic: Regional information derived from the Austrian real estate database (Austrian Federal Office of Metrology and Surveying) from 31.12.2018, processed by Umweltbundesamt, 2019

Results

Application cookbook

We ran the Level 1 version of the soil sealing cookbook as described for the Sentinel 2 tile 32TNT with the reference year 2019. In QGIS we compared the possible changes identified by Sentinel 1 and/or Sentinel 2 with a Geoland basemap orthophoto of 2022 and the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service High Resolution Layer Imperviousness for 2018.

As the Copernicus layer and the orthophoto were from different years, we decided to use two categories for the polygons. The likely changes were categorised as '1' for “most likely artificial change” and '2' for “somewhat likely artificial change”. For a more precise interpretation, local knowledge or a detailed literature study could support the categorisation. Changes in the alpine landscape (e.g. riverbanks, water surfaces, glaciers or steep slopes) were not taken into account. Changes in traffic and parking areas also were not considered/detected.

We followed the cookbook and categorized the detected possible changes by Sentinel 1 and Sentinel 2 in two categories, most likely changes (1) and possible changes (2) by the interpretation of both orthophoto and the layer of imperviousness from Copernicus.

In Figure 6.1.2 we also see blue areas indicating 'most likely changes in 2018', which we did not count (in 2C) if the area was already marked as intensively developed by the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service High Resolution Layer Imperviousness 2018 layer (dark red) in 2B. Using this initial interpretation, we quantified a total of 30 ha of probable and most likely new sealed areas. This represents 0.005% of the permanent settlement area, but we were only able to detect new buildings.

A)

Figure 6.1.2 A) Most possible changes identified by Sentinel 1 and Sentinel 2 in blue, likely changes in yellow B) Copernicus Land Monitoring Service High Resolution Layer Imperviousness 2018 C) Possible changes identified manually by comparing results from Sentinel 1 and/or Sentinel 2 with orthophotos and CORINE LCC in red, most likely, somewhat possible new sealed area in orange.

Comparison

In 2018, the Austrian Environment Agency reported soil sealing at the national level from data statistically aggregated at the administrative level (cadastral municipality), obtained from the digital cadastral map (DKM). Land use was categorised according to settlement and transport areas, leisure, recreation and extraction areas and their respective changes over the years. Compared to the 2017

assessment, the change in "sealed building land and traffic and transport areas" in 2018 is 100 ha (Umweltbundesamt, 2022).

The results of the Umweltbundesamt in Table 6.1.1 in km² do not show minor changes and the area of sealed land is estimated according to the following key: sealed building land: buildings (100%), building related areas (75%), industrial and commercial areas (60%), cemeteries (35%). This makes it impossible to compare with the spatial approach.

However, since 2022, Austria has developed a 'new' methodology for monitoring land use changes. The new methodology combines a total of nine different data sources. For example, it includes the identification of areas used for transport purposes using a combination of DKM transport areas and active road axes from the Graph Integration Platform (GIP). For the two most important types of land use in Austria, agriculture and forestry, corresponding GIS data are compiled by Agrarmarkt Austria (AMA) as part of the subsidy administration and by the Federal Forestry Office (BFW) as part of the forest inventory. Areas managed in these systems are therefore classified as actively managed agricultural and forestry land. Changes in soil sealing are now determined from a combination of GIS vector data (buildings from the Digital Landscape Model (DLM), car parks or buffered GIP road axes) and remote sensing data (orthophoto interpretation or COPERNICUS satellite image products) at a scale of 1x1 m². Compared to very recent satellite imagery, this method will always lag a few years behind, but in the future all changes can be recorded, and a consistent time series can be produced. The new methodology is closer to the methodology used in the SERENA cookbook, as both approaches use open access European data from Copernicus, such as Sentinel 1 and 2 imagery.

Recommendations

To summarize we find that with the SERENA soil sealing cookbook

- The methodology is clearly described.
- We could not detect changes in the imperviousness of an existing flat surface (car park or square).
- Lack of local knowledge makes it sometimes difficult to interpret the images, especially in already built-up areas.

We suggest that for a more accurate interpretation, more than one year should be considered. By comparing the results of several years and adding local knowledge, uncertainties and errors can be reduced.

Resources

BEV, 2019. Regional Information derived from the Austrian real estate database BEV. Vienna, Austria.

Michel, K., Niedźwiecki, J., 2022. D3.1.1 Currently available assessments of soil threats and ecosystem services: data, metadata, and methodologies. SERENA, Vienna.

Umweltbundesamt, 2022. Flächeninanspruchnahme bis 2021 [WWW Document]. Flächeninanspruchnahme bis 2021. URL <https://www.umweltbundesamt.at/umweltthemen/boden/flaecheninanspruchnahme>

6.2 Belgium

Kasper Cockx & Katrien Oorts

Region: Flanders

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
Topography (vector)	Large-scale Reference Database (“Grootschalig Referentiebestand”) ¹	1/250 - 1/5000	Open data on Flemish Government website
Aerial imagery	Medium-scale annual winter aerial ² images	25 cm/15 cm	Open data on Flemish Government website

Methods

Data preparation

The “water” and “building” layers from the Large-scale Reference Database (LRD) could be used directly. For buildings, the Gbg (building at ground level), Gba (building attachment) (subcategories ‘afdak’ (shelter), ‘uitbreiding’ (extension), ‘verdieping’ (floor)), Knw (subcategories ‘cabine’ (cabin), ‘schoorsteen’ (chimney), ‘watertoren’ (water tower), ‘silo, opslagtank’ (silo, storage tank), ‘chemische installatie’ (chemical installation), ‘overbrugging’ (bridge)) and Trn (Terrain) (subcategory ‘verhard’ (sealed)) categories from the LRD were selected as ‘sealed’. The “roads” and “railways” layers often contain unsealed parts. Therefore, they required additional processing to arrive at a usable layer (see Cockx et al., 2022 page 8-10). The finally obtained water, building, road and railway layers were converted to 1 m grid cells.

Application cookbook

Level 2 of the soil sealing cookbook was applied and resulted in the map “Jaarlijkse bodemafdekkingskaart (JaarBAK), 1 m-resolutie”, which is abbreviated to “JaarBAK” in the text below.

Comparison results

The results of the Level 2 approach (JaarBAK) were compared to the existing 2012, 2015 and 2018 soil sealing maps “Bodemafdekkingskaart”, also known as “BAK”³, from the Flemish government agency Digitaal Vlaanderen. These 5 m resolution maps are produced every three years based on the LRD, summer aerial imagery, vegetation maps and agricultural parcels data.

Figure 6.2.1: Level 2 soil sealing map of Flanders in 2021, a.k.a. “Jaarlijkse bodemafdekkingskaart (JaarBAK), 1 m-resolutie, 2021” (Departement Omgeving, 2023).

¹ <https://www.vlaanderen.be/digitaal-vlaanderen/onze-oplossingen/basiskaart-vlaanderen-grb>

² <https://www.vlaanderen.be/datavindplaats/catalogus/orthofotomozaiek-middenschalig-winteropnamen-0>

³ <https://www.vlaanderen.be/datavindplaats/catalogus/bodemafdekkingskaart-bak-5m-resolutie-opname-2018>

The BAK's and JaarBAK's accuracies were assessed using a test set of labelled data. These labelled data were created by manually labelling soil sealing on parts of the available aerial images for Flanders between 2012 and 2020. 70% of the labelled images was assigned to the training set for training the machine learning model. The remaining 30% served as the test set for validating the model's results.

Results

Application cookbook

The Level 2 approach was applied to Flanders for every year between 2013 and 2021. The resulting map for 2021 – “Jaarlijkse bodemafdekkingskaart (JaarBAK), 1 m-resolutie, 2021” – shows the region's severe urban sprawl, resulting in a high degree of soil sealing scattered throughout Flanders (Figure 1). The map can also be consulted [online in the regional Geopunt data portal](#).

The 1 m resolution allows for highly detailed detections of a.o. residences and garden houses (Figure 6.2.2a), industrial sites and road networks (Figure 6.2.2b) and ribbon development in low-density areas (Figure 6.2.2c).

Comparison

Based on the test set, the Level 2 maps (JaarBAK) at 1 m resolution obtain an accuracy of 97.8%. This value is probably an underestimate, as the labelled material may contain small errors. The biggest differences compared to the ground truth occur at the edges of soil sealing, e.g. a road that is labelled just slightly narrower or wider than what eventually shows up on the Level 2 maps.

Aggregated 5 m resolution versions of the Level 2 maps (JaarBAK) and the test set were created for allowing a comparison with the BAK maps. The 5 m version of the JaarBAK maps obtain an accuracy of 98.0%. The BAK maps' accuracy level is 96.0%. Thus, the Level 2 maps (JaarBAK) offer a significant improvement over BAK. However, it should be noted that the BAK maps are based on summer aerial images, while the test set consists of winter aerial imagery, which will slightly lower the BAK's accuracy.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6.2.2: Examples of the 2020 Level 2 map (JaarBAK) at 1 m resolution (blue) for the urban core of Mechelen (a), the industrialised region of Overpelt (b) and the rural area of Ronse (c).

Additionally, a visual comparison for 2018 pointed to the specific improvements of the Level 2 maps (JaarBAK) compared to BAK (Figure 6.2.3 and Table 6.2.1). The Level 2 approach's biggest merit is the detection of sealed areas that are not (sufficiently) covered by the LRD, but form a significant part of Flanders' soil sealing, like houses' terraces and driveways, along with car parks and paved squares.

Figure 6.2.3: Contrary to BAK, the Level 2 maps (JaarBAK) correctly classify grass fields that have dried out in summer as ‘unsealed’ based on the winter aerial images. Example for the same area in the port of Antwerp.

Table 6.2.1: Improvements in the Level 2 maps (JaarBAK) compared to BAK based on a 2018 visual comparison.

Actual soil sealing usually detected correctly in the Level 2 maps (JaarBAK), but not or much less so in BAK

- Houses’ terraces and driveways
- Car parks and paved squares
- Small/narrow roads
- Cemeteries
- Gravel courts (red tennis courts and athletics tracks)
- Water fields (blue hockey fields)

Actual unsealed areas usually detected correctly in the Level 2 maps (JaarBAK), but not or much less so in BAK

- Unsealed areas of (major) roads
- Grass fields dried out in summer
- Large sand plains/quarries

Recommendations

The Level 1 approach of the soil sealing cookbook was considered for comparison to the Level 2 approach, but not applied. Given Flanders’ highly complex, fragmented settlement pattern, it would be too time-consuming to manually label the potential changes produced by the Level 1 tool. The

Copernicus' Impervious Density map, which is proposed as the reference soil sealing map, is also too coarse to be a reliable starting point for Flanders.

Based on our test of the Python notebook though, it might be useful to allow the user to change the thresholds of the Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 conditions, since different types of vegetation and building infrastructure in other regions might result in different spectral behaviour. Also, it could be interesting to make it possible/easier to not only compare to the previous year, but also to other years, e.g. by providing the option for inputting a second year. Lastly, it would be helpful to include direct links to the Sentinel-2 tiles and WMS services in the cookbook text and/or Python notebook.

Though the Level 2 approach at first requires a significant amount of time, effort and computational power for labelling aerial images and training a machine learning model, it results in automatically produced, highly detailed soil sealing maps for all years covered by aerial images and topography datasets, both in the past and in the future.

References

- Cockx, K., Pieters, J., Willems, P., Vanacker, S. (2022). *Jaarlijkse bodemafdekkingskaart Vlaanderen: Technisch rapport*. Vlaams Planbureau voor Omgeving. <https://archieff.onderzoek.omgeving.vlaanderen.be/Onderzoek-3331558>
- Departement Omgeving (2023). *Jaarlijkse bodemafdekkingskaart (JaarBAK), 1 m-resolutie, 2021*. <https://metadata.omgeving.vlaanderen.be/srv/dut/catalog.search#/metadata/1f229657-dc84-5fe5-95e4-fed297bc6b67>

6.3 Ireland

Alan Fahy

Region: County Wexford

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
Imperviousness	Copernicus imperviousness layer for 2018	10 * 10 m	https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/high-resolution-layer-imperviousness/imperviousness-density-2018#download
Satellite images	Google Earth		https://www.google.it/intl/it/earth/
Orthophotos	Tailte Éireann	1 * 1 m	Restricted WMS
Country boundaries	Administrative boundaries of the country	Vector	County Wexford Boundary County Wexford Boundary ArcGIS Hub
Grid 2x2 km	Shapefile to support the photointerpretation	Vector	

Methods

Data preparation

Data preparation followed the methodological procedures outlined in the cookbook. The prepared layers are shown in Figure 6.3.1:

Figure 6.3.1: A) 2x2 km grid of the selected region County Wexford. B) Copernicus Land Monitoring Service High Resolution Layer Imperviousness for 2018 (serving as a base soil-sealing layer)

Application cookbook

Cookbook procedures followed the Level 1 methodology, which clearly identified areas of possible soil sealing, providing a basis for photointerpretation. During photointerpretation, the option of using more detailed Eagle nomenclature for land classification was not adopted due to time constraints and the requirement of additional data from local government. For a more precise interpretation, local knowledge or a detailed literature study could support further categorisation. Changes in roadways were not detected by the methodology and were thus excluded from this analysis.

Comparison results

The SERENA methodology to identify soil sealing differs from Ireland's national approach. The national approach does not explicitly quantify changes in soil sealing, but rather maps an artificial imperviousness surface layer, synonymous with soil sealing. The artificial impervious surface layer presents as a level one layer for the National Land Cover Map, which is subdivided into buildings, roads, carparks, etc. in a level two layer. The most recent National Land Cover Map for 2018 (NCL 2018) combines existing land cover data with remote sensing, aerial, and satellite imagery to provide detailed information on Ireland's land cover types. It includes 36 classifications, using data from 2018. The main data sources are the OSi aerial photography campaign of 2018, satellite imagery from the European Space Agency Sentinel 2 programme, and OSi's PRIME 2 vector spatial database. This provides a more accurate assessment than the CORINE 2018 land cover map (Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), 2023).

The study area, County Wexford, is a significant agricultural hub located in the Southeast of Ireland. The region is composed of 4,437 farms covering an average size of 41.4 hectares, amounting to a total farmed land area of 183,651 hectares (IFA, 2020). The agricultural sector here employs ~5,970 full-time equivalents at the farm level and supports thousands of ancillary jobs in the rural economy. There are several well-developed townships and urban centres across the county despite a rural dominance. For the year 2018, NCL 2018 indicated that the percentage of Ireland covered by level one artificial surface class was 3.79% (EPA, 2023). County Wexford was slightly above the national average at 4.83%, with an area of 11,432 ha under artificial surfaces. For reference, Dublin had the highest average with 22.4% imperviousness (EPA, 2023).

Table 6.3.1: Total area in hectares (ha) and percentage of national area by Level 1 group for NLC 2018 and CLC 2018 (National Land Cover Map, 2018).

	Code	Level 1	NLC 2018 Area (ha)	Corine 2018 Area (ha)	NLC 2018 %	CLC 2018 %	% Diff.
	100	ARTIFICIAL SURFACES	268,016.08	155,961.25	3.79	2.21	+1.59
	200	EXPOSED SURFACES	133,270.48	151,080.74	1.89	2.14	-0.25
	300	CULTIVATED LAND	427,033.09	320,624.53	6.05	4.54	+1.51
	400	FOREST, WOODLAND AND SCRUB	1,290,756.87	672,084.98	18.27	9.51	+8.76
	500	GRASSLAND, SWAMP AND SALTMARSH	3,828,160.69	4,521,366.43	54.20	64.00	-9.81
	600	PEATLAND	462,291.55	968,808.26	6.55	13.71	-7.17
	700	HEATH AND BRACKEN	456,916.50	126,087.98	6.47	1.78	+4.68
	800	WATERBODIES	196,799.81	148,198.01	2.79	2.10	+0.69

Results

Application cookbook

We conducted an analysis using the Level 1 version of the soil-sealing cookbook on Sentinel 2 tiles 29UPU and 29UPT, with a reference year of 2019. For this analysis, we used National Orthophotos and Google Satellite images to confirm/deny potential changes in soil sealing identified by cookbook methodology. The 2018 Copernicus Land Monitoring Service High Resolution Layer Imperviousness served as the baseline for soil sealing (<https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/high-resolution-layer-imperviousness/imperviousness-density-2018#download>).

It is important to note that changes along beach lines, such as coastal erosion works, were not considered. Additionally, changes in roadways were not detected or considered, as the methodology only identified small and sporadic 'potential' changes in road networks.

The resolution of the orthophotos and satellite images allowed us to confirm the presence of impermeable materials like concrete, asphalt, and stone. Consequently, we categorized areas as 'sealed soil' instead of subdividing them into 'sealed' and 'most likely sealed' classes.

By quantifying the possible changes identified through the cookbook methodology, we detected 19.94 hectares of newly sealed soil from 2018 to 2019 in County Wexford. This represents 0.0084% of County Wexford's total land area. It is likely that the actual change in soil sealing from 2018 to 2019 was somewhat higher due to the ongoing construction of a major road network over the course of the analysis period, which was not accounted for in this research. This highlights the potential benefits of incorporating metadata and/or supplementary administrative data when analysing changes in soil sealing for a given region. Nevertheless, the methodology proved effective in identifying areas where soil sealing may have occurred during the year, allowing for a smooth photointerpretation process (e.g. Figure 6.3.2).

Figure 6.3.2: A) Site identified by the cookbook methodology as possible change in soil sealing, including the newly sealed soil identified by photointerpretation (green polygon). B) The same site in 2018

This application revealed new soil sealing in both rural and urban areas, with a significant concentration of newly sealed soil in and around the main urban centres of Wexford Town, Enniscorthy, and Gorey. Notably, several instances showed that productive agricultural land had been sealed. Figure 6.3.3 (A) shows the areas of newly sealed soil over the analysis period, while Figure 6.3.3 (B) presents these changes with the incorporation of the 2018 Copernicus Land Monitoring Service High Resolution Imperviousness Layer.

Figure 6.3.3: A) Map of Wexford including the polygons of newly sealed soil per the cookbook methodology. B) 2018 Copernicus Land Monitoring Service High Resolution Imperviousness Layer imposed on newly sealed soil

Figure 6.3.4: An example of a townland with identified areas of soil sealing (purple) added to the Copernicus base layer (red)

Comparison

The NCL 2018, published by the EPA and Tailte Éireann (formerly Ordnance Survey of Ireland) in March 2023, represents a significant improvement over previous data, such as the CORINE Land Cover 2018. The NCL 2018 reveals that artificial surfaces were previously underestimated by 1.59%, revising the figure to 3.79% of national land cover. Agriculture remains the primary Land Use Land Cover (LULC) type in Ireland, followed by wetlands and forestry.

The EPA reports that artificial areas have increased significantly (by 65%) since 1990. The majority of this change occurred between 1990 and 2006, slowed between 2006 and 2012 likely due to the economic recession, and increased again in 2018. Primary changes in artificial surfaces are attributed to increase in urban development, commercial/industrial areas, transport infrastructure, and sports and leisure facilities. These changes have predominantly affected agricultural areas.

The differing definitions of 'artificial surfaces' and 'soil sealing' complicate direct comparisons across various data sources. However, in 2021, Teagasc published a preliminary map of soil sealing in Ireland based on OSI Prime 2 data, indicating the percentage of soil sealing per km², categorised into <2%, 2-5%, 5-10%, and >10%. The main urban centres of County Wexford show soil sealing rates of >10% and 5-10%, while the majority of the land falls into the 2-5% sealed category.

The SERENA methodology effectively detected changes in soil sealing from 2018 to 2019 in County Wexford. Figure 6.3.5 illustrates this, with purple areas indicating newly sealed soil on both the Copernicus imperviousness layer for 2018 (A) and the national OSI Prime 2 artificial surface layer (B). The OSI Prime 2 layer, with its higher resolution, provides a more accurate representation of rural sites, including one-off housing, remote buildings, and tertiary roads. Despite these differences, the newly sealed areas identified by the SERENA methodology (purple) are clearly visible in both Figure 6.3.5 (A) and (B) which were previously unmapped.

Figure 6.3.5: A) 2018 Copernicus Land Monitoring Service High Resolution Imperviousness Layer (red) with newly sealed soil (purple). B) OSI Prime 2 national mapping artificial layer (red) with newly sealed soil (purple)

Resources:

Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), 2023. National Land Cover Map of Ireland 2018. Dublin, Ireland. URL: [National Land Cover Map of Ireland 2018 \(tailte.ie\)](https://www.tailte.ie/national-land-cover-map-of-ireland-2018)

Irish Farming Association (IFA) 2020. Economics. URL: [Wexford.pdf \(ifa.ie\)](https://www.ifa.ie/wexford.pdf)

6.4 Italy

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Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
Satellite images	Sentinel-1 C-band synthetic aperture radar imaging	20 x 20 m	https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/
Satellite images	Sentinel-2 Multispectral Instrument (MSI)	10 x 10 m	https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/
Satellite images	Google Earth		https://www.google.it/intl/it/earth/
Country boundaries	Administrative boundaries of the country	Vector	
Grid 2x2 km	Shapefile to support the photointerpretation	Vector	

Methods

Data preparation

Before cookbook application, we selected the cookbook Level 1 as the level to apply to the Italian national territory.

Furthermore, we defined the monitoring period in order to detect changes between two years:

- Year 1, 2021
- Year 2, 2022

Application cookbook

No deviations from the cookbook.

Comparison results

As the methodology applied in previous applications is the same proposed in the soil sealing cookbook, the results are comparable to those reported in D3.1.1.

Results

Application cookbook

Figure 6.4.1 Distribution of the main artificial surfaces changes of Italy from 2006 to 2022, and for the selected period (2021-2022).

Figure 6.4.1 shows the distribution of artificial surfaces in 2022 and the net increase from 2021 to 2022. In 2022 artificial surfaces cover 7.14% of national territory (accuracy 99%), mainly distributed in Lombardia, Veneto, and Campania administrative regions, with an increase of 0.33% compared to 2021 (Table 6.4.1). The higher net increase from 2021 to 2022 instead occurred in Sardegna, Molise and Puglia administrative regions (Table 6.4.1).

Table 6.4.1. Distribution, in hectares and percentages, of artificial surfaces in the administrative regions in 2022 and net increase from 2021 to 2022.

Region	Artificial surfaces 2022 [ha]	Artificial surfaces 2022 [%]	Net increase 2021-2022 [ha]	Net increase 2021-2022 [%]
Piemonte	170,199	6.70	617	0.36
Valle d'Aosta	7,025	2.15	22	0.32
Lombardia	290,278	12.16	908	0.31
Trentino-Alto Adige	41,061	3.02	130	0.32
Veneto	217,825	11.88	739	0.34
Friuli Venezia Giulia	63,528	8.02	156	0.25
Liguria	39,327	7.26	33	0.08
Emilia-Romagna	200,025	8.89	635	0.32
Toscana	141,842	6.17	238	0.17
Umbria	44,434	5.26	65	0.15
Marche	64,940	6.96	218	0.34
Lazio	140,430	8.16	485	0.35
Abruzzo	54,012	5.00	149	0.28
Molise	17,489	3.94	80	0.46
Campania	143,020	10.52	557	0.39
Puglia	159,459	8.24	718	0.45
Basilicata	31,825	3.19	100	0.32
Calabria	76,451	5.07	78	0.10
Sicilia	167,684	6.52	608	0.36
Sardegna	80,582	3.34	537	0.67
Italy	2,151,437	7.14	7,076	0.33

Comparison

As the methodology applied to detect artificial surfaces in 2021 and 2022 is the same, the results are comparable. Table 6.4.2 shows the extension and distribution of artificial surfaces in the administrative regions in 2021 and the net increase from 2020 to 2021.

Table 6.4.2. Distribution, in hectares and percentages, of artificial surfaces in the administrative regions in 2021 and net increase from 2020 to 2021.

Region	Artificial surfaces 2021 [ha]	Artificial surfaces 2021 [%]	Net increase 2020-2021 [ha]	Net increase 2020-2021 [%]
Piemonte	169,582.16	6.68	679.02	0.37
Valle d'Aosta	7,002.61	2.15	14.58	0.15
Lombardia	289,370.49	12.12	924.27	0.31
Trentino-Alto Adige	40,931.02	3.01	92.33	0.21
Veneto	217,085.57	11.84	616.58	0.31
Friuli Venezia Giulia	63,371.11	8.00	121.50	0.16
Liguria	39,294.46	7.25	38.56	0.10
Emilia-Romagna	199,389.83	8.86	713.54	0.33
Toscana	141,604.17	6.16	287.88	0.21
Umbria	44,369.04	5.25	100.28	0.25
Marche	64,722.46	6.94	144.26	0.21
Lazio	139,944.39	8.13	422.91	0.29
Abruzzo	53,863.31	4.99	327.48	0.78
Molise	17,409.52	3.92	54.14	0.31
Campania	142,463.46	10.48	504.23	0.34
Puglia	158,740.21	8.20	488.65	0.32
Basilicata	31,725.08	3.18	76.88	0.24
Calabria	76,372.64	5.06	100.76	0.11
Sicilia	167,075.94	6.50	513.61	0.29
Sardegna	80,044.19	3.32	199.89	0.23
Italia	2,144,361.66	7.11	6,421.35	0.30

6.5 Netherlands

Martine Trip and Joost Crujisen

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
Land use	Sentinel-2	10 m	Can be obtained by the Google Earth Engine procedure as described in the cookbook
Land use	Sentinel-1	10 m	Can be obtained by the Google Earth Engine procedure as described in the cookbook

Methods

Data preparation

The data that was used in the cookbook application was obtained from the Google Earth Engine procedure as proposed and was ready to process.

Application cookbook

The cookbook was implemented until the photointerpretation part. Due to time constraints and lack of experience on photointerpretation, this part was only carried out on a small area of the country, to evaluate the method.

Comparison results

The results were compared to the CORINE Land Cover map from 2018 (CLC2018).

Results

Application cookbook

The potential soil sealing map of the Netherlands between 2020 and 2021 can be found in figure 6.5.1. However, the photointerpretation part of the cookbook has not been performed. Therefore, we can only refer to the marked areas of the map as potentially sealed areas.

It is visible in the total map that lots of water areas are marked as potentially sealed, which would be very unlikely. The changes on land are so small that they are not visible in this map for the whole country.

- 1 Possible changes identified by both Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 methodologies (very probable changes)
- 2 Possible changes identified by Sentinel-1 methodology
- 3 Possible changes identified by Sentinel-2 methodology
- 4 Possible changes identified by Sentinel-2 methodology with shift period (less probable)

Figure 6.5.1 Soil sealing map of the complete country. Only small spots are visible on land.

If we zoom to an area (Almere-Poort) for which it is known that there was built intensively during the past years, it shows different sealed areas, mostly identified by Sentinel-2 methodology (figure 6.5.2; yellow and orange areas).

- 1 Possible changes identified by both Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 methodologies (very probable changes)
- 2 Possible changes identified by Sentinel-1 methodology
- 3 Possible changes identified by Sentinel-2 methodology
- 4 Possible changes identified by Sentinel-2 methodology with shift period (less probable)

Figure 6.5.2 Map of potential soil sealing in Almere-Poort, a recently build district in the city of Almere.

The photointerpretation (Figure 6.5.3) was performed on the district Almere-Poort. It is visible that several spots on land are correctly marked as sealed, but most of the spots are false positives. All marked spots on open water (see Figure 6.5.2) are false positives, but for convenience not taken into account in the photointerpretation part.

- Correctly marked as soil sealing
- Incorrectly marked as soil sealing

Figure 6.5.3 Photointerpretation of the potential soil sealing in Almere-Poort (as marked in figure 6.5.2).

Comparison

- 1% imperviousness value
- 25% imperviousness value
- 50% imperviousness value
- 75% imperviousness value
- 100% imperviousness value

Figure 6.5.4 Results of soil sealing in Almere-Poort by the Corine Land Cover 2018 map.

The results from the potential soil sealing map can be compared to the CORINE Land Cover 2018 data (CLC2018), Figure 6.5.4. However, the cookbook application was done on soil sealing between 2020 and 2021, while the CLC2018 was based on earlier satellite data. Nevertheless, it provides a fairly good indication as only sealing in 2019 is not included in Figure 6.5.4.

Recommendations

- A large part of the false positive values for the Netherlands are on water, which is clearly no soil sealing. Improving this sensitivity for water would be an addition.
- Photointerpretation is a very time consuming operation. It would be an addition if there is a faster way to do it. It would also improve the cookbook if there is a more standard way of photointerpretation. There remains a lot of freedom now on how to do the photo interpretation, while a cookbook should guide you through a standard way to make these maps.

6.6 Spain

Emilio Doñate, Sabina Asins

Region (if not national scale): Valencia

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
<i>Orthophotography 2020</i>	<i>Orthophotography of the Valencian Community (05/2020)</i>	0.25 m	https://terramapas.icv.gva.es/02_2020CVAL0025
<i>Orthophotography 2021</i>	<i>Orthophotography of the Valencian Community between 05/2021 and 08/2021</i>	0.25 m	https://terramapas.icv.gva.es/02_2021CVAL0025
<i>Cadastral parcels (vector)</i>	Cadastral parcels layer	1:2000 1 m	http://ovc.catastro.meh.es/Cartografia/WMS/ServidorWMS.aspx
<i>Orthophotography 2023</i>	<i>Orthophotography of the Valencian Community between 04/2023 and 08/2023</i>	0.25 m	https://terramapas.icv.gva.es/02_2023CVAL0025

Methods

Data preparation

For data preparation in the soil sealing analysis, several layers available through Web Map Service (WMS) servers were loaded and managed in QGIS. The main layers used were the orthophotos of the years 2020 and 2021, and the cadastral parcels. These layers provide essential geospatial data for the identification and delineation of sealed areas.

First, connections to the relevant WMS servers were configured within QGIS, allowing real-time access to high-resolution orthophotos provided by the Spatial Data Infrastructure of the Valencian

Community. The 2020 and 2021 orthophotos, with a resolution of 0.25 meters, were crucial for the visual identification of changes in land cover.

In addition, the vector layer of cadastral parcels at a scale of 1:2000, obtained from the WMS service of the Cadastre, which is updated daily from the cartographic bases of the Cadastre, was incorporated. This layer allowed a more precise delimitation of the areas of interest, facilitating the identification of parcel changes.

Application cookbook

We implemented the soil sealing monitoring process following the structured guidelines outlined in the Soil Sealing Cookbook. The focus was on employing Level 1, which involves semi-automatic classification techniques using remote sensing data, GIS software, and advanced classification methodologies. This approach aimed to detect and quantify soil sealing within the study area using Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellite imagery, complemented by high-resolution orthophotos and cadastral data.

To carry out the soil sealing monitoring process in the Valencia area, the steps detailed in the Cookbook were followed. Google Colab was used to work with the notebook provided, focusing on tile 31SBD and the year 2021. The process included the execution of specific steps to obtain and prepare the relevant raster layer, which was stored in Google Drive for later use.

Figure 6.6.1 Grid of tile 31SBD

Subsequently, in QGIS, a grid with cells of 2 km² in size was created, with the aim of segmenting and analysing the area of the city of Valencia in a systematic way. This selection allowed the following stages of the analysis to be carried out, ensuring a detailed and specific approach to the assessment of soil sealing in that particular urban area.

After selecting the area of interest in the city of Valencia, the process of photo-interpretation began. This step involved reviewing the images in detail and supplementing existing polygons or adding new ones in a layer created specifically for this purpose. This additional layer allowed for a more accurate and detailed representation of the sealed and unsealed areas, ensuring that all modifications and additions correctly reflected the features observed on the ground. The photointerpretation was supported by high-resolution orthophotos and other recent geospatial data to ensure the accuracy of the results obtained.

Comparison results

The results of the soil sealing analysis obtained by applying the Soil Sealing Cookbook were compared with the D3.1.1 report, which used data from the 2014 Spanish Land Cover Information System (SIOSE). While the previous report provided a view based on data from several years ago, the current study used updated data from 2020 and 2021, including Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellite imagery, high-resolution orthophotos and other recent geospatial data.

It's important to note that this comparison could not be realized due to the temporal differences between the datasets.

Results

Application cookbook

As seen in the images, the purple polygons represent the areas identified in the 2021 orthophoto that have been paved or levelled for further paving. The notebook indicates that there have been changes in these areas. On the other hand, the red lattice indicates areas where changes have occurred but have not been detected in the automated classification.

Figure 6.6.2 Orthophoto 2020 with photointerpretation and mask of tile 31SBD

Figure 6.6.3 Orthophoto 2020 with photointerpretation and mask of tile 31SBD

Comparison

As can be seen, most of the changes reflected by the mask are changes detected by the NDVI. This may give incorrect results in soil sealing, as the changes in NDVI may not correspond directly to the paving or sealing. The images show several areas that have been modified and detected by the mask, but over a period of one year, changes in NDVI may generate incorrect data for some areas. We have detected areas in the city where changes in trees are detected without any real modifications of soil sealing. We have also identified areas where masonry works were carried out during that period, where the ground was already sealed before the works and the mask still detects changes.

Figure 6.6.4 Orthophotography 2021 with cadastral parcels, transport network, photointerpretation and mask of tile 31SBD

By comparing these results with the images shown below, which present the current state of the cadastre and the orthophoto of 2023, the evolution of the area can be observed and the accuracy of the detected changes can be verified.

Figure 6.6.5 Orthophotography 2023

Recommendations

It is recommended that the thresholds used in the NDVI index be revised to improve the accuracy of interpretations and the detection of changes in soil sealing. Adjusting these thresholds could reduce the incidence of false positives and negatives, especially in areas with vegetation that have not experienced significant changes. It is also recommended that the possibilities of interpreting "bare soil, without vegetation" be reviewed, because the satellite does not detect it and identifies the "bare soil" with "sealed soil".

In addition, it is suggested to consider extending the time period analysed to assess whether better results are achieved in the change mask. A longer temporal analysis could provide a more accurate and reliable picture of soil sealing trends and land use changes.

6.7 Summary and Synthesis

Table 6.7.1 Differences between cookbook application and earlier results from member states.

Difference	Member States
Small difference	Belgium, Italy
Values different	
Patterns different	
Values and patterns different	Austria , Ireland, Spain

Table 6.7.2. Differences in application between earlier assessment and cookbook. For those MS for which no earlier results were available a summary of the cookbook application is provided.

Member State	Difference type (V, P, V&P)*	Assessment	Soil data	Auxiliary data	Methods	Spatial resolution (m)
Austria	V&P	Earlier		EU Data MS Data	Data statistically aggregated obtained from the digital cadastral map	100
		Cookbook		EU Data MS Data	Remote sensing classification and photointerpretation	10
Belgium	NO	Earlier		MS Data	Machine learning model	1
		Cookbook		MS Data	Machine learning model	1
Ireland	V&P	Earlier		EU Data	Object-oriented digital mapping data model	1 Km ²
		Cookbook		EU Data	Remote sensing classification and photointerpretation	10
Italy	NO	Earlier		EU Data	Remote sensing classification and photointerpretation	10
		Cookbook		EU Data	Remote sensing classification and photointerpretation	10

Netherlands		n.a.	Cookbook		EU Data	Remote sensing classification and photointerpretation	10
Spain	V&P	Earlier			MS Data	Data aggregated from cadastral dataset and photointerpretation	1
		Cookbook			EU Data	Remote sensing classification and photointerpretation	10

*n.a. = not available, S = similar, V = values are different, P = patterns are different

Table 6.7.2 shows that almost all MS that applied the cookbook already had earlier results, the Netherlands being the only exception. Note also that the soil data column is empty since, contrary to other ST and SES, no soil data is used to evaluate soil sealing.

The applications of the cookbook illustrate that both level 1 and level 2 methods have advantages as well as disadvantages, as described below.

Level 1

Pro: Easily detection of artificial surfaces by running the Python code required for the monitoring of soil sealing

Shortcomings/Recommendations:

- The photointerpretation is time consuming
- For a more accurate interpretation, more than one year should be considered. By comparing the results of several years and adding local knowledge, uncertainties and errors can be reduced.
- To allow the user to change the thresholds of the Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 conditions, since different types of vegetation and building infrastructure in other regions might result in different spectral behaviour
- Some difficulties to detect bare soils

Level 2

Pro: Automatically production of highly detailed soil sealing maps (e.g. terraces, driveways)

Shortcomings/Recommendations:

- An existing "known" sealed map for buildings, roads, railways is required
- Large amount of time, effort and computational power for labelling aerial images and training a machine learning model

7 Bundles

The cookbook for bundles of ST/SES provides a detailed description of how bundles were evaluated (D2.3.2). The analysis of bundles focused on the co-occurrence in space, without investigating the relationships between ST/SES in depth. It also used an a posteriori approach in which erosion, biomass and SOC loss were considered. Hence, the analysis determined how these co-occur in space. The following sections present the results of cookbook applications for bundles that have been done within the framework of SERENA.

7.1 Czech Republic

Jessica Reyes Rojas

Data used:

Czech Republic boundaries data source (upper table) and Soil-based ecosystem service and soil threat indicators (lower table).

Category	description	Availability data
Czech Republic national boundary	administrative boundaries for Czech Republic:	https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/eea-reference-grids-2/gis-files/czech-republic-shapefile

SES/ST	Databas e	Indicator	Unit	Resoluti on (km)	Projection	Type spatial	YEAR	Land use
SOC loss	Pan-Europe an SOC stock of agricult ural soils	Eroded soil organic carbon: C_eroded_prj.tif	t C ha-1 yr-1	1	Projection: ETRS_LAEA	raster	avera ge of the perio d 2000-2010	Agricul ture land

Primary biomass production	Soil Biomass Productivity maps of grasslands and pasture, of croplands and of forest areas in the European Union (EU27)	Biomass production	Dimensionless (1-10)	1	ETRS_LAEA_10_52	raster	Not clear 2013?	Agriculture land, grassland, forest
Soil erosion	Water erosion	Water erosion	t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	0.1	Projection: ETRS_LAEA	raster	2015	Agriculture land

Methods

Data preparation

The cookbook's methodology and scripts were applied

Application cookbook

As stated in the cookbook, using the R script.

Comparison results

There is a lack of applications in the literature of bundles for the Czech Republic.

Results

Application cookbook

I took already quantified indicators provided by ESDAC. Each indicator was quantified at European scale at 1 km² spatial resolution based on the ETRS89 LAEA projection. Then I cropped the area corresponding to the Czech Republic. The indicators were standardized (Figure 7.1.1) by subtracting the minimum value observed and then dividing by the difference between the maximum and the minimum values observed (Paracchini et al., 2011).

Figure 7.1.1. Distribution of the standardized indicators using min-max standardization

I estimated the best number of clusters using the Nbclust package (Charrad et al., 2014). According to the result the best number of clusters was 3 (Figure 7.1.2).

Figure 7.1.2. Calculating the optimal number of clusters (K) using Nbclust package in R

B1 is a high biomass production, low erosion and low SOC loss bundle medium quality one. B3 is a medium PBP, low erosion and SOC loss bundle medium quality. In contrast B2 is high erosion and SOC loss with low PBP, indicating a low-quality one (Figure 7.1.3).

Some of the areas with high primary biomass production located in the lowlands of the country demonstrate the protective effects of the vegetation in controlling erosion and SOC loss. The spatial patterns of bundle B2 moderately represent the distribution of threatened areas due to the combined effect of water and tillage erosion, as well as SOC loss. These results were compared with the map of the potential risk of the combined effect of water and tillage erosion at a 5 m spatial resolution (Žížala et al., 2020). In our analysis, while some areas of southern Moravia with the presence of chernozems were moderately represented, other neighbouring areas with intensive agriculture were not, suggesting that the coarse resolution of the input data used for our bundle assessment may have failed to capture important information about the erosion. Therefore, it is important to use national data at a finer spatial resolution to provide a more accurate and realistic bundle assessment.

Bundle	Erosion	PBP	SOC loss
B1	0.02	0.81	0.02
B2	0.03	0.43	0.03
B3	0.02	0.65	0.02

Figure 7.1.3. Spatial clusters of primary biomass production (PBP), erosion and SOC loss given by k-means method. These are not consolidated results that require expert validation

Comparison

There is a lack of studies mapping bundles for the Czech Republic, making it difficult to draw comparisons. The indicators selected for this analysis were extracted from the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC). This means the data correspond to European-level assessments rather than national-

level data. Additionally, the maps used in this exercise have a 1km² resolution, which hides important information about the soil threats and services interactions at finer scales.

Recommendations

First, to produce bundles for the Czech Republic, I recommend computing the indicators using national data at a finer spatial resolution. This will allow for an assessment that considers the specific patterns of the indicators occurring at a finer scale, which would otherwise be hidden at a coarser scale. Additionally, the use of similar data sources is crucial to avoid the high uncertainty generated by data from different sources.

Second, the careful selection of indicators to produce meaningful combinations or bundles is of utmost importance. In this case, we combined two soil threats with one ecosystem service, which may not be the ideal set of indicators. Our analysis was constrained by the available data.

References

- Paracchini, M. L., Pacini, C., Jones, M. L. M., & Pérez-Soba, M. (2011). An aggregation framework to link indicators associated with multifunctional land use to the stakeholder evaluation of policy options. *Ecological indicators*, 11(1), 71-80.
- Charrad, M., Ghazzali, N., Boiteau, V., & Niknafs, A. (2014). Determining the number of clusters using NbClust package. *MSDM*, 2014, 1.
- Žižala, D., Juřicová, A., Kapička, J., & Novotný, I. (2021). The potential risk of combined effects of water and tillage erosion on the agricultural landscape in Czechia. *Journal of Maps*, 17(2), 428-438.

7.2 Estonia

Elsa Putku, Tambet Kikas

Data used

Data type		Indicator	Unit	Resolution (km)	Year	Preprocessing
ST	SOC loss	Loss of SOC stock in 5 years in agricultural soils	t C ha-1 yr-1	0.1*0.1	2014-2021	maps of SOC stock in t0 and t2 using ISRIC DSM workflow with EU covariates.
ST	Soil erosion	Soil loss by water	t ha-1 yr-1	0.1*0.1	potential erosion	
SES	Primary biomass production	Biomass production	Dimensionless (1-10)	1	2013	

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
SOC stock	SOC stock in year 0 (representing years 2014-2017) SOC stock in year 0+t (representing years 2019-2021)	100 * 100 m	Generated using ISRIC DSM workflow, will become available in metadata catalogue

Soil organic carbon concentration	1037 point data of measured SOC (%)	point data	not available
soil erosion	water erosion potential in agricultural soils modelled by USLE	100*100m	not available
Primary biomass production	2013 biomass production	1*1 km	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-biomass-productivity-maps-grasslands-and-pasture-coplands-and-forest-areas-european
Land use	agricultural land of EE, also used as a mask	100 * 100 m	derived from Estonian Topographic Database: https://geoportaal.maaamet.ee/index.php?lang_id=2&page_id=618

Methods

Data preparation

Raster data was resampled to the same extent and resolution with the land use mask, meaning that biomass production was resampled to 100*100 m. Biomass production was used as it was available from the CREA sharepoint. Soil erosion was modelled using the USLE model and only the potential erosion by water as an indicator was used, not actual erosion accounting the vegetation. That means that erosion potential shows the potential on bare soil. SOC loss for a 5 year period was calculated by the following formula:

Absolute sequestration rate ($t\ C\ ha^{-1}\ a^{-1}$): $(SOC\ stock_{t2} - SOC\ stock_{t0})/5$

SOC therefore represents also the increase in SOC stock, not only loss.

Application cookbook

The bundles cookbook was used 100%, no deviations in the script were made.

Comparison results

This was the first time a bundles map was generated at the scale of the country and therefore no comparison is available.

Results

The input layers in bundles analysis showed very different statistical distribution in indicators (Figure 7.2.1). The distribution of erosion is left-skewed which is expected, as the country is flat in topography (average elevation in Estonia reaches 50 m) and the erosion potential in most of the country is very low (Figure 7.2.2).

SOC loss values have a normal distribution representing that relatively equal area of the arable soils in Estonia sequester or lose carbon in five years. SOC loss is more visible in the center of the country and in few specific areas what can be associated with soils with higher carbon content (gleyic and organic soils) (Figure 7.2.3). Higher SOC values, these are soils that sequester carbon, are more in the eastern Estonia. The spatial pattern indicates that in areas where the soils have naturally higher SOC concentrations, these soils lose carbon in time, however, in the areas (northeastern and southeastern part) where soils have already lower SOC concentrations and therefore SOC stock these soils seem to

gain SOC in time. This spatial pattern is in accordance with the soil types in the Estonian large-scale soil map. Also a relevant topic to consider is that the soils samples used for predicting SOC stock in two years were mainly sampled from arable soils. Arable soils with high organic carbon stock are more prone to losing carbon when they are managed as croplands compared to grasslands as soil management induces decomposition of organic matter. The results of SOC loss/RSR map are more representative to managed arable soils compared grassland management in Estonia.

Figure 7.2.1. Distribution of indicators before and after scaling by min and maximum values.

Figure 7.2.2. Spatial distribution of scaled erosion (Er) values.

Figure 7.2.3. Spatial distribution of scaled SOC loss values.

Biomass production has highest scaled values in the center of Estonia (Figure 7.2.4) what are the most productive agricultural areas in Estonia in terms of best agricultural soils. Therefore, this region is highly utilized in crop production compared to grasslands and pastures which dominate in the coastal regions and on gleyic and organic soils. Of course, the original resolution of biomass production was 1*1 km which is much coarser compared to SOC loss and erosion maps (100*100m). Therefore, the spatial pattern might be different if biomass production was available on finer scale.

Figure 7.2.4. Spatial distribution of scaled biomass production values.

Based on different measures of cluster quality (Figure 7.2.5 and 7.2.6), 3 clusters were chosen for further bundles analysis. However, according to option A described in the cookbook, the best number

of clusters was 2, but taking into account also the Elbow method for defining the best number of clusters, 3 was chosen.

Figure 7.2.5. Cluster quality measures according to subsetting the entire database to calculate K value.

Figure 7.2.6. Cluster quality measure according to the elbow method for K calculation.

Application cookbook

Bundle B3 dominates in the center of Estonia – north from lake Võrtsjärve until the northern coast of Estonia (Figure 7.2.7). Biomass production center value was the highest in B3 coupled with high SOC. Comparing scaled biomass values map to the bundles map the overlap of higher biomass values with the area of B3 is evident. Bundle B2 is more visible in the western part of the continental mainland and islands, whereas bundle B1 is dominating in the southeastern part of the country and in the northern coastline. Bundle B1 has the biggest representation (the highest number of pixels in the cluster), B3 has a bit less pixels in clusters and B2 has the lowest representation (Figure 7.2.8).

Figure 7.2.7. Spatial distribution of bundles in Estonian agricultural land.

Figure 7.2.8. Number of pixels in the clusters.

Erosion is a variable that does not contribute too much to differentiating the clusters (bundles) as the centroid values are low (Table 7.2.1, Figure 7.2.9) and also due to the low erosion potential in the country. Therefore, B1 is a bundle with high SOC loss relatively low biomass, B2 is a high biomass relatively low SOC loss, and B3 is the highest biomass, but high SOC loss too.

Table 7.2.1. Summary of main results of bundles’ analyses (k = 3). Values for the different SES/ST per bundle are cluster centroid values (e.g, bundles’ means). Er = erosion, Bio = biomass, SOC = SOC stock change. B1 = bundle 1, B2 = bundle 2, B3 = bundle 3.

SES/ST	Er	Bio	SOC	Interpretation
B1	0.011	0.684	0.634	B1, highest erosion between bundles, biomass and SOC have the more or less the same value, SOC relatively highest
B2	0.007	0.702	0.454	B2 is a low erosion, higher biomass, low SOC
B3	0.009	0.934	0.621	B3 is a low erosion and high SOC, biomass is the highest relative to other bundles.

Figure 7.2.9. The share of ST/SES values in each of cluster.

Recommendations

Specify in the cookbook that the user must choose correct number clusters and indicate the line where to insert the number. Explain more how to interpret the results of bundles analysis.

7.3 Italy

Medina-Roldán, Eduardo, Lorenzetti, Romina, Ungaro, Fabrizio

Region (if not national scale): Emilia-Romagna lowland plains (see map from wiki-commons below)

Data used

Apart from the data input specified in the cookbook.

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
Emilia-Romagna Region political boundary	Borders of the Emilia-Romagna Region, this layer was then cropped for the plain area only with a vector of soil properties, and re-projected to various reference/coordinated systems	NA	Can be downloaded at: https://geoportale.regione.emilia-romagna.it/download/dati-e-prodotti-cartografici-preconfezionati/tutti-download-preconfezionati/limite_pianura_collina-montagna_wgs84.zip/@download/file/Limite_pianura_collina%20montagna_WGS84.zip
Emilia-Romagna soil organic C stock	This product is the upgrade (2023) to an existing one in the region. It comprises the whole region (lowland plain and mountain area) and it is derived from a spatialised organic C map and a PTF-derived soil bulk density 0-30 cm. For this application, the	100 m	https://datacatalog.regione.emilia-romagna.it/catalogCTA/dataset/r_emiro_2023-08-09t162508

	map was clipped to encompass only the lowland plains.		
<i>Emilia-Romagna soil erosion control</i>	Difference between Potential and Actual water erosion (2019 time stamp) as determined by RUSLE. For this application, the map was clipped to encompass only the lowland plains.	100 m	http://mappegis.regione.emilia-romagna.it/gstatico/documenti/dati_pedol/download/erosione_idrica_2019_raster.zip
<i>Emilia-Romagna NEP</i>	NEP SERENA product for early summer. This application is restricted to the lowland plains.	500 m (nominal)	

Methods

Data preparation

The extents of the soil C stock and soil erosion control were restricted to the lowland plains of the region.

Application cookbook

As stated in the cookbook. Some variations from the cookbook had to be implemented to make the data compatible. Since the NEP layer is vector built upon around the polygons of wheat land cover determined by the Eurocrop map 2018, the treatment of the other two soil-based ecosystem services had to adapt to this layout. The values of these two variables are rendered as the mean values of each variable in a given polygon coming from the wheat land cover from the Eurocrop map 18. In this way, if a wheat polygon comprised more than either a soil C stock or soil erosion control location (pixel), the value was averaged at the polygon level. Once this was done for both soil C stock and soil erosion control, the clustering algorithm was applied.

Comparison results

A previous version of SESs bundles for the whole region (in opposition to the one shown in this application that corresponds to wheat land cover) is available from Medina-Roldán et al. 2024. Whereas the SESs to identify the bundles are different in general, the exercise allows to look for spatial patterns in the distribution of SESs bundles.

Results

Application cookbook

The spatial distribution of the SESs bundles map can be seen in the figure 7.3.1 below. Four bundles were identified.

Figure 7.3.1. Bundles map of the Emilia-Romagna Region, Italy. The bundles represent clusters for the SESs: net ecosystem production (NEP), erosion control (ERCTRL), and soil organic carbon stocks (SOC). The radar plots radius shows the scaled value of a particular SESs in the bundle. ERCTRL has been magnified 100 times to make it visible.

The values of the 3 different SESs for the 4 bundles can be seen in Table 7.3.1.

Table 7.3.1. Mean values (min-max scaled) of SESs in the 4 bundles solution in the Emilia-Romagna Region. The min-max scaling was applied to the lowland plain area for SOC and ERCTRL and to the areas identified as wheat fields for NEP.

Bundles	NEP	ERCTRL	SOC
1	0.26	0.00008	0.26
2	0.65	0.006	0.09
3	0.51	0.002	0.08
4	0.36	0.0007	0.07

The bundle 1 corresponds to soils with high SOC and low NEP and ERCTRL; bundle 2 to soils with low SOC, highest NEP and medium ERCTRL; bundle 3 is high NEP, medium ERCTRL and low SOC; and bundle 4 represents areas with low NEP, ERCTRL and SOC. It can be seen that the areas covered by the bundles' map do not correspond to the areas of maximum erosion control in the low land plains of the Emilia-Romagna region.

Comparison

A bundles analysis for 7 different SESs was applied in Medina-Roldán et al. 2024 (Figure 7.3.2). Whereas strictly these bundles are not the same (and as such not strictly comparable), a contrast between the two maps allows us to:

- 1) Observe that certain soils (in this case the rich organic soils represented by bundle 1 in this application) are singled out, despite using different input variables (SESs) as a result of their uniqueness in properties.
- 2) Different inclusion of input variables produces different bundles. This has to be taken into account in the communication of SES bundles to non-scientific audiences, and it highlights that approaches might be used in the future where SESs are selected “a priori” depending on the objectives of the analysis.

Figure 7.3.2. Bundles map of the Emilia-Romagna Region, Italy. The bundles represent clusters for seven SESs (from Medina-Roldán et al. 2024).

Recommendations

- 1) To develop strategies to validate internally (sensitivity and uncertainty) and externally the maps.
- 2) To increase the number of approaches to identify SESs/STs relations.

References

Medina-Roldán, E., Lorenzetti, R., Calzolari, C., & Ungaro, F. (2024). Disentangling soil-based ecosystem services synergies, trade-offs, multifunctionality, and bundles: A case study at regional scale (NE Italy) to support environmental planning. *Geoderma*, 448, 116962.

7.4 Poland

Sylwia Pindral

Data used

Apart from the data input specified in the cookbook.

Category	Description	Resolution	Availability data
ST rasters	SOC content Soil erosion	100m*100m	IUNG-PIB – on a special request
SES rasters	GHG – Net Ecosystem Production Soil erosion control	100m*100m	IUNG-PIB - on a special request

Methods

Data preparation

All the steps were done following the Bundles cookbook.

Application cookbook

Most of the steps were done in RStudio (R 4.3.1). For the Bundles cookbook testing we used all the rasters that were prepared according to the SERENA WP3 cookbooks. We created maps for soil threats (ST) and soil-based ecosystem services (SES) bundles:

- 1) Including soil threats: SOC content as the in, soil erosion
- 2) Including soil-based ecosystem services: GHG, Erosion control

Comparison results

The map cannot be compared with previous studies, due to the lack of such an analysis for Poland.

Results ST

Application cookbook

Figure 7.4.1. Histograms of the ST values distribution. Upper part presents raw values, bottom histograms present standardised values of ST.

The input data distribution is presented in Figure 7.4.1. For SOC content and soil erosion, the histograms are strongly right-skewed.

Based on the rasters values distribution, the results of the optimal clusters number were calculated:

- * Among all indices:
- * 3 proposed 2 as the best number of clusters
- * 8 proposed 3 as the best number of clusters
- * 4 proposed 4 as the best number of clusters
- * 1 proposed 5 as the best number of clusters
- * 2 proposed 6 as the best number of clusters
- * 4 proposed 8 as the best number of clusters
- * 1 proposed 9 as the best number of clusters

***** Conclusion *****

* According to the majority rule, the best number of clusters is 3

As was shown above, most of the calculated indices propose 3 as the optimal number of clusters. According to this result we decided to implement this number in the further analysis. This choice can be supported by the plots of Dindex and sum of squares presented on Figure 7.4.2.

Figure 7.4.2. DIndex and total sum of squares plots.

The final results on bundles are presented in Figure 7.4.3-7.4.5.

Figure 7.4.3. The number of pixels in selected clusters.

Soil Threats Bundles

Soil Threats Bundles

Figure 7.4.4. The maps of ST bundles for Poland.

Figure 7.4.5. The mean of ST values in each of cluster.

We identified three ST Bundles. However, they are strongly related to the distribution of the SOC values, not soil erosion. In the Bundle 3 we can observe very high SOC content values and low soil erosion (Figure 7.4.5). These areas occur in the valley bottoms and local depressions where organic soil occur (Figure 7.4.4). Bundle 2 is the group of soils with low SOC content but also wide range of soil erosion values (including the highest rates of soil erosion, but also soils where erosion is very low or does not occur). In the Bundle 1 we can identify the group of soil rich in SOC, and also low rates of soil erosion (Figure 7.4.4 and 7.4.5).

Results ST

Application cookbook

Figure 7.4.6. Histograms of the SES values distribution. Upper part presents raw values, bottom histograms present standardised values of SES.

The input data distribution is presented in Figure 7.4.6. For soil erosion control the histograms are strongly right-skewed, for climate control (GHG) the distribution is normal platykurtic.

Based on the rasters values distribution, the results of the optimal clusters number were similar to ST:

** Among all indices:*

- * 5 proposed 2 as the best number of clusters*
- * **6 proposed 3 as the best number of clusters***
- * 2 proposed 4 as the best number of clusters*
- * 2 proposed 5 as the best number of clusters*
- * 5 proposed 6 as the best number of clusters*
- * 1 proposed 7 as the best number of clusters*
- * 2 proposed 9 as the best number of clusters*

****** Conclusion ******

** According to the majority rule, the best number of clusters is 3*

The final results on bundles are presented in Figure 7.4.7-7.4.9. The possible solution how to solve the problem of the domination of one ST/SES in cluster analysis was presented on figures 7.4.10-7.4.12.

Figure 7.4.7. The number of pixels in selected clusters for SES.

Soil-Based Ecosystem Services Bundles

Soil-Based Ecosystem Services Bundles

Figure 7.4.8. The maps of SES bundles for Poland.

Figure 7.4.9. The mean of SES values in each of cluster.

We identified three SES Bundles. Similarly, to ST bundles distribution, they are strongly related to the GHG, where values and distribution of erosion control seems omitted. In the Bundle 2 we can observe very high GHG values and low soil erosion (Figure 7.4.9). These areas are located in the north-east Poland and Pomerania region, where the temperatures are lower, and the vegetative season is the shortest (Figure 7.4.8). Bundle 1 is the group of soils with the lowest values of GHG and low soil erosion control. This cluster is located in the south-west of Poland and in the valley bottoms (Figure 7.4.8). Bundle 1 in a big part occurs within the area of the longest vegetative season, and the highest temperatures. In the bundle 3 we can identify the group of soil with medium GHG, and also low rates of soil erosion (Figure 7.4.8 and 7.4.9).

However, due to the inequalities in the inclusion of these two rasters in the clustering process, we did the second approach as an example of solving this problem. We standardized the raster values according to the following formula:

$$x_s = (x - \mu) / \sigma, \text{ where}$$

x_s – standardized value

x – input value

μ – mean value of the ST/SES raster

σ – standard deviation of the ST/SES raster

```
# Calculate mean and standard deviation of the input SES rasters
mean_ghg <- cellStats(GHG2, stat='mean', na.rm=TRUE)
sd_ghg <- cellStats(GHG2, stat='sd', na.rm=TRUE)

mean_ec <- cellStats(Erosion_c2, stat='mean', na.rm=TRUE)
sd_ec <- cellStats(Erosion_c2, stat='sd', na.rm=TRUE)
```

```
# Standardise the SES rasters
GHG_stand <- (GHG2-mean_ec)/sd_ec
Erosion_c_stand <- (Erosion_c2-mean_ghg)/sd_ghg
```

After the transformation, the final result of SES bundles presents as following: of the domination of one SES in cluster analysis was presented on figures 7.4.10-7.4.12.

Figure 7.4.10. The number of pixels in selected clusters for SES.

SES Bundles

Figure 7.4.11. The maps of SES bundles for Poland.

Figure 7.4.12. The mean of SES values in each of the cluster.

Three SES Bundles were identified. The Bundle 1 occurring in the north-east Poland is characterized by the highest climate control (GHG) and low soil erosion control. Second Bundle with the lowest values of GHG and low (but higher than Bundle 1) soil erosion control occurs in the south-west of Poland and the valley bottoms. The smallest representation has the Bundle 3 with the highest erosion control (pastures in the mountains region) and medium values of GHG (Figures 7.4.11 and 7.4.12).

Recommendations

Before the clustering analysis, values of all rasters should be normalized or standardized taking into account the values distribution in all rasters. Due to the extreme right-skewness of soil erosion and soil erosion control, they might have marginal significance in the clustering process. This problem requires further discussion.

The script works very well with harmonized data. There are only a few small corrections that can be done:

- 1) A note should be added to inform users about changing the optimal number of clusters, more specifically:

```
kmeancClust <- KMeans_rcpp(dat,3) #change 5 to your optimal number of clusters
pal10 <- c("#1F78B4", "#B2DF8A", "#FDBF6F") # Add or remove colors, according to the number of clusters
centr <- centr %>%
  mutate(cluster_order = factor(cluster, levels = c(1, 2, 3))) # Add more levels according to the optimal number of clusters
```

- 2) It is worth to add a line to save the final raster (just in case of problems)

```
writeRaster(bundles_pl, "D:/PROJEKTY/SERENA/BUNDLES/bundles_pl.tif", overwrite=TRUE)
```

7.5 Summary and Synthesis

Table 7.5.1. Differences in application between earlier assessment and cookbook. For those MS for which no earlier data were available a summary of the cookbook application is provided.

Member State	Difference type (V, P, V&P)*	Assessment	Soil data	Auxiliary data	Methods	Spatial resolution (m)
Czech Republic	n.a.	cookbook	EU data	EU data	k-means	1 km
Estonia	n.a.	cookbook	Combination of global modified for national conditions, and EU data	EU data	k-means	100 m
Italy (Emilia-Romagna)	V&P	Earlier	Emilia-Romagna Region ESSs	Regional terrain and	A number of different SDM approaches	500

			database (Calzolari et al 2016).	climatic predictors		
		Cookbook	Emilia-Romagna Region updated ESSs database (https://map.pegis.regione.emilia-romagna.it/gstatico/documenti/dati_pedolo/servizi_ecosistemici_suoli.pdf) plus SERENA GHG cookbook	Regional terrain and climatic predictors	A number of different SDM approaches plus spatial transfer	100 (500 nominal)
Poland		Earlier	Not reported in cookbook report			
		Cookbook	National data	Cookbook data	k-means	100 m

*n.a. = not available, S = similar, V = values are different, P = patterns are different

Shortcomings/Recommendations:

- A note should be added to inform users about changing the optimal number of clusters, as this will have an impact on results
- Soil sealing cannot be incorporated in the analysis with the current method. Within the available time frame it was not possible to develop an additional step in which the effects of soil sealing on bundles could be analysed

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8 Summary and synthesis

The developed cookbooks have been applied by a varying number of MS, ranging from just 3 for bundles to 11 for soil erosion. This range is probably influenced by experience and expertise of the different SERENA participants, but also by the moment when the cookbook became available, and by the fact that to evaluate bundles one needs to evaluate individual ST/SES too.

For applications of the same cookbook, variation can also be observed. This is due to reasons such as data availability, expertise, available time. This has consequences for comparison between countries.

At the same time, evaluations were done with a greater degree of similarity between MS than before, and in several cases the cookbook application constituted the first assessment of the ST/SES for specific countries.

Feedback on the cookbook, and the evaluation of ST/SES in general, was also solicited. This resulted in various responses dealing with several subjects, like:

- Technical suggestions for improvement of methodology or cookbook
- That the use of different methods results in different results, and that if the same method is used, the use of different data can result in different results too
- Suggestions for revision of the method used. For example:
 - o For RUSLE there were suggestions to revise several of the factors, to obtain better national values for the different factors, to include other processes and to rely not solely on RUSLE for erosion assessment. Also difficulty in validating results was mentioned
 - o For sealing to use more than one year in the analysis. Also photo-interpretation was found to be very time consuming.
 - o For SOC loss the importance of covariates at appropriate scale/resolution, to use methods that help decide which covariates are most important, to harmonize with EJP SOIL T6.2, to change the indicator to SOC stock loss in the long run
- The importance of harmonizing the rasters that are used as input for the cookbooks (e.g. all the same extent, pixel size etc)
- The need to have flexible thresholds etc to reflect MS context

These suggestions can be used to revise the cookbooks, which will make them of better quality and more suited for applications elsewhere.

Comparison with earlier results proved difficult to the several reasons:

- Different indicators were used in the cookbook compared to the earlier assessment
- Different thresholds or units were used in both applications
- Even if the indicator was the same, different methods were used to obtain values for the indicator
- There was no previous assessment at appropriate scale or place.

Though the factors mentioned above hampered comparison they also highlight the relevance of developing the cookbooks, as the selection of standardised methods should help to overcome several of the factors mentioned above in the future.

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Annexes

Annex 1. Reporting template

ST/SES:

Note: Text in italics provides information on what kind of info is expected, so it is meant for clarification purposes. It can be deleted from the completed report. Length of report 3-4 pages.

Country:

Region (if not national scale):

Elaborated by:

Data used

Category	Description	Resolution ¹	Availability data
<i>Land use</i>	<i>Land use map</i>	<i>100 * 100 m</i>	<i>Can be obtained/downloaded at...</i>
<i>Soil</i>			
<i>Climate</i>			
...			

¹. We assume that raster maps are used. If you use vector maps instead please make this clear in the table and mention the scale of the map here.

Methods

Data preparation

Describe any pre-processing done before data could be used in cookbook application

Application cookbook

No need to repeat the cookbook, but do describe deviations from the cookbook if you adapted the method.

Comparison results

Describe how the results of cookbook application were compared to earlier results, if these are available. Earlier results refer to D3.1.1, but other sources could be used to.

Note that an evaluation with stakeholders is also planned, but this will be part of D1.3. You will be contacted about that evaluation by WP1 later.

Results

Application cookbook

Provide map resulting from cookbook application, with some description and explanation of patterns that are visible. If your map is available online please provide a link.

Comparison

Provide results of comparison with earlier data. Could include map from D3.1.1 as well. Describe differences between the maps, and explain these if possible.

Note that an evaluation with stakeholders is also planned, but this will be part of D1.3. You will be contacted about that evaluation by WP1 later. This evaluation in WP1 will e.g. deal with the following questions: Is the new map an improvement? Why or why not? How realistic are results? Are the thresholds/classes that are used appropriate?

Recommendations

Any suggestions for improvement of the cookbook, based on application and/or on comparison with earlier results? Or on evaluation of this ST/SES in general?

